

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

**Network Slicing in Software Datapaths
for 5G Multi-tenant Networks**

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate this thesis to my beloved wife for her unconditional support, endless encouragement, unlimited patience and advice, not only during this last exciting stage of my life as PhD student, but also throughout the most astonishing and breathtaking journey that no one can ever undertake. The journey that we decided to embark on together many many years ago, united as one soul and one body, the journey of life. Without you everything would have been impossible.

I would also like to dedicate this thesis to my family: siblings, nephews, nieces and family-in-law. Finally, a warm and touching remembrance to my parents. From both of you I learned that with hard work, perseverance and honesty you can achieve your goals and dreams no matter how far away they may seem to be. You taught me that if the road is easy, you are probably going in the wrong direction. I hope that wherever you are, you will be proud of me.

Acknowledgements

I would like to warmly express my most sincere gratitude to my supervisors, Professor Jose Maria Alcaraz Calero and Professor Qi Wang, for their unconditional support throughout my PhD. Their expertise, guidance and advice have made possible to achieve the results presented in this thesis. I would also like to extend my thanks to my research colleagues and friends at UWS, especially to my colleagues in the UWS Beyond 5G Hub research group. More than colleagues, more than friends, I consider you all part of my family. It is a privilege being part of such an exceptional research group, always pushing beyond the boundaries of technology and human knowledge.

Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis and the work presented in it are my own and has been generated by me as the result of my own original research. This thesis contains no material that has been submitted previously, in whole or in part, for the award of any other academic degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements. This dissertation contains more than 10,000 and less than 25,000 words excluding appendices, bibliography, footnotes and tables.

Antonio Matencio Escolar

June 2021

This thesis, based on publications, has been funded by two large European H2020 research projects in which the candidate has been actively involved, carrying out tasks of design, prototyping, implementation and deployment of innovative advanced network control capabilities on software data path in 5G multi-tenant architectures:

- **Project 1:**

Project Title	SliceNet: End-to-end cognitive network slicing and slice management framework in virtualised multi-domain, multi-tenant 5G networks [1]
Horizon 2020 Call Topic Type of action Duration Start date Budget	H2020-ICT-2016-2 ICT-7-2016 RIA - Research and Innovation action 36 Months 01/06/2017 8 million €
Description	SliceNet intends to meet the challenging requirements from the management and control planes of network slicing across multiple administrative domains, facilitating early and smooth adoption of 5G slices for verticals to achieve their demanding use cases, and managing the QoE for slice services. SliceNet follows a layered architectural approach to allow the creation of a modular, extensible and scalable framework.
Partners	University of the West of Scotland (UK) (Technical Leaders) Altice Labs (PT) Cork Institute of Technology (IE) Creative Systems Engineering (GR) Dell EMC (IE) EFACEC Energia (PT) Ericsson Telecomunicazioni SpA (IT) Eurecom (FR) Eurescom (DE) IBM Israel Science and Technology Limited (IL) Nextworks S.R.L (IT) Orange France (FR) Orange Romania (RO) RedZinc Service Ltd. (IE) The Hellenic Telecommunications Organisation S.A. (GR) Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (ES)

- **Project 2:**

Project Title	6G-BRAINS (Bring Reinforcement-learning Into Radio Light Network for Massive Connections) [2]
Horizon 2020 Call Topic Type of action Duration Start date Budget	H2020-ICT-2020-2 ICT-52-2020 - 5G PPP – Smart Connectivity beyond 5G RIA - Research and Innovation action 36 Months 01/01/2021 5.7 million €
Description	6G BRAINS aims to bring AI-driven multi-agent Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to perform resource allocation over and beyond massive machine-type communications with new spectrum links including THz and optical wireless communications (OWC) to enhance the performance with regard to capacity, reliability and latency for future industrial networks.
Partners	University of the West of Scotland (UK) Altran Portugal,SA (PT) Association ISEP - Edouard Branly (FR) Brunel University London (UK) Eurecom (FR) Eurescom (GR) Fraunhofer Gesellschaft E.V. (GR) Oledcomm SAS (FR) Robert Bosch GMBH (GR) Runel NGMT LTD (IL) Telekom Deutschland GMBH (GR) Thales Six GTS France SAS (FR) University of Leicester (UK) Viavi Solutions UK Limited (UK)

The research work presented in this thesis is the aggregation of publications that have been submitted, peer-reviewed, accepted and published in recognised international journals and international conferences and where the PhD candidate is the first and main author. Hence, the PhD candidate confirms that he has made the major contribution to all publications comprising this thesis. The following is a detailed list of the published research outcomes that constitute this thesis (2 journals and 2 conferences):

- **Outcome 1 (Journal):**

Journal	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management
Title	SliceNetVSwitch: Definition, Design and Implementation of 5G Multi-Tenant Network Slicing in Software Data Paths [3]
Authors	Antonio Matencio Escolar, Jose M Alcaraz Calero and Qi Wang
JCR Impact (Journal Citation Report)	3.878
Volume	17
Issue	4 (December 2020)
Pages	14 (2212-2225)
Year of Publication	2020
Electronic ISSN	1932-4537
DOI	10.1109/TNSM.2020.3029653
URL	https://doi.org/10.1109/TNSM.2020.3029653
Contribution	This contribution presents the design, implementation, validation and evaluation of a novel traffic control software datapath with fine-grained network slicing capabilities suitable for 5G multi-tenant networks. First, this publication proposes a novel definition of the scope of network slice flexible enough to embrace the perspective of the different stakeholders involved in 5G. The prototyped solution is able to deal with network traffic with different levels of nested encapsulation present in 5G overlay networks. It provides support to enforce and manage the life cycle of network slices in the software datapath with guaranteed QoS parameters such as bandwidth, latency and jitter. Experiments have been carried to empirically validate and evaluate the proposed solution, achieving promising results in terms of number of slices and fulfillment of the ambitious 5G KPIs. Up to 8192 slices are managed concurrently while ensuring performance isolation in terms of QoS requirements.

- **Outcome 2 (Conference):**

Conference	IEEE ICC 2020 International Conference on Communications WS-16: Workshop on intelligent 5G Network Slicing
Title	Scalable Software Switch Based Service Function Chaining for 5G Network Slicing [4]
Authors	Antonio Matencio Escolar, Jose M Alcaraz Calero and Qi Wang
Australian Conference Ranking	CORE B
Date of Conference	7-11 June 2020
Location	Dublin, Ireland
Electronic ISSN	2474-9133
DOI	10.1109/ICCSWorkshops49005.2020.9145067
URL	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9145067
Contribution	This contribution proposes a Service Function Forwarder (SFF) and classifier with network slicing capabilities for 5G multi-tenant networks. It allows the dynamic deployment of network slices as a chain on network functions, offering tenants and users with catalogues of network services that can be deployed on demand in a automated manner while ensuring performance isolation between slices, i.e. chains of network functions. The proposal solution has been empirically validated and evaluated and the achieved results show that up to 16834 SFC hops can be simultaneously managed in a stressful scenario achieving a bandwidth of 20 Gbps, a maximum delay of 11 microseconds and very high reliability (0% packet loss). Hence, these results indicate that the provided solution meets the QoS requirements and KPIs targeted in 5G networks.

- **Outcome 3 (Conference):**

Conference	IEEE ICC 2020 International Conference on Communications SAC-IOT4 Internet of Things Track
Title	Highly-Scalable Software Firewall Supporting One Million Rules for 5G NB-IoT Networks [5]
Authors	Antonio Matencio Escolar, Jose M Alcaraz Calero and Qi Wang
Australian Conference Ranking	CORE B
Date of Conference Location Electronic ISSN DOI URL	7-11 June 2020 Dublin, Ireland 1938-1883 10.1109/ICC40277.2020.9149152 https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC40277.2020.9149152
Contribution	This paper presents an enhanced software firewall able to provide fine-grained firewall capabilities over 5G NB-IoT devices. The proposed firewall shows high scalability, being able to manage up to 1 million of firewall rules instantiated and 1 million NB-IoT devices sending traffic simultaneously. The proposed firewall has been empirically validated and evaluated and the results of the experiments carried out show promising performance: around 8% packet loss and 4 ms of delay when 1 million devices are simultaneously connected to the same radio interface. This level of scalability is compliant with the 5G KPI expectation and it is suitable for massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC).

• **Outcome 4 (Journal):**

Journal	IEEE Access
Title	Adaptive Network Slicing in Multi-tenant 5G IoT Networks [6]
Authors	Antonio Matencio Escolar Jose M Alcaraz Calero Pablo Salva-Garcia Jorge Bernal Bernabe Qi Wang
JCR Impact (Journal Citation Report)	3.745
Volume	9
Pages	22 (14048-14099)
Year of Publication	2021
Electronic ISSN	2169-3536
DOI	10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3051940
URL	https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3051940
Contribution	<p>This paper presents a highly scalable and effective network slicing frame work for 5G IoT networks, following a SDN approach. The proposed solution is able to support 5G features such as NFV, multi-tenancy and user mobility. It is able to manage simultaneously thousands of heterogeneous slices providing the high scalability demanded in mMTC use cases. Moreover, it supports other 5G use cases such as enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), critical mission communications (uRLLC) or a combination of them. The novel 5G framework proposed has been successfully tested and evaluated in a realistic testbed using five 5G use cases covering the three ITU service categories individually or collectively. The gathered results indicate a high scalability and performance achieved by the framework. In the tests, the implemented framework has been validated to be able to support mMTC traffic of up to 1 million IoT devices, achieve over 15 Gbps eMBB bandwidth, ensure delays in the order of microseconds for uRLLC, whilst providing high reliability in all of the tested scenarios with 0% packet loss ratio. Moreover, it takes only 5.7 ms on average to create a network slice in the data plane for challenging heterogeneous traffic situations.</p>

In addition, the following software projects have been developed to empirically validate and evaluate the research work presented in this thesis. The author's will is to make them public once we have exploited their results in the context of the fore-coming post-doctoral activities, so that they could be share with the scientific community as open source projects and thus allowing the extension and continuation of this research contribution:

- **Outcome 5 (Software):**

Software Project	UWS Slicenet VSwitch
Author	Antonio Matencio Escolar
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/amatencio/uws-ovs
Description	Virtual Switch with network slicing capabilities for multi-tenant 5G networks. It provides a novel software data path able to enforce fine-grained slicing policies defined by the management and control layers and ensures network traffic with customized QoS requirements such as bandwidth, delay, reliability and priority. In terms of scalability, it is able to simultaneously manage up to 8192 slices while delivering 0% packet loss ratio and reaching a bandwidth of 10 Gbps.

- **Outcome 6 (Software):**

Software Project	UWS-NTG (Network Traffic generator)
Authors	Antonio Matencio Escolar
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/amatencio/traffic-generator
Description	This application generates network traffic according to a traffic profile previously defined in JSON format. Additionally to traditional protocols such as MAC, IP, TCP or UDP, it supports tunneling and tagging protocols used in 5G multi-tenant networks, allowing to generate network traffic with different levels of nested encapsulation as expected in 5G. Some of these protocols are VXLAN, GRE-VXLAN, GTP, GENEVE, NSH or MPLS. Each packet can be tagged with an unique ID that identifies it across the whole data plane. For example, it allows to emulate scenarios with heterogeneous traffic where thousands or millions of users (e.g. IoT devices) are sending traffic, each user with a different customized traffic profile (packet size, packet structure, customized L2/L3/L4 headers, customized encapsulated and inner headers fields or Tx Bandwidth.)

- **Outcome 7 (Software):**

Software Project	UWS-PCAP-C (PCAP Compare Tool)
Authors	Antonio Matencio Escolar
URL	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/amatencio/pcap-compare
Description	This tool is able to compare the network traffic captured at different hook points in the 5G data plane. It produces detailed statistics on the performance and behaviour of the network for each network slice (delay, packet loss, jitter and bandwidth). The obtained results are saved in JSON and EXCEL format, easing their analysis by the researcher.

The following publications **have not been included as part of the main core of this thesis** since the candidate is not the main author of them. Nonetheless, these publications are the result of an active collaboration of the candidate in research projects and have been produced and published during the development of this thesis. Moreover, all of them are related to 5G technology and are aligned with the context of the research carried out in this thesis:

- **Outcome 8 (Journal):**

Journal	Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies
Title	Toward hardware-accelerated QoS-aware 5G network slicing based on data plane programmability [7]
Authors	Ruben Ricart-Sanchez Pedro Malagón Antonio Matencio Escolar J. Maria Alcaraz Calero Qi Wang
JCR Impact (Journal Citation Report)	1.258
Volume	31
Issue	1
Pages	19
Year of Publication	2019
Publisher	Wiley
DOI	10.1002/ett.3726
URL	https://doi.org/10.1002/ett.3726

- **Outcome 9 (Conference):**

Conference	2020 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)
Title	An Analysis of Multicast Inefficiencies in Multi-Tenant MEC Infrastructures for 5G Networks [8]
Authors	Steve Eager Antonio Matencio Escolar J. Maria Alcaraz Calero
Australian Conference Ranking	CORE B
Date of Conference Location Electronic ISSN DOI URL	7-11 June 2020 Dublin, Ireland 2474-9133 10.1109/ICCWorkshops49005.2020.9145140 https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCWorkshops49005.2020.9145140

- **Outcome 10 (Conference):**

Conference	2020 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)
Title	Multi-Domain Orchestration of 5G Vertical Services and Network Slices [9]
Authors	Giacomo Bernini Pietro G. Giardina Salvatore Spadaro Fernando Agraz Albert Pagès José Cabaça Pedro Neves Konstantinos Koutsopoulos Antonio Matencio Escolar
Australian Conference Ranking	CORE B
Date of Conference Location Electronic ISSN DOI URL	7-11 June 2020 Dublin, Ireland 2474-9133 10.1109/ICCWorkshops49005.2020.9145221 https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCWorkshops49005.2020.9145221

Finally, as a result of the commitment and active involvement in the successful development of the European H2020 research projects in which this research work has been undertaken, the candidate has contributed, among other tasks, to the release of several technical deliverables as listed below:

- **Outcomes 11 to 14 (project deliverables):**

Project	No.	Deliverable name	Release Date
Slicenet	D3.1 [10]	Design and Prototyping of SliceNet Virtualised Mobile Edge Computing Infrastructure	March 2018
Slicenet	D4.3 [11]	Single-Domain, Multi-Tenant Network Slicing Control	December 2018
Slicenet	D5.6 [12]	Modelling, Design and Implementation of QoE Monitoring, Analytics and Vertical-Informed QoE Actuators; Iteration II	October 2019
Slicenet	D9.3 [13]	Final Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardisation planning and report of activities	June 2020

If the reader is interested in further information, these deliverables are available online at the official website of the Slicenet project (<https://slicenet.eu/deliverables>).

List of Acronyms

1G	First Generation of mobile networks 3
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project 8, 19, 20, 30, 33, 160, 176, 180
4G	Forth Generation of mobile networks 5, 7, 8, 46, 67
5G	Fifth Generation of mobile networks 3–13, 15, 17, 19–24, 26, 27, 29–37, 40, 42–47, 49–51, 54, 56–62, 64, 65, 67–73, 76–79, 81–83
5G-NR	5G New Radio 8, 33
5G-PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership 6, 77
AAU	Active Antenna Unit 20
ACO	Ant Colony Algorithm 125
AMF	Access and Mobility Functions 19
API	Application Programming Interface 45, 49, 51, 78, 102, 128, 165, 168, 174, 176, 179
AR	Augmented Reality 184, 185
ASDS	Automated Scenario Deployment Script 190, 191
AUSF	Authentication Server Functions 19, 20
BS	Base Station 182
C-RAN	Cloud-RAN 17, 20, 34
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures 8, 22, 89, 138, 172
CN	Core Network 31
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf 8, 95
CP	Control Plane 22, 36, 44, 51, 159
CPU	Central Process Unit 111, 131, 188
CSC	Communication Service Customer 30
CSP	Communication Service Provider 30
CU	Centralized Unit 19, 20, 96
DP	Data Plane 10, 22, 27, 34–36, 43, 44, 52, 54, 60, 64, 79
DPAS	Data Plane Abstraction Service 168, 170, 174, 176, 179, 190, 201
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit 78, 98, 99, 203
DPI	Deep Packet Inspection 122
DSCP	Differentiated Service Code Point 26, 94, 100, 107, 108, 120
DSLS	Dynamic Spectrum-Level Slicing 34
DSP	Digital Service Providers 94

DU	Distributed Unit 17, 19, 20, 95, 97
E2E	End to End 9, 19, 24, 32–36, 89, 94, 96
eBPF	Extended Berkeley Packet Filter 79, 99
ECN	Explicit Congestion Notification 26
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broad Band Communications 5, 6, 11, 13, 14, 19, 35, 40, 47, 77, 82, 88, 155, 158, 159, 162, 163, 181, 182, 184, 185, 194, 195, 203
EMS	Element Management System 166
EPC	Evolved Packet Core 34
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute 5, 31, 35, 124, 180
EU	European Union 4
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array 35, 82, 100, 174
GBP	Group Based Policy 125
GENEVE	Generic Networking Virtualization Encapsulation 135, 173, 175
gNB	gNodeB 23, 89, 173
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service 139
GRE	Generic Routing Encapsulation 44, 56, 103, 104, 135, 173, 175
GSMA	Global System for Mobile Communications Association 31, 91
GTP	GPRS Tunneling Protocol 23, 44, 56, 58, 67, 104, 109, 110, 126, 128, 139, 140, 156, 160, 173–175, 186
H-NOMA	Heterogeneous Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access 33
HD	High Definition 184
HDD	Hard Disk Drive 188
HTB	Hierarchical Token Bucket 45, 62, 108, 179
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning 184
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force 92, 124, 176
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things 154, 183
IoT	Internet of Things 3–5, 10, 40, 42, 47, 54, 69, 71, 77, 82, 138, 140, 154–163, 172–177, 179, 181–185, 187, 189–192, 194–199, 201–203
IP	Internet Protocol 12, 20, 26, 46, 89, 93, 98, 100, 102, 104, 105, 107, 113, 114, 120, 128, 131, 138, 174, 184, 186
IPC	Inter-Process Communication 78
ISP	Infrastructure Service Provider 9, 12, 17, 21, 25, 26, 30, 94, 122
ITU	International Telecommunication Union 4, 6, 13, 19, 30, 33–36, 47, 69, 82, 88, 89, 181, 188, 203
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation 190
KPI	Key Performance Indicator 6, 10, 14, 27, 35–37, 40, 65, 70, 77, 78, 82, 132, 135, 138, 203
KPPS	Kilo Packets Per Second 140

LPWA	Low Power Wide Area 182
LTE	Long-Term Evolution 7, 33, 46, 67, 93, 98, 113, 140
LTE-A	Long Term Evolution Advanced 140
LTE-M	Long Term Evolution for Machines 4, 140
MAB	Maximum Allowed Bandwidth 171, 186, 187, 194
MAC	Media Access Control 33, 128, 186
MANO	Management and Network Orchestration 35, 96, 124, 125
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing 8, 9, 19, 23, 35, 95, 159, 160, 163
MEM	Metadata Extractor Module 128
MGB	Minimum Guaranteed Bandwidth 171, 186, 187, 194
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output 7
mIoT	Massive Internet of Things 36, 159
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communications 4, 6, 11, 13, 14, 19, 40, 47, 69, 71, 72, 77, 82, 88, 154–156, 159, 162, 163, 181, 182, 184, 192, 195, 199, 203
mmWave	millimeter waves 8
MNO	Mobile Network Operator 7, 12, 19–21, 30, 54, 92, 122, 125
MP3	MPEG Audio Layer-3 184
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching 26
NAT	Network Address Translation 122
NB-IoT	Narrow Band Internet of Things 4, 13, 46, 54, 56, 68, 76, 82, 120, 138–140, 159
NBI	North Bound Interface 10, 27, 44, 61, 124, 165, 168, 170, 176, 201
NF	Network Function 19, 189, 191
NFaaS	Network Function as a Service 8
NFV	Network Function Virtualization 8, 9, 14, 19, 27, 31, 35, 42, 68, 79, 82, 89, 124, 125, 158, 172, 174, 183
NFVI	Network Functions Virtualization Infrastructure 124
NGMN	Next Generation Mobile Network 5, 30, 91, 123, 133
NIC	Network Interface Card 22, 57, 62, 63, 71, 83, 97, 100, 126, 141, 174
NMS	Network Management System 166
NR	New Radio 138, 180
NS	Network Service 31, 124
NSaaS	Network Slice as a Service 30, 31
NSH	Next Service Header 56, 59, 68, 76, 125, 126, 130
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function 160, 180
OAI	Open Air Interface 34, 35
ODL	Open DayLight 123, 124
OF	Open Flow 12, 23, 44, 45, 51, 57, 58, 62, 76–78, 124
ONF	Open Networking Foundation 31, 124
ONOS	Open Network Operating System 125
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications United Architecture 160

OPEX	Operational Expenditures 8, 22, 89, 138, 172
OVS	Open Virtual Switch 44–46, 57, 58, 64, 67, 77, 78, 88, 90, 100, 102, 110, 111, 113, 114, 120, 122, 123, 125, 131, 157, 158, 163, 174–176
OVSDB	Open vSwitch Database Management Protocol 124
PCAP	Packet Capture 112, 113, 131, 146, 191
PCF	Policy Charging Function 19, 20
PCRF	Policy and Charging Rules Function 93
PHB	Per-Hop Behaviour 26
PIoT	Power Internet of Things 158
PPS	Packets Per Second 40, 78, 99, 197
PTP	Precision Time Protocol 188
QoE	Quality of Experience 25
QoS	Quality of Service 4, 9–11, 15, 17, 19, 20, 22, 24–27, 33, 35–37, 40, 42, 44–46, 51, 52, 54, 56, 60, 61, 69–71, 77, 78, 81, 82, 88–90, 92–94, 98–100, 110, 128, 135, 154, 155, 157–160, 173, 174, 176–180, 183, 185, 191, 197, 199, 202, 203
RAM	Random Access Memory 111, 131, 188
RAN	Radio Access Network 9, 31–35, 37, 92, 159, 173
RAT	Radio Access Technology 30, 33
REST	Representational State Transfer 176
RFC	Request For Comments 124
RSVP	Resource Reservation Protocol 25
SBA	Service Based Architecture 163
SCA	Slice Control Agent 165, 168, 170, 174, 176, 178–180, 190, 201, 202
SCSI	Small Computer System Interface 188
SCTP	Stream Control Transmission Protocol 99
SDN	Software Defined Networks 10, 11, 22, 23, 27, 31, 33–36, 42, 44, 50–52, 56, 60–62, 77, 79, 89, 100–102, 124, 125, 158, 159, 163, 165, 168, 172, 174, 176, 179, 189, 201
SDO	Standardization Development Organization 5, 11, 29, 30, 160, 176, 177, 180
SDP	Service Data Plane 126
SF	Service Function 47, 68, 122, 124, 126–128, 130, 134
SFC	Service Function Chain 12, 13, 33, 45, 46, 54, 56, 59, 68, 76, 82, 122, 124–128, 130, 131, 133–135
SFF	Service Function Forwarder 46, 68, 82, 122, 124–128, 131, 134
SLA	Service Level Agreement 9, 10, 15, 25, 26, 30, 33, 36, 44, 51, 54, 100, 155, 163, 186, 190, 194, 197, 199
SMF	Session Management Functions 20
SSD	Solid State Drive 111, 131
STT	Stateless Transport Protocol 135, 173

TC	Linux Traffic Control 99
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol 99, 120
TEID	Tunnel Endpoint Identifier 59, 109, 110, 128, 174
TGA	Traffic Generator Agent 112
TOS	Type of Service 26
TSP	Telecommunication Service Provider 172
UDM	Unified Data Management 19, 20
UDP	User Datagram Protocol 99, 186
UE	User Equipment 19, 23, 34, 90, 92, 95, 161
UHD	Ultra High Definition 99
UP	User Plane 36, 159
UPF	User Plane Function 20, 23, 90, 96, 97, 172, 173
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications 5, 6, 11, 13, 14, 19, 35, 40, 47, 63, 69, 77, 82, 88, 89, 154, 155, 159, 162, 163, 181–183, 185, 192, 194, 195, 198, 203
v2X	Vehicle to Everything 35
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager 166
VLAN	Virtual Local Area Network 103
VM	Virtual Machine 8, 9, 22, 24, 96, 97, 174, 189
VNF	Virtual Network Function 9, 14, 19, 22, 33, 79, 124, 165, 166
VNFO	Virtual Network Function Orchestrator 166
VNI	VXLAN Network Identifier 59, 109, 128, 174
VNO	Virtual Network Operator 19, 21, 22
VR	Virtual Reality 184
VXLAN	Virtual Extensible Local Area Network 44, 56, 59, 67, 103, 104, 110, 128, 156, 160, 173–175, 186
VXLAN-GPE	Generic Protocol Extension for VXLAN 68, 128
XDP	eXpress Data Path 78, 99, 203

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Abstract

5G is reshaping the current landscape in mobile networks, opening up new business opportunities. Mobile industry can now address use cases that are not feasible for 4G technology due to the strict requirements demanded in terms of delay, reliability, bandwidth, scalability and high connection density. This will enable to address the requirements of challenging eMBB, URLLC and mMTC use cases in highly dynamic and evolving environments.

To meet this ambitious QoS requirements, the evolution from 4G to 5G has imposed the shift to a new paradigm, leaving behind the static architectures based on the "one-size-fits-all" approach commonly used by 4G and its precursors, bringing a SBA with the ability to address the specific requirements of vertical industry to customer segments. ISPs are facing significant financial investments to adapt their networks to this new landscape, devising new business models in a growing and dynamic global telecommunication market. 5G relies on virtualization and softwarization, using technologies such as SDN and NFV as key enablers, leading to a reduction in both CAPEX and OPEX. Softwarization and virtualization facilitate the deployment of multi-tenant networks in which several tenants share the same physical infrastructure. In this context, network slicing has emerged as a cornerstone technology, enabling the deployment of different virtualized logical networks running on top of the same physical network while providing network isolation performance between tenants and guaranteeing QoS requirements.

The notion of network slicing is an E2E concept that entails its implementation in all segments throughout the 5G network. This represents a significant challenge due to the complexity of 5G networks. This research work aims to deliver network slicing capabilities in the Edge-Core segment, more precisely in the software datapath, which is responsible

for connecting the virtual machines with the common shared physical network. To this end, this research work proposes a novel software datapath able to handle all types of network traffic envisioned in 5G networks, including encapsulated traffic inherent to multi-tenant 5G networks. This solution is based on SDN principles, providing the control and management layers with extended programmability beyond the current state of the art.

The proposed solution has been designed, prototyped, validated, and evaluated in the context of the H2020 5G-PPP Phase II SliceNet project. Its suitability has been empirically tested in the edge-core segment of a realistic 5G multi-tenant architecture where promising results in terms of bandwidth, delay, reliability, and scalability have been achieved. The prototype has been successfully applied to cope with different scenarios such as security in 5G NB-IoT networks, network slicing support for SFC in VNF and network slicing for heterogeneous traffic in 5G IoT networks.

In the security use case, the solution operates as a firewall for NB-IoT traffic, being able to simultaneously deal with traffic from 1 million devices while achieving a bandwidth of 4 Gbps and 8% of packet loss. In the SFC scenario, the datapath software adopts the role of SFF agent with network slicing capabilities, being able to cope with 16384 SFC hops at 20 Gbps while delivering a maximum delay of 11 microseconds and no packet loss. Finally, in the most stressful scenario, the proposed solution simultaneously copes with heterogeneous traffic from 5 IoT use cases representing all 3 ITU categories or a combination. The gathered results demonstrate that this novel software datapath guarantees performance isolation between slices while meeting the stringent 5G KPIs. It provides high levels of scalability for mMTC traffic (up to 1 million devices), ultra-high reliability and ultra-low latency for delay-sensitive critical-mission traffic (0% packet loss ratios and delay in the order of microseconds) while reaching peaks of 15 Gbps for eMBB use cases. These promising outcomes indicate the feasibility of the proposed solution for the software segment of the 5G DP with the aim of delivering E2E network slicing capabilities in 5G multi-tenant networks and, thus, satisfying the demanding QoS requirements foreseen in 5G use cases.

Part I

Summary

Chapter 1

Introduction

Mobile technology has evolved substantially since its initial roll-out 40 years ago, in the early 1980s. As illustrated in Fig. 1.1, since the release of First Generation of mobile networks (1G), a new generation of wireless mobile technology has been released roughly every 10 years [14]. With each new generation, with each new technological evolution, the customers have enjoyed a better user experience and a wider range of services. From simply voice or text messaging at the beginning of the mobile age to the myriad of new services promised by Fifth Generation of mobile networks (5G) technology. The massive deployment of 5G communication networks is enabling unforeseeable levels of connectivity, transforming economic sectors such as healthcare, agriculture, energy and transportation, just to mention a few of the most relevant ones [15]. 5G coupled with Internet of Things (IoT) is playing a key role in the successful development of Smart Cities, promising the scalability and high performance levels necessary to deploy large-scale IoT scenarios with millions of devices, sensors and users interconnected throughout vast urban areas [16]. According to the latest *Ericsson Mobility Report* [17], there were 220 million 5G subscribers by the end of 2020 across the globe. Furthermore, their projection is that by the end of 2026 there will be 3.5 billion 5G subscribers, accounting for 40% of the worldwide mobile market at that time and covering around 60% of the world's population.

From an economic viewpoint, 5G unlocks a wide range of commercial opportunities, bringing new business models that will have a huge social and economic impact worldwide.

Fig. 1.1 From 1G to 5G: Evolution of mobile networks. A new generation launched roughly every 10 years providing new services and higher transmission rates.

A recent study published by the World Economic Forum [18] estimates that 5G industry will generate an economic value of \$13.2 trillion while creating 22.3 million jobs by 2035. Focusing on Europe, according to a report carried out by Tech4i2 [19] for the European Union (EU), the estimated cost of 5G deployment in EU Member States is €56.6 billion. The impact and benefits of this forecast are straightforward: investment in 5G will create 2.39 million jobs and a potential economic output of €141.8 billion in EU Members States.

5G provides support for numerous and diverse new tailored services demanded by a wide range of business verticals such as Tele-surgery, Smart Manufacturing, Industry 4.0 or Smart Agriculture. These new use cases and scenarios envisioned by 5G impose diverse extreme Quality of Service (QoS) requirements in terms of bandwidth, delay, reliability as well as demanding high scalability, novel security mechanisms and flexibility [20]. A detailed analysis of the specific requirements of these verticals has led the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) [21] to consider three main categories of traffic as described below:

- **Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC):** This category of traffic is associated with large-scale IoT deployments such as Long Term Evolution for Machines (LTE-M) or Narrow Band Internet of Things (NB-IoT) scenarios. This type of service does not impose extreme requirements in terms of latency or reliability. Nonetheless, the major challenge to be addressed is to provide support for an extremely high connec-

tion density in scenarios where millions of IoT devices and sensors are simultaneously interconnected.

- **Enhanced Mobile Broad Band Communications (eMBB):** eMBB can be considered as a natural evolution of Forth Generation of mobile networks (4G) that will provide faster data rates and a improved user experience. Depending on the use case, eMBB will need to adapt to different scenarios providing higher capacity for broadband access in densely crowded areas , enhanced connectivity and higher user mobility in moving vehicles.
- **Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC):** this category of service, also termed critical-mission services, covers applications and use cases having stringent requirements for ultra low latency and high reliability. These extreme requirements are a major challenge in the design of 5G systems but they are crucial to enable critical-mission applications such as remote healthcare, intelligent transportation systems or smart grids.

Providing solutions flexible enough to be capable of handling all these traffic categories while meeting their diverse and demanding requirements is a major challenge that 5G industry has to tackle. Furthermore, the landscape foreseen by 5G is even more complex and challenging, since these solutions have to be deployed in infrastructures where all these categories of traffic are present concurrently and even use cases in which the traffic profile is a hybrid combination of them. This challenging need for flexible and robust solutions suitable for handling multitude of use cases with diverse extreme requirements is the main motivation driving this research wok, which presents a novel solution to address this gap in a specific segment of the data plane of 5G networks: the software datapath.

These requirements demanded by this new scenarios foreseen in 5G are measurable and are a quantifiable metric to reflect the 5G network performance and how well the needs of the users and industrial verticals are fulfilled. They have been defined and published by technological industries and Standardization Development Organizations (SDOs) such as Nokia [22], Next Generation Mobile Network (NGMN) [23], European Telecommunications

Fig. 1.2 Qualitative relevance of different KPIs for ITU service categories

Standards Institute (ETSI) [24] or 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP) [25]. These metrics, related to as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), capture a variety of dimensions of the network performance such as peak data rate, bandwidth, control plane latency, user plane latency, reliability, mobility, connection density, energy efficiency, etc. Among all the targeted KPIs, bandwidth, latency, reliability and scalability are the ones that the research work presented in this thesis contributes to achieve by providing a novel enhanced Software Datapath suitable for 5G multi-tenant networks. Regarding user plane latency, ITU sets minimum End-to-End latency requirements of 1 ms for URLLC and 4 ms for eMBB, with no value specified for mMTC use cases since these are not latency-sensitive services. For scalability, ITU establishes a minimum supported connection density of 1 million devices in mMTC usage scenarios. High data rates are required to deliver enhanced user experience in eMBB use cases deployed in dense urban environments. To this end, ITU proposes ambitious KPI values of 100 Mbps for downlink and 50 Mbps for uplink. Finally, reliability, meaning the success probability of transmitting traffic within a required maximum time, is an extreme requirement in critical-mission URLLC use cases where ITU proposes an ultra high reliability of $1-10^{-5}$ (99.999 %). Fig. 1.2 illustrates in a qualitative fashion the most relevant KPIs established for each of the 3 ITU service categories.

These ambitious KPIs require significant investigation to achieve improvements and enhancements of current networks solutions to make them ready for next-generation networks. Such improvements and enhancements are in the scope of this research work. 5G must cater to an evolving mobile market in continuous and rapid expansion. This fascinating and challenging new landscape is composed of a rapidly growing number of interconnected subscribers, verticals and devices demanding a plethora of heterogeneous services requiring high performance requirements that need to be deployed and managed in a dynamic, agile and simultaneous way. Meeting these extreme requirements will be a technological challenge that Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) will have to cope with.

Existing 4G infrastructures are reliant on expensive specific hardware, following the "one-size-fits-all" paradigm where dedicated networks are deployed to fulfill specific use cases, thus making upgrade and management tasks hard to carry out. Tasks such as deployment of new services, changes in network topology or network devices configuration are performed manually by engineers. This is costly not only from an economic perspective but also in terms of the amount of time taken to accomplish such tasks, constraining the flexibility of the network to adapt dynamically on demand to the extreme and diverse needs of the new use cases and services envisaged. It seems clear that it is needed a shift towards a new technological paradigm able to respond to the expectations of a growing mobile phone business. Hence, MNOs are investing and researching to remodel and upgrade all segments of the current 4G network infrastructures based on Long-Term Evolution (LTE) technology and evolve towards 5G [26].

The economic effort undertaken by the mobile industry is reflected in a remarkable number of technological innovations and new standards spanning different network domains. The application of Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) on a larger scale, known as Massive MIMO [27], involves the deployment of a larger number of antennas and is a game-changing technology to achieve high scalability in the radio segment. Combined with antenna techniques such as beamforming [28], Massive MIMO increases significantly connection capacity and network efficiency in densely crowded urban areas without requiring more spectrum. It also enables improved coverage and makes mobile networks more resistant to

interference enabling an enhanced user experience. The new air interface defined by Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), named 5G New Radio (5G-NR) [29], makes use of the millimeter waves (mmWave) frequency band [30], which covers a range between 24 GHz and 100 GHz. Although the use of mmWave entails drawbacks such as short range, susceptibility to interference and difficulties for indoor penetration, its deployment allows high-speed communications (in the order of Gbps) and low latency. Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) is an emerging technology that extends computing and cloud services accommodation to the edge of the network, closer to the end user to improve latency and save bandwidth [31].

1.1 Problem Statement

By decoupling network capabilities from the underlying hardware, virtualization and softwarization are considered a cornerstone paradigm in the design of 5G networks [32]. By means of key technologies such as Network Function Virtualization (NFV) [33], the benefits of adopting softwarization and virtualization in the deployment of 5G infrastructures are manifold. In virtualized infrastructures, services and applications run on Virtual Machines (VMs) allocated on Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) equipment instead of more expensive dedicated hardware, contributing to reduce both Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditures (OPEX). Virtualization also provides a high degree of flexibility by means of a flexible VM placement and migration to other physical servers. Thus, the provision of new services implies the creation of virtualized abstractions of computers (as VMs), network resources, operating systems, network interfaces or storage devices, not requiring additional effort from a hardware perspective. NFV enables agile and automated deployment of virtual network services such as firewalls or load balancers that have traditionally been run on proprietary hardware, allowing Network Function as a Service (NFaaS).

Unlike 4G, where network devices and interfaces are physical components, the use of softwarization and virtualization (i.e. NFV) in 5G implies the deployment of virtualized network components (e.g. virtual switches). The role of these virtual switches is to connect

the Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) running on VMs to the physical network components (e.g. network cards). This leads to the concept of software datapath which represents the logical connection implemented in software between the VMs and the physical network interfaces.

NFV poses major challenges that need to be addressed. One of them is the need to allow multiple virtualized and/or softwarized network functions to compete for the hardware resources available on the physical machine. Hence, this scenario entails an important endeavor in achieving the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and QoS requirements across all the functions being concurrently executed in the same machine and competing for the same available resources. Besides, multi-tenant 5G infrastructures involve the use of overlay networks to deploy a virtualized logical network for each tenant. The Infrastructure Service Provider (ISP) is required to ensure performance isolation between tenants, which implies coping with traffic with different levels of nested encapsulation characteristic of overlay networks. This challenges are the main focus and motivation of the research work presented in this thesis.

Furthermore, 5G architectures are based on an End to End (E2E) concept where different domains are involved including Radio Access Network (RAN), fronthaul, midhaul, MEC, transport, core or backbone just to name some of the most important ones. Thus, the competition problem previously mentioned is exacerbated as it has to be addressed from an E2E perspective to avoid bottlenecks across the whole 5G infrastructure.

In such a complex scenario, meeting the ambitious QoS requirements promised by 5G is a major challenge in its design and roll-out. In this context, Network Slicing has emerged as a core technology playing a crucial role in the control of the networks resources all across the network segments and all across the physical, softwarized and virtualized infrastructures. Network Slicing allows the creation of multiple virtualized logical networks on top of the same physical network that are customized to meet the specific SLAs and requirements of users, services, applications and operators. To truly achieve this, all network domains must provide network slicing capabilities including RAN, Fronthaul, Edge, Transport, Core and Backbone.

1.2 Objectives and scope of this thesis

1.2.1 Aim

The main goal of this research work is to design, prototype, develop and empirically validate and evaluate a novel software data path with fine-grained network slicing capabilities suitable for 5G multi-tenant networks. This contribution can meet the demanding KPIs required in 5G related to QoS features such as bandwidth, delay, reliability and scalability. Furthermore, the novel traffic control solution proposed in this research work must be deployed and integrated in virtualized and softwarized environments as those foreseen in 5G multi-tenant infrastructures. Therefore, it should accomplish the Software Defined Networks (SDN) paradigm, exposing a North Bound Interface (NBI) with efficient novel control and programmability capabilities to the control and management planes, allowing to enforce network slices in the Data Plane (DP) to satisfy the QoS requirements agreed in the SLAs.

1.2.2 Research questions

The research work presented in this thesis investigates novel mechanisms that enable efficient traffic control in the software data plane to meet the diverse and demanding requirements in 5G. Due to the huge complexity of 5G networks in general and of the 5G data plane in particular, this thesis has required a multidisciplinary work covering different areas of network engineering such as QoS, IoT, network protocols, network control and management and network security.

Several key questions arise at the time of conducting this thesis. The answer to these questions is crucial to, first, a thorough understanding of the problem being addressed and, second, provide a solution that successfully fulfills the ambitious aim set out in this thesis:

- **Question 1:** What are the key architectural, performance, efficiency and design aspects to consider when developing a novel software data path with network slicing functionalities suitable for 5G multi-tenant networks?

- **Question 2:** How can the concept of network slicing be applied and integrated into novel network traffic control solutions to provide guaranteed QoS services in the data plane for 5G multi-tenant networks?
- **Question 3:** What network protocols, packet structure and traffic profile are expected to be found in virtualized and softwarized networks such as 5G multi-tenant infrastructures and what implications does it have on the design of a novel software data path suitable for this kind of networks?
- **Question 4:** How should the current programmability of network control be extended to enforce guaranteed QoS in overlay networks such as 5G multi-tenant networks?
- **Question 5:** What levels of scalability should a network traffic control solution provide to achieve the ambitious requirements of the different types of services envisioned in 5G networks such as eMBB, URLLC and mMTC?
- **Question 6:** How to empirically validate and evaluate the feasibility of a novel software data path solution with network slicing capabilities to meet the requirements of users and verticals in the new use cases foreseen in 5G networks?

1.2.3 Research Objectives

To successfully achieve the challenging aim outlined above, a number of specific, measurable and feasible objectives have been identified and targeted as follows:

- **Objective 1:** To collect and analyze the current state in the literature of the following topics related to this research work: software data paths, network traffic control, 5G architecture, SDN technology and network slicing. The purpose of this task is to identify the requirements that a software data path implementation should satisfy to contribute to deliver End-to-End network slicing throughout all the segments of the 5G network. The standards released by SDOs and industrial proposals will be analyzed as well to align the outcome of this work with them.

- **Objective 2:** To provide a precise, accurate yet flexible definition of the network slice concept within the scope of network traffic over the datapath. This definition must be flexible enough to cover all the possible kinds of network traffic that a 5G multi-tenant network has to deal with. This implies that the proposed definition has to cover traffic inherent to 5G overlay networks where different levels of nested encapsulation are used to ensure tenant isolation and user mobility across the 5G infrastructure. Moreover, this definition must embrace and satisfy the network slicing perspective of the different stakeholders involved in a 5G multi-tenant network (ISPs, MNOs, vertical business).
- **Objective 3:** To design and implement a new and efficient flow dissector able to identify network traffic flows with the necessary granularity to match the network slice definition previously proposed in objective 2. Unlike traditional Internet Protocol (IP) traffic classifiers, the developed algorithm must handle encapsulation and tunneling protocols and it has to be able to extract meta-data from nested inner headers that will allow a tailored fine-grained identification of the 5G network traffic.
- **Objective 4:** Extend the Open Flow (OF) protocol with new fields and actions matching the information gathered by the flow dissector developed in objective 3. This extension will enhance OF, providing the necessary expressiveness so that the control and management layer can enforce flexible and fine-grained network slicing policies within the data plane according to the definition of network slice proposed in objective 2.
- **Objective 5:** To create a novel software data path based on integrating the outcomes of objectives 2, 3 and 4 and extending a defacto well-known virtual switch, such as Open VSwitch (OVS). The result will be able to effectively enforce network slices in the data path with tailored QoS requirements and complying with the levels of flexibility and accuracy of the network slice definition proposed in objective 2. The network slicing capabilities will be empirically validated and evaluated in a realistic 5G scenario, demonstrating its suitability for 5G multi-tenant networks.
- **Objective 6:** To extend the capabilities of the data plane by adding Service Function Chain (SFC) capabilities with the aim to allow network services linked and ordered

in a proper way to address specific use case requirements. These enhanced SFC capabilities will empower SDN/NFV with network slicing capabilities in 5G multi-tenant infrastructures.

- **Objective 7:** To demonstrate the scalability of the traffic control functionality of the proposed software data path solution in challenging use cases. In particular, a high-scalable NB-IoT firewall will be prototyped to handle up to 1 million rules simultaneously and the corresponding performance will be analyzed.
- **Objective 8:** To demonstrate the versatility of the novel software data path with network slicing capabilities developed in objective 5 and 6. To achieve so, an exhaustive empirical validation will be carried out to cope with different simultaneous use case with diverse demanding QoS requirements. To be concrete, the proposed solution will be evaluated with 5 simultaneous IoT uses cases, covering the service categories defined by ITU or a combination of them: URLLC, eMBB and mMTC. These 5 scenarios will impose challenging requirements in terms of scalability, bandwidth, delay and reliability. The use cases will be used to analyze the effectiveness of the network slicing solution proposed for 5G multi-tenant networks.

		Research question					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Objective	1	1,2,3,4	1,2,3,4	1,2,3,4	1,2,3,4		
	2	1	1				
	3			1			
	4				1		
	5		1				
	6			2			
	7					3	3
	8	4		4		4	4

Table 1.1 Mapping between objectives and research questions. The number(s) in each cell indicates the outcome(s) where each objective has been fulfilled and published as described in Table 1.2.

Table 1.1 shows how the aforementioned objectives match with the research questions raised in subsection 1.2.2, and how these objectives, by answering such questions, contribute

Outcome Number	Title	Chapter	Reference
1	SliceNetVSwitch: Definition, Design and Implementation of 5G Multi-Tenant Network Slicing in Software Data Paths	9	[3]
2	Scalable Software Switch Based Service Function Chaining for 5G Network Slicing	10	[4]
3	Highly-Scalable Software Firewall Supporting One Million Rules for 5G NB-IoT Networks	11	[5]
4	Adaptive Network Slicing in Multi-tenant 5G IoT Networks	12	[6]

Table 1.2 Outcomes: Title, chapter of the second part containing the publication and bibliographical reference

to the requirements analysis, design, prototyping and implementation of the solution provided in this research work and defined as the ultimate aim of this thesis. The successful accomplishment of the defined objectives can be verified throughout the four outcomes comprising the core of this thesis. The reader can observe in Table 1.1 how each of the objectives and research questions has been achieved and published in associated outcomes. The details of each outcome are explained in Table 1.2.

1.3 Innovations

The main innovation of this research work is focused on providing network slicing capabilities in all the involved network segments that contain softwarized and/or virtualized NFVs, to be precise the software datapath in the Edge and the Core network segments of the 5G network, those responsible for inter-connecting VNFs to the physical infrastructure. Such ambitious network slicing capabilities will address the three different categories of traffic envisioned for 5G networks (eMBB, URLLC, mMTC) and also a concurrent combination of multiple of them running at the same time on the same infrastructure. The proposed solution will also meet all the ambitious KPIs envisioned for 5G in terms of latency, bandwidth, density, scalability and reliability and all the challenges associated to achieve that purpose.

It has provided the following key innovations:

- To provide a flexible enough formal definition of network slicing to allow: i) its implementation in all the diverse and heterogeneous deployment scenarios envisioned for 5G infrastructure. ii) the coverage of the significantly divergent views on the scope of network slicing provided by the different stakeholders which are involved in 5G multi-tenant networks such as ISPs, MNOs, SDOs or vertical businesses.
- To propose a novel network traffic classification approach that allows the maximum flexibility to define the scope of network slices in 5G networks, including advanced scenarios such as: virtualized environment, multi-tenant environment and MEC environments.
- To propose novel traffic control mechanisms to guarantee the QoS requisites (bandwidth, latency, reliability, jitter, security) of the SLAs that need to be provided on each of the network slices, ensuring performance and security protection capabilities.
- To extend the management and control interfaces of the software datapath to allow the novel network traffic classification and control mechanism previously described to be applied in the relevant network segments.
- To achieve the expected 5G KPIs and to provide support of network slicing for all the proposed 5G use cases, including dealing with complex and concurrent 5G use cases scenarios and dealing with a large number of slices.

Current software datapath solutions lack several or all of these aforementioned features. Filling this gap with an original research contribution is the main motivation behind the research work presented in this thesis. Thus, the main goal of this thesis is the design, prototyping, implementation and empirical validation and evaluation of a novel software datapath enhanced with fine-grained network slicing functionalities for the edge-to-core network segment of 5G multi-tenant networks.

1.4 Structure of this thesis

From an organizational viewpoint, this thesis consists of two differentiated parts. The first part is composed of the chapters belonging to the thesis and it is organized in nine chapters, including this introductory chapter. Chapter 2 contextualizes and familiarizes the reader with a brief overview of architectural concepts, technologies, protocols and terminology related to the scope of this thesis. Next, Chapter 3 provides a literature review of technologies involved in this work, highlighting the current status of network slicing and software datapaths. Then, Chapter 4 provides the reader with a clear understanding of the methodological approach followed to conduct this thesis. Chapter 5 describes technical and architectural details of the design and implementation of the novel software datapath solution proposed. Following this, chapter 6 discusses the achieved results that have been empirically validated and evaluated and published in international journals and conferences comprising the core of this portfolio-based thesis. Chapter 7 performs a deep critical analysis, discussing the strengths and weaknesses of this work, describing the problems and challenges faced during this thesis and how they have been solved or mitigated. To conclude the first part of this thesis, chapter 8 outlines the conclusions reached and proposes future lines of research to continue and further extend the work presented in this document. Lastly, The second part of this document consists of four chapters (9 to 12) and includes the publications peer-reviewed, accepted and published in international journals and conferences comprising the core of this portfolio-based thesis.

Chapter 2

Background

The main purpose of this chapter is to introduce the reader with technologies, concepts and terminology related to 5G networks and therefore commonly used throughout this thesis. This chapter is not a literature review nor does it intend to introduce any novel contribution. Rather, it is aimed at providing the reader with a thorough understanding that will allow them to approach the remaining chapters with a clear global vision of 5G infrastructures. In particular, this chapter focuses on aspects concerning the software datapath segment of 5G such as overlay networks, traffic control and QoS mechanisms.

2.1 5G Infrastructure

The term infrastructure refers to the physical components needed for the operation of the ISPs. These components, interconnected and deployed in facilities geographically dispersed, comprise diverse equipment such as small cells, towers, computers, storage devices or network devices. Fig. 2.1 provides an overall view of the multi-tenant 5G infrastructure and architecture employed in this research work. As it can be noticed, 5G infrastructures are composed by three main network segments clearly differentiated and geographically distributed: Cloud-RAN (C-RAN), Edge and Core.

First, at the bottom of Fig. 2.1 the C-RAN segment is located. The C-RAN segment consist of two components: remote radio access points termed Distributed Units (DUs) and

Fig. 2.1 5G multi-tenant architecture overview

pools of Centralized Units (CUs). The DUs are responsible to provide wireless connectivity to User Equipments (UEs) whereas the CUs, allocated in pools at the Edge of the network, offer high computational and storage performance. In this way, the logical functionality of 5G gNBs (eNBs in 4G-LTE) is split between CUs and DUs. CUs process physical layer protocols and real time services while CUs handle non-real time protocols and services. Fig. 2.1 shows 4 DUs connected to different CUs allocated in two Edges. The infrastructure delivers support for the 3 ITU service categories comprising the demanding 5G use cases: eMBB, URLLC and mMTC.

The next segment of the infrastructure is is the Edge. 5G infrastructures are based on MEC architecture where the Edge segment is considered the last mile, close to the mobile subscribers. MEC architecture provides the extension of cloud-computing capabilities such as high-capacity data processing and massive storage resources from the Core segment to the Edge segment, running services and applications in the boundaries of the infrastructure, closer to the UEs. In this way, network traffic bottlenecks are mitigated in the rest of the 5G multi-tenant infrastructure. In addition, the deployment of services at the Edge segment of the network reduces E2E latency, enabling the support for delay sensitive critical-mission use cases (URLLC traffic). Finally, the Core segment is commonly associated with cloud computing and data centers with high computing and storage capacities where services and applications of each MNO are instantiated. The new 5G Core, as defined by 3GPP, utilizes a SBA covering all 5G functions and interactions such as authentication, security, session management and traffic aggregation from end users. The 5G Core further empowers NFV as an integral design approach where VNFs are deployed using the MEC architecture that is key to the 5G architectural principles.

As illustrated in Fig. 2.1, the virtualized data centers of each Virtual Network Operator (VNO) in the Core accommodate different Network Functions (NFs) responsible for several 5G functionalities. The Policy Charging Function (PCF) is one of the control plane NFs and provides QoS policies and rules for control plane functions including network slicing, roaming and mobility. The Unified Data Management (UDM)/Authentication Server Functions (AUSF) manages data for access authorization and user registration. Access and Mobility

Functions (AMF)/Session Management Functions (SMF) receives the subscribers data from the UDM/AUSF and is responsible for assigning IP addresses and handling the user sessions on the network. Finally, in the data path, the User Plane Function (UPF) acts as a mobility anchor for the 5G users, receiving the traffic from the CUs allocated in the Edge and acting as a gateway where the users get access to the internet.

The three aforementioned network segments are interconnected by means of a transport network. The 5G transport network is the bond that connects and holds together all 5G segments, from the C-RAN to the Core, providing end users with access to services and connectivity to the global internet (inter-domain access). It is composed of different transport segments: fronthaul, midhaul and backhaul. For the sake of clarity they have not been included in Fig. 2.1. The fronthaul is responsible to connect the antennas or small cells, now termed 5G Active Antenna Units (AAUs), with the DUs. The midhaul provides communication between one CU and a set of DUs, typically by using optical fiber due to its inherited capabilities of low latency and high bandwidth [34]. Finally, the backhaul transport segment enables connectivity between the different Edges deployed at the boundaries of the 5G infrastructure and the Core or backbone segment, thus allowing users to access the internet.

From an architectural perspective, this contribution is aimed at providing technological innovations in two of the Core components described above: PCF and UPF, enhancing the UPF with extended programmability and network slicing capabilities that will allow PCF to apply enhanced fine-grained QoS policies, leading to fulfill the diverse QoS requirements of the 5G use cases.

2.2 5G Architecture

As a result of the development of this research within the framework of the European 3GPP H2020 SliceNet project, the proposed architecture provides a vision of the network from the perspective of MNOs. The logical 5G architecture consist of three planes or layers:

- **Management Plane:** It carries the traffic from the infrastructure administrator. It encompasses mechanisms involved in the design, configuration and monitoring of network resources, services and network slices. This plane is shown with blue lines in Fig. 2.1. It is worth noting that each VNO has its own management plane.
- **Control Plane:** It conveys traffic for programming the behaviour and configuration of the data plane with the purpose of ensuring the QoS policies designed by the management plane are fulfilled. In Figure 2.1 the control plane is depicted by the black dotted line.
- **Data Plane:** The data plane is responsible for processing and forwarding end-user traffic across the devices and network components comprising the 5G infrastructure. In Figure 2.1, the data plane is represented by the black line. It is noteworthy that in multi-tenant architectures such as those addressed in this work, all traffic traverses the software datapath, i.e., the software switches placed at the Edge and the Core segment. This allows the use of this segment to perform enhanced traffic control.

The division between data plane and control plane is in accordance with the SDN approach adopted, the fundamentals of which are explained in section 2.4. Furthermore, this division of the architecture into logical planes with different requirements and functionalities described above has driven this research work which is focused on the control and data planes. In this sense, the data plane will provide the control plane with an extended fine-grained programmability, allowing an enhanced semantic richness when defining QoS policies to be enforced in the data plane. This will allow to deal with all possible data paths in 5G.

2.3 5G Multi-tenant Architecture

In 5G multi-tenant infrastructures, the owning ISP leases the infrastructure to multiple VNOs that, in turn, offer connectivity and services to end-users and verticals. Softwarization and virtualization are key enablers in this kind of networks where different tenants such as MNOs operate their own virtualized logical infrastructure deployed on top of the same shared

physical infrastructure, leading to savings in CAPEX and OPEX. This implies that multiple VNFs belonging to different VNOs share the same physical machines in a pay-as-you-go business model. Notice the VMs of 2 different tenants in Fig. 2.1 (tenant A in orange and tenant B in green) allocated in the same physical servers of the Edge and Core segments. Softwarization and Virtualization impose the implementation of software datapaths to interconnect the virtual interfaces of VMs with the physical Network Interface Cards (NICs). In this regard, Fig. 2.1 also shows a software switch in each of the physical machines in both Edge and Core physical machines responsible for this functionality.

Multi-tenancy implies the need to provide security mechanisms and performance isolation between tenants to control competition of VNFs belonging to different organizations for the same resources. An approach to achieve this is the use of overlay networks, i.e. virtual logical networks built on top of the same underlying physical network. Overlay networks rely on encapsulation and tunneling protocols where the original user traffic is encapsulated in other packets. The solution provided in this research work will be able to deal with network traffic with several levels of nested encapsulation inherent to overlay networks as those deployed in 5G multi-tenant infrastructures.

This type of virtualized mobile infrastructures has been the main focus of study of this research work and emphasize the necessity of achieving network slicing to meet performance isolation between tenants while satisfying the diverse QoS requirements for end users in the multiple 5G scenarios envisioned. To be precise, this work focuses on providing fine-grained network slicing capabilities in the software datapath segment described above, that is the virtual software switches that allow VMs send and receive network traffic.

2.4 Software Defined Networks

SDN allows the disassociation of the Control Plane (CP) and the DP [35], decoupling control process and network forwarding functionalities (see Fig. 2.2). SDN provides the flexibility, programmability and easy troubleshooting required by current networks, allowing a centralized abstract vision and control of the network. This is a significant step in contrast to

complex traditional monolithic network stacks where the management is done in a completely isolated way without having a common overview of the whole infrastructure. OF is the protocol commonly associated with SDN. It provides the control plane with an abstraction of the different network devices and underlying technologies enabling an uniform and efficient programmability of the data plane.

Fig. 2.2 A High-level overview of the SDN architecture

2.5 Overlay networks in 5G architectures

In 5G multi-tenant infrastructures, overlay networks are used to achieve tenant isolation and handover of UEs between different radio access nodes. Different encapsulation and tunneling protocols are used to perform these functionalities. GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP) [36] is the standard protocol used in 5G MEC architectures to provide user mobility. Users traffic coming from the radio segment is encapsulated by the gNodeB (gNB) in the Edge segment and decapsulated by the UPF in the Core segment. The L2/L3 virtual network traffic of each particular tenant is isolated from the rest of the network traffic by means of encapsulation protocols such as VXLAN [37], GRE [38], STT [39], NVGRE [40] or GENEVE [41]. The encapsulation/decapsulation process takes place in the Edge and Core segments, more

precisely in the virtual switches responsible for providing connectivity between the VMs and the shared underlying physical network.

Fig. 2.3 Different types of traffic in 5G multi-tenant overlay networks as a consequence of the encapsulation/decapsulation process: IP traffic, 4G GTP traffic and 5G multi-tenant traffic

Therefore, as a consequence of the encapsulation and decapsulation process, the traffic flow associated with a specific tenant, end user or service varies in its packet structure (number of headers and protocols) along the 5G multi-tenant infrastructure (see Fig. 2.3). This poses a challenge, since the first step towards delivering tailored fine-grained E2E QoS capabilities is to unambiguously identify and classify the traffic flow from a user or service over all network segments regardless of their levels of nested encapsulations. Traditional flow classifiers are based on L3/L4 5-Tuple (source IP, destination IP, source port, destination port and L4 transport protocol) and lack this functionality. Hence, this issue has to be addressed by providing novel traffic classification capabilities with support for encapsulation and tunneling protocols inherent to 5G overlay networks and thus able to carry out a deep inspection of the inner headers.

2.6 Quality of Service and Traffic Control

The concept of QoS can be defined as the capability of a network to deliver a guaranteed transport service to a specific flow or type of traffic in a independent and isolated way from the rest of the network traffic. To achieve this, it is needed to allocate the appropriate network resources that allow to ensure the QoS parameters agreed in the SLAs between users and service providers.

As computer networks have become more complex and network traffic has grown due to a rapidly increasing number of users requesting higher Quality of Experience (QoE), QoS mechanisms have evolved to offer improved traffic control solutions. QoS and QoE are different yet complementary approaches to monitor network performance. QoS provides an assessment of network performance based on numerical metrics such as E2E delay, jitter, bandwidth or packet loss rate. On the other hand, QoE focuses on the end-user experience, indicating the impact of the network behaviour on the user's experience satisfaction (e.g., the quality of a video or phone call). Therefore, QoS offers a more objective approach than QoE which is a subjective estimation of network performance driven by user's opinion of how they perceive the network performance. Early IP networks were based on a "best-effort" model with no QoS provided and where network devices composing the data plane received and sent network packets as fast as possible.

IntServ architecture, defined in 1994 in IETF RFC 1633 [42], was the first attempt to offer a fine-grained QoS system, proposing simple extensions to the traditional internet model, that is, without introducing changes to existing protocols. *IntServ* introduces the concepts of flow specification (*flowspec*) and service category. A *flowspec* describes the characteristics of the traffic (TSPEC) and the service category requested by the user or application (RSPEC). Three QoS categories are offered: Guaranteed Service (RFC 2212) [43], Controlled Load Service (RFC 2211) [44] and Best-Effort Service. Resource Reservation Protocol (RSVP) (RFC 2205) [45] is the transport protocol responsible in *IntServ* architectures for signalling the reservation of resources throughout the network. Although *IntServ* was a significant breakthrough in computer networking compared to the best-effort approach, problems soon became evident: Many ISPs were reluctant to adopt it due to scalability limitations of a

stateful architecture. All routers and intermediate network devices within the data plane had to keep a soft state of the network resource reservation for every particular flow, which was difficult to accomplish as the network scaled up to the size of the internet.

The Differentiated Service model *DiffServ* was developed to address scalability problems in huge complex networks such as the internet (IETF RFC 2475) [46]. *DiffServ* is based on the aggregation of flows into service categories and relies on three main features: an easy traffic differentiation mechanism, high scalability and interoperability between different ISP domains. Based on the QoS parameters stipulated in the SLAs, routers at the network Edge tag each packet arriving to the ISP domain. Then, on the basis of this tagging value, the intermediate routers and network devices apply a differentiated treatment to each packet, called Per-Hop Behaviour (PHB), with no need to keep flow states nor explicit provisioning of network resources. *DiffServ* uses the outdated one-byte IPv4 Type of Service (TOS) field, renamed Differentiated Service field. The upper 6 bits contain the Differentiated Service Code Point (DSCP) value which is used to set the priority of the packet. The lower 2 bits, referred as to Explicit Congestion Notification (ECN), are for network congestion detection. Thus, the DSCP value is used to group IP packets into traffic classes that are given the same QoS treatment. Multiprotocol Label Switching (MPLS) [47] is another data forwarding technology based on traffic engineering techniques that provides End-to-End QoS with 8 QoS categories. With MPLS, network traffic is routed by means of short path labels instead of look-ups in large routing tables.

Traditional QoS mechanisms such as those described above present limitations of scalability, programmability, flexibility and adaptability that make them unsuitable for current networks. Traffic differentiation is based on traditional IP classifiers mapping outer L3/L4 values into a 5-tuple that lack enough expressiveness to provide the fine-grained classification capabilities required in 5G multi-tenant networks where information about tenants, users and services is conveyed in the inner encapsulated headers of the network packets. Furthermore, to deliver services with extreme and diverse requirements as those expected in 5G, novel programmable QoS capabilities are necessary to enable a dynamic and flexible management of network resources.

Thus, an evolution towards new QoS mechanisms and architectures is imperative. In this sense, Softwarization and virtualization, by means of SDN and NFV, provide the flexibility and programmability needed to deploy overlay networks, enabling improved network performance and monitoring and a efficient reaction to network troubleshooting. In turn, the flow agents comprising the DP are required to expose a NBI with programmability and monitoring mechanisms. Eventually, flow agents composing the DP are responsible for handling network traffic and enforcing QoS policies for fulfilling the requirements demanded by users and verticals.

Connected to the concept of overlay networks and fueled by the wide range of strict requirements demanded by the use cases covered by 5G, network slicing has emerged as a new paradigm and a cornerstone technology able to provide QoS capabilities and network performance isolation in 5G. A detailed review of the current state of the art regarding network slicing is provided in Chapter 3. Based on network slicing, this research work proposes a programmable control traffic solution with SDN capabilities to ensure QoS and performance isolation between flows in the 5G software datapath. The novel 5G software datapath fulfills the challenging KPIs of 5G networks.

Chapter 3

Literature Review

This chapter discusses the current background in network slicing as a cornerstone technology for the successful roll-out and management of 5G networks. It is worth underlining the fact that since this portfolio-based thesis consists of a set of published contributions attached in the second part of this document, an analysis of the specific background on the research topic tackled in each contribution can be found in these chapters.

Hence, rather than going into deep and specific details, this section aims to present an overview of the current landscape of network slicing technology, identifying the gap and limitations of existing solutions and highlighting why this contribution proposes a solution beyond the current state of the art. The first section presents an overall vision of the different definitions and approaches to the network slicing concept proposed by several worldwide initiatives such as SDOs and the mobile industry. In the second part of this chapter, the reader will be provided with a comprehensive analysis of the main features and capabilities of the most relevant network slicing solutions and proposals currently available in the research literature.

3.1 Network Slicing Definitions

At high level, the basic notion beneath the network slicing technology approach is straightforward to understand: to split a common physical network into isolated logical networks to

serve the needs of specific customer use cases. However, the existing literature does not offer a single unified definition of network slice. This is due mainly to the fact that the scope of the network slice definition depends on the use case addressed and on the role and the vision of the 5G network of the different stakeholders involved in 5G such as SDOs, ISPs, MNOs, verticals or end-users.

Different SDOs have made significant efforts in the development of standards for network slicing, establishing a common terminology and a refined definition that will help the mobile telecommunications industry to get a better and common insight into the features of such an important concept. According to the NGMN approach, a network slice *"supports the communication service of a particular connection type with a specific way of handling the Control and User Plane for this service"* [48]. For this purpose, a 5G slice consists of a set of network functions and specific Radio Access Technology (RAT) settings combined together for a specific use case or business model. NGMN suggests a high level network slicing architecture comprising 3 logical layers: Service Instance Layer, Network Slice Instance Layer and Resource Layer [49].

ITU, in its recommendation ITU-T Y.3100 [50], proposes a definition within the IMT-2020 Standard [51] whereby a network slice is *"a logical network that provides specific network capabilities and network characteristics"*. ITU distinguishes between a network slice blueprint and a network slice instance. A network slice instance is created from a network slice blueprint and consists of a set of network functions and the appropriate physical, logical and/or virtual resources required to run those network functions, forming a logical network to meet the network characteristics demanded by a particular service.

3GPP embraces the same definition of network slicing as ITU although, from a Communication Service Provider (CSP) perspective, introduces the concept of Network Slice as a Service (NSaaS) where a CSP can offer a slice to its Communication Service Customers (CSCs) as a service characterized by specific capabilities to satisfy SLAs (e.g. bandwidth, E2E latency, reliability, mobility requirements or degree of isolation requirement). To provide NSaaS, the CSP is required to manage the complete life cycle of a slice that 3GPP divides into 4 phases: preparation, commissioning, operation and decommissioning.

Unlike communication services delivered to end users, in NSaaS the communication service provided is the slice itself [52].

From the perspective of a mobile operator, Global System for Mobile Communications Association (GSMA) provides a definition of network slice as a independent end-to-end logical network consisting of different subnets such as RAN, Core Network (CN) or Transport Network subnet, deployed on top of a common physical infrastructure and intended to serve the business purpose of a customer [53].

In [54], regarding multi-tenant and multi-domain environments as those envisioned in 5G, ETSI emphasizes that network slices should run simultaneously on top of a common shared infrastructure where network resources can be owned and managed by different (and potentially un-trusted) administrative domains. This shared and multi-domain aspect implies that isolation between slices is a critical requirement for network slicing. ETSI proposes to apply the ETSI NFV concepts described in [55], [56] and [57] to fulfill the isolation properties needed to achieve network slicing, considering a NFV network service as a resource-centric view of a network slice for the scenarios where a network slice consists of at least one virtualized network function.

As defined by Open Networking Foundation (ONF) in [58], a slice is a collection of partitioned, assigned and dedicated network resources that can be used in a isolated, disjunctive or shared manner. Some examples of such resources, which could be either physical or virtual, include bandwidth on a network link, forwarding tables in network devices, or processing capabilities of network elements. In order to understand the notion of slice within the ONF approach, it is needed to comprehend the fundamentals of SDN architectures and the concepts of *client context* and *server context* as described by ONF in [59]. In this respect, ETSI proposes the concept of SDN controller client context can be mapped to the concept of Network Service (NS) in NFV.

From the perspective of a mobile operator, Huawei defines a slice as a customized end-to-end logical network requiring support from across the RAN, transport network, core network and management system and aimed to cater for the specific requirements of vertical industries [60]. In a similar approach, Ericsson considers a slice as " a logically separated,

self-contained, independent and secured part of the network, targeting different services with different requirements on speed, latency and reliability" [61]. Nokia has a network slice vision as a dedicated set of physical and virtualized network resources allocated in a E2E manner from end devices, over the RAN, transport network and packet core to application, content delivery and edge cloud domains. For that purpose, network slicing technology lets service providers partition their networks into discrete horizontal slices to support specific use cases, individual customers or even vertical segments [62].

Hence, it is clear how the scope and perception of what a network slice is differs depending on the stakeholders business role. The first main contribution of this research work is a definition of network slice, in terms of network traffic over the data path, that embraces, complements and extends the previous definitions. The proposed novel definition of the scope of network slice establishes the foundations on top of which this thesis has been conducted. The architectural design and implementation of the proposed 5G software datapath is targeted to provide network slicing capabilities within the wide scope of this novel definition, allowing enough flexibility, accuracy and granularity in the network slice instantiation to deal with all the types of network traffic that can be identified in 5G networks, including multi-tenant traffic with different levels of nested encapsulation. This definition will enable flexible, customized and tailored solutions for the different scenarios with diverse extreme requirements in terms of performance, scalability and availability envisaged in 5G. For further details on this contribution, refer to section 9.3 of chapter 9 (outcome [3]).

3.2 Network Slicing Solutions

The previous section has discussed different definitions of the network slice concept proposed by the stakeholders involved in the design and standardization of 5G networks. These propositions cover a high level view without getting into implementation details and highlighting network slicing as an E2E concept. This entails that, to effectively perform network slicing, it is necessary to implement it across all the network segments comprising 5G infrastructures, posing a huge technological challenge due to the different underlying technologies, hardware

equipment, network devices and network protocols composing each network segment, which turn 5G networks into heterogeneous and complex ecosystems. This section moves on to the implementation level, providing an analysis of the most relevant network slicing solutions available in the existing research literature and offering the reader a detailed comparison of the features of the different approaches.

The fact that network slicing is a key enabling technology in the successful deployment of 5G and an ongoing topic of interest among the scientific community is endorsed by the significant amount of related works, proposals and solutions published in the recent years. From the perspective of network slicing as an E2E concept, solutions in existing literature can be categorized into those providing E2E solutions and those targeting a specific network segment, tackling the challenges and technical aspects inherent to such a segment. Table 3.1 summarizes a comparative analysis of the main features of the network slicing solutions found in the existing state of the art. For each approach, it is outlined whether the solution is suitable for virtualized environments by exposing SDN capabilities or providing support for VNF or SFC. The reader can also observe the ITU categories covered and the QoS requirements for which some kind of result is reported. Finally, the network segments involved in the proposed solution and the type of network traffic it is able to deal with are indicated as well.

Slicing on the RAN domain, the wireless segment of the 5G network, has attracted the attention of many researchers and several proposals have been published regarding this matter. RAN slicing poses a challenge because of scarce radio resources and the complexity of dealing with different RATs such as WiFi, LTE or 5G-NR that allow connectivity between end-users and the 5G core network. In this sense, in [75] and [76] 3GPP describes the fundamentals of RAN slicing implementation including QoS support, resource isolation, SLA enforcement and RAN awareness of slices. In [63], authors propose an architecture for RAN slicing based on a two-level Media Access Control (MAC) scheduler to abstract and share the physical radio resources, relying on FlexRAN [77] to enable programmability and flexibility in resource allocation according to the slice needs. In [64], authors propose a theoretical model for slicing the RAN segment by means of Heterogeneous Non-Orthogonal

	Virtualiz. Capabilities			ITU Category			Results on QoS Requirements					Type of Traffic			5G Network Segment					Validation ¹	
	SDN	VNF	SFC	mMTC	eMBB	URLLC	Bandwidth isolation	Latency isolation	Reliability	High density	Scalability	5G	Multi-tenant	5G Multi-tenant	RAN	Edge	Core	Software datapath	Hardware datapath		
[63]	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	E
[64]	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	A
[65]	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	S
[66]	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	D
[67]	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	D
[68]	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	S
[69]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	R
[70]	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	S
[71]	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	E
[72]	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	E
[73]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	S
[74]	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	S
This	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	R

⁽¹⁾ A=Analytical, S=Simulation, E=Emulation, R=Real infrastructure, D=Architectural proposal or design with no implementation

Table 3.1 Comparison of features of different Network Slicing solutions and proposals found in the current state of the art.

Multiple Access (H-NOMA) in order to ensure performance guarantees for the three ITU generic services. In [65], authors prototype an architecture to manage slices in the C-RAN segment, coping with the spectrum slicing problematic. The prototyped solution makes use of the Open Air Interface (OAI) platform and the well-known SDN controller FlexRAN [77]. Although the feasibility of the proposal is validated in a testbed with 2 slices where bandwidth isolation between slices is ensured, this work does not provide numerical results and does not refer to any specific use case or category of service. These aforementioned proposals, focused on the wireless segment, are complementary to the solution described in this dissertation with the common goal of providing E2E slicing support.

In [66], authors provide a 5G architecture con E2E network slicing support. RAN slicing whilst providing communication between UEs and gNBs is achieved using OAI [78] and Dynamic Spectrum-Level Slicing (DSLS) [79]. The programmability of the DP in the Evolved Packet Core (EPC) is possible by using programmable FLARE nodes [80] and

Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) that allow resource isolation and thus enabling to perform network slicing in the edge and core segments of the 5G network. Although this architecture is prototyped to deliver E2E network slicing in virtualized networks, it lacks support for multi-tenancy and no empirical validation on performance is given.

In [67], a network slicing approach is presented to cater for different use cases related to Vehicle to Everything (v2X) such as autonomous driving or vehicular remote diagnostics and management. These use cases imply the fulfillment of the KPIs of the three ITU services and the design of a multi-tenant architecture. Nevertheless, although promising, authors present a work at a early stage, providing neither a real deployment of the proposed infrastructure nor results to evaluate the proposal.

In [68], authors implement 5G core network slicing based on the open source NFV Management and Network Orchestration (MANO) architecture and reporting results about bandwidth and latency for three eMBB use cases with different QoS requisites.

In [69], authors describe an E2E network slice architecture with two slices enforced in the DP for eMBB and URLLC respectively and in which MEC is adopted to reduce latency for URLLC traffic. Experiments on a OAI-based testbed provides results for latency and throughput but not for scalability.

In [70], authors present a model named "DeepSlice" that makes use of a Deep Learning Neural Network to predict the slice of the incoming traffic and thus allowing an efficient use of the network resources and existing slices. The training of the neural network is conducted with a data-set with the most relevant KPIs for both the network and the devices.

In [71], an open source solution is described to achieve E2E network slicing based on a slice-aware RAN, allowing the slicing of both the RAN and the core segments. The experimental results indicate that the proposed framework provides independence between slices, although the tests have been carried out in an emulated testbed in which only two slices have been created.

In [72], it is described a NFV and SDN approach to network slicing for critical infrastructures compatible with ETSI NFV, providing numerical results for three scenarios.

In [73], an auction-based mechanism is presented for a smart resource allocation in order to provide E2E network slicing in 5G networks. Authors evaluate the performance of 2 different strategies based on price competition and a two-step auction mechanism respectively. Both approaches consider the availability of network resources (radio spectrum, storage and computational capacity) towards an efficient allocation of resources and slices and no results related to QoS performance are presented.

In [74], authors present an E2E network slicing solution for Massive Internet of Things (mIoT) scenarios with small data transmission and sporadic connectivity. The solution reduces the CP signaling and optimizes User Plane (UP) resource utilization. Although some results about scalability, performance and density are presented, they are based on a Matlab simulation tool, so the performance of the proposed architecture has not been tested in a realistic infrastructure.

As the reader can check in Table 3.1, none of the network slicing solutions described so far provides all the 5G features that this research work fulfils:

- Advanced traffic classification capabilities for overlay networks in virtualized 5G multi-tenant environments.
- Enhanced SDN capabilities to extend the DP programmability allowing to enforce fine-grained customized QoS policies to fulfill the agreed SLA requirements.
- Empirical validation and evaluation in a realistic 5G testbed.
- Experimental testbed based on challenging use cases covering all ITU service categories.
- Numerical results for critical 5G KPIs such as bandwidth, delay, jitter, scalability and packet loss showing the suitability of this solution.

To the best of the author's knowledge, this is the first time a network slice solution with the above characteristics has been reported, which highlights the innovation and relevance of the research work described in this dissertation.

The contribution that this research work provides to support the development of network slicing for 5G networks may be considered from two different perspectives. From the architectural point of view, considering the segments composing 5G networks, this thesis provides network slicing functionality for the softwarised datapath in the edge and core segments of the 5G networks. The remaining segments involving hardware and wireless (RAN) are out of the scope of this thesis. From the 5G KPIs perspective, this dissertation focuses on improving those ones related to QoS. Other features of 5G infrastructures, however, are beyond the scope of this work. For instance, strong security, extended coverage for challenging locations, energy and cost efficiency, automatic deployment and control of the 5G infrastructure or radio spectrum efficiency, among other features.

Chapter 4

Methodology

All research work seeks to find answers or solutions to unanswered and open questions within the scientific community, providing new solutions and knowledge. In order for the new contribution to be recognized and embraced by the research community, it is essential to demonstrate that it is valid and reliable. The validity and reliability of the novel contribution proposed is closely linked to the methodology applied to conduct the research work. According to Murthy & Bhojanna [81], a research methodology is the blueprint of a research work, a systematic and organized method of solving a research question encompassing all phases of the research process: knowledge acquisition, design and implementation of the solution, experimentation, interpretation of the gathered data and drawing conclusions. Therefore, the impact of the adopted methodology on the final result of the research work is evident and, for this reason, this chapter provides the reader with a clear understanding of the methodological approach followed to conduct this dissertation.

4.1 Research method

The first step before starting a research work is to choose an appropriate research method, which, depending on the discipline of study, can be qualitative, quantitative or even a combination or both [82]. Due to the nature of the problem addressed in this dissertation, the methodology adopted is based on a quantitative method conducted by experiments where the

data gathered as a result of such experiments has been analyzed to demonstrate the suitability and feasibility of the proposed solution. This approach has been chosen because it allows to objectively measure the overall performance, robustness and goodness of the solution in terms of 5G KPIs commonly used in computer networks such as delay, jitter, packet loss and bandwidth. In addition, 5G technology aims to provide services in highly dense areas where millions of users and devices can be simultaneously connected. This makes scalability another key factor to consider when developing 5G solutions. Scalability has been validated and evaluated by analyzing the behaviour of the proposed solution when ranging parameters such as number of network slices enforced, number of users or IoT devices connected, Packets Per Second (PPS) processed or packet size. Finally, another set of experiments has been carried out to objectively assess the adaptability and versatility of the proposed solution to continuously evolving heterogeneous scenarios such as those expected in 5G infrastructures where the network must be able to simultaneously provide diverse QoS requirements demanded by different types of services such as eMBB, URLLC and mMTC.

4.2 Scheduling of the workload of the thesis

In order to successfully achieve the aim of this thesis set out in subsection 1.2.1, the workload was scheduled and distributed throughout the duration of this thesis using a hierarchical approach. The thesis was split in 2 phases according to the nature of the tasks performed: theoretical or practical. In turn, each phase was composed of different work packages. Finally, at the bottom of the hierarchy, each work package consist of a set of interdependent tasks. Each of the tasks is targeted to fulfill one or more of the objectives stated in subsection 1.2.3.

The first phase involves work packages related to theoretical and conceptual processes such as knowledge acquisition, gap identification, requirements analysis and design of the proposed solution. As a result, this first phase provides a deep understanding of the problem addressed which is essential to successfully complete the second phase and thus this research work. Besides, the first phase also produces a first theoretical design of the novel software datapath with network slicing capabilities. The second phase comprises work

Fig. 4.1 Methodology: hierarchical organization of the workload into phases, work packages and tasks. Interdependence and precedence between tasks.

packages with tasks focused on experimentation such as prototyping, implementation and experimental validation and evaluation. Apart for the prototyped solution and the software projects developed to set up and execute the experiments, the outcomes of the second phase are the publications that constitute the core of this portfolio-based thesis.

Fig. 4.1 shows the logical workflow and hierarchical breakdown of the workload into phases, work packages (purple boxes) and tasks (orange boxes) as well as the interdependence and precedence between tasks (see arrows from one task to another indicating precedence in execution). Notice the green circles indicating the achieved objective associated with each task. As it can be observed, each one of the tasks 8 to 11 comprising the work package 4 results in one the above-mentioned publications. For the sake of clarity, the titles of the

publications have been shortened by using the acronyms listed in Table 4.1 alongside with their bibliographical references and the chapter of the second part of this thesis containing every outcome.

Acronym	Title	Chapter	Reference
SliceNetVSwitch	SliceNetVSwitch: Definition, Design and Implementation of 5G Multi-Tenant Network Slicing in Software Data Paths	9	[3]
NB-IoT-FW	Scalable Software Switch Based Service Function Chaining for 5G Network Slicing	10	[4]
SFC-NS	Highly-Scalable Software Firewall Supporting One Million Rules for 5G NB-IoT Networks	11	[5]
5G-IoT-NS	Adaptive Network Slicing in Multi-tenant 5G IoT Networks	12	[6]

Table 4.1 Publications: acronyms, chapter containing the publication and bibliographical reference

The following is a brief description of each of the tasks, outlining how each task has contributed towards achieving the main aim of this research work:

- **Phase I: Knowledge acquisition, analysis and design**

- **Work Package 1: State of the art and knowledge acquisition**

- * **Task 1:** This task was intended to conduct an in-depth study and analysis of the state of the art related to 5G, network slicing and other technologies and topics relevant to the research line of this work such as NFV, SDN, IoT, softwarization, virtualization, traffic control, or QoS. Unlike the rest of the tasks, this task has been conducted throughout the whole duration of the thesis. This is due to the fact that network slicing and 5G are ongoing topics within the research community. A significant number of publications, proposals and standards related to 5G have been published during the course of this thesis, requiring a continuous process of knowledge acquisition and literature updating. Two major conclusions were drawn from this task. First,

the necessity to provide a novel definition of network slice. Second, the research gap was clearly identified: the lack of traffic control solutions with network slicing capabilities for the software datapath segment in 5G multi-tenant environments.

– **Work Package 2: Analysis and design**

- * **Task 2:** After reviewing the different definitions of network slice found in the literature, it was concluded that, firstly, they all provide a high-level logical view of what a network slice is and, secondly, they differ depending on the perspective of the stakeholder involved in 5G. This is so even though the underlying notion behind the concept of network slicing is clear, easy to understand and transversal to all proposed definitions available: to split a physical common network into logical virtualized and isolated networks. Therefore, the outcome of this task is a novel definition of network slice that is closer to the DP and therefore to implementation tasks. This novel definition has the versatility and semantic richness to embrace all previous definitions while allowing, from a DP perspective, it covers all types of traffic expected in 5G including overlay traffic inherent to multi-tenant environments.
- * **Task 3:** The purpose of this task is the design of a novel traffic classifier capturing the flexibility and accuracy of the network slice definition proposed in task 2. This entails dealing with overlay traffic with different levels of nested encapsulation characteristic of 5G multi-tenant networks. Unlike traditional classifiers based on a 5-tuple containing L2/L3/L4 information extracted from the outer headers, this novel flow dissector has to perform a deep inspection of the inner encapsulated headers to gather information about end-users, tenants and inner services, ports and IP addresses. The new extracted metadata will allow to associate each packet with an extended 5G flow key providing a more flexible, accurate and fine-grained traffic classification, which is an essential first stage in the delivery of fine-grained

network slicing capabilities on the basis of the slice definition proposed in task 2. Hence, the design of the flow dissector has to provide support for encapsulation and tunneling protocols used in 5G overlay networks such as Virtual Extensible Local Area Network (VXLAN), Generic Routing Encapsulation (GRE), or GTP. Furthermore, the design has to drive a robust and efficient implementation, minimising the impact of the extra overhead in the delay caused by performing a in-depth inspection of the network traffic.

- * **Task 4:** This task is aligned with tasks 2 and 3. In line with the SDN approach followed, the novel software datapath exposes a NBI providing the controller with enhanced programmability capabilities and an abstract technology-agnostic vision of the network. Since the implementation of the software datapath is a significant extension of the base version of the well-known software datapath Open Virtual Switch (OVS), the communication between the controller and the flow agent (i.e CP and DP) was implemented by using the OF protocol. Therefore, it was required to extend the OF protocol with new fields and actions enabling the control layer the enforcement of network slices in the DP to fulfill the verticals and users QoS requirements defined in the SLAs. The new OF fields contain information about the packet structure (number and types of encapsulations and tunnel IDs) as well as information extracted from the inner encapsulated headers, resulting in an enhanced semantic richness of the OF flow definition (left part of the rule). The new actions will allow to enforce slices and set traffic priorities. These new OF extensions match the metadata added in the extended 5G flow key generated by the classifier designed in task 3 and they have been carefully considered as they will have an impact on the overall system performance and scalability.

- **Phase II: Implementation, experimentation and publication**

- **Work Package 3: Implementation**

- * **Task 5:** Based on the design made in task 3, the implementation of the flow dissector was carried out to support all possible datapaths in 5G multi-tenant networks. The programming language used was C since the classifier must run both in Linux kernel space as part of the OVS kernel module and in user space as part of the OVS daemon. The implementation follows a modular approach where each module is in charge of parsing a specific protocol and, based on the gathered data, sending the packet to the module responsible for processing the next header. This modular architectural approach followed provides ease of extensibility (adding support for a new protocol is straightforward) and reentrancy (a parsing module can be visited more than once). This reentrancy feature is what makes it possible to deeply inspect overlay traffic and provides versatility to support different datapaths. Finally, the implementation was performed with the aim of producing a more efficient code in terms of execution time, thus minimizing the overhead caused by these new classification capabilities.
- * **Task 6:** The 5G traffic classifier and the OF extensions resulting from the previous tasks was applied to the prototyping and implementation of a novel software datapath with network slicing capabilities suitable for 5G multi-tenant networks, by undertaking significant extensions to OVS. To accomplish this, it was required the extension of the majority of modules, Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), data structures, protocols, kernel-user space inter-process communication mechanisms and command line applications composing the OVS architecture in both user and kernel space. The slices were implemented as Hierarchical Token Bucket (HTB) queuing disciplines configurable with QoS parameters. Finally, the integration into OVS has been conducted in such a way that the novel 5G features can be enabled or disabled at compilation time using flags.
- * **Task 7:** The software datapath was enhanced by adding network slicing support for SFC needed in virtualized and softwarized network architectures

where the scope of network slice is a sequence of network services and resources comprising a logical network to meet specific user requirements. This allows the software datapath to assume the role of Service Function Forwarder (SFF) in such architectures, providing the scalability levels needed to simultaneously manage a large number of SFCs while guaranteeing QoS requirements and isolation performance between network slices.

– **Work Package 4: Experimentation and publication**

- * **Task 8:** This task was targeted at empirically evaluating the system performance and validating the network slicing functionalities of the novel software datapath prototyped in task 6. Since the implementation was carried out by extending the OVS base features, the first step was to assess the extra overhead incurred when processing network traffic associated to different datapaths expected in 5G (IP, 4G/LTE, multi-tenant and 5G multi-tenant traffic) when compared to the OVS time baseline. In a second step, the system behaviour in terms of delay and packet loss is evaluated when ranging the number of rules enforced and the total bandwidth transmitted. Finally, an empirical validation of the network slicing capabilities is conducted. All these results along with the definition of network slice proposed in task 2 were published in the contribution shortened SliceNetVSwitch.
- * **Task 9:** The software datapath was tested in a security use case in which it was exploited as a firewall for 5G NB-IoT networks. The goal of the experiments carried out were twofold. First, to demonstrate the suitability of the proposal as a valid security solution for 5G NB-IoT networks. Second, to assess the scalability of the firewall in terms of number of rules simultaneously managed, that is, how the number of rules impacts the overall system performance in terms of delay, jitter and packet loss. As a result of this task, the contribution shortened NB-IoT-FW was published.
- * **Task 10:** The goal of this task was to empirically validate the SFC-aware network slicing capabilities developed in task 7. To this purpose, an empirical

evaluation of the overall performance overhead introduced was carried out as well as experiments were conducted to measure the scalability in terms of Service Function (SF) hops concurrently managed and bandwidth, providing an analysis of the behaviour in terms of delay. The technical details and results achieved are available in the publication shortened SFC-NS released as outcome of this task.

- * **Task 11:** The main goal of this task was the integration of the novel software datapath in a 5G IoT framework, delivering network slicing capabilities to cope with challenging IoT scenarios, thus demonstrating its feasibility as a viable solution for these infrastructures. In the experiments carried out, the architecture was able to cope with the requirements in 5G-enabled IoT networks such as multi-tenant support, user mobility, scalable slicing for mMTC, IoT service differentiation for high bandwidth in eMBB, IoT device differentiation with ultra-low latency and high reliability in delay-sensitive critical-mission use cases URLLC or interoperability. Furthermore, the architecture was designed to manage efficiently and on-demand the complete life cycle of a slice. The proposed approach was empirically evaluated by means of 5 IoT use cases covering the 3 ITU categories or a hybrid combination of them, achieving promising results that demonstrate the suitability of the solution for 5G IoT networks. The architectural design, testbed and experimental results of this task can be found published in the publication 5G-IoT-NS.

Table 4.2 presents a Gantt chart illustrating the time scheduling of the tasks. The diagram depicts the start and end dates of the activities as well as the dependency and precedence between activities (see arrows from one task to another). Notice how several tasks have been undertaken in parallel throughout the progress of this dissertation. It is worth mentioning that task 1 (knowledge acquisition and background) takes place during the whole duration of this thesis, including the last stage of writing this document. As mentioned above, this is due to the fact that network slicing and 5G are currently topics of great relevance within

Table 4.2 Gantt chart: Chronology and dependence of tasks during the research work

the research community, resulting in a huge number of publications, projects, proposals and standards being released even at the time of writing down this document, thus requiring a continuous revision and monitoring process of the related literature.

Chapter 5

Analysis and Design of Proposed Network Slicing Software Datapath

Many details about the architectural design and implementation of the solution developed in this research work have been described in the outcomes comprising the core of this portfolio-based thesis. The reader can find these publications in the second part of this document. Nonetheless, each publication provides a partial vision of the novel software datapath proposed in this research work, providing partial information concerning design and implementation (features, architectural components and details), only that information needed for the reader to obtain an overall vision and a good understanding of the proposal presented in each particular publication. Furthermore, the proposed 5G multi-tenant software datapath solution has been continuously evolving and refining over the course of the research work conducted, using a spiral software development process where each iteration is linked to an outcome and used as baseline for the next research milestone.

The purpose of this chapter is to provide a complete description of the architecture including the evolution and all the features provided along the outcomes: the components it consists of (modules, APIs and data structures), their functionality and the cooperation between them to deliver fine-grained network slicing capabilities in the software datapath segment of the data plane of 5G multi-tenant networks.

5.1 Design of the Proposed Network Slicing Solution for 5G Multi-tenant Software Datapaths

Fig. 5.1 provides an overview of the different components of the control and data plane of the logical architecture developed in the research work. The architecture has been designed on the basis of the SDN paradigm, decoupling network control and forwarding functionality, providing programmability of network control and an abstract vision of the underlying network infrastructure.

The reader can observe in Fig. 5.1 the component named *UWS 5G Multi-tenant Software Datapath*. This component is the main innovation and contribution presented in this research work. This architectural component is a software flow agent providing advanced traffic control capabilities for a particular segment of the 5G multi-tenant networks: the software datapath segment. This network segment plays a key role in virtualized networks since it is responsible for connecting the virtualized infrastructures of the different tenants sharing the same physical resources (i.e. virtual machines and dedicated virtual logical networks) with the physical network infrastructure.

Fig. 5.1 Architectural design of the Software Data plane

The novel software datapath consist of six logical components that interact together to provide flexible fine-grained traffic control and network slicing capabilities and thus leading

to meet the QoS requirements demanded by verticals and end-users and agreed in SLAs. The following is a short description of the functionality of each component:

- **North Bound Interface:** This interface is in charge of the communication between the CP, i.e. the SDN controller, and the software datapath. For this purpose it exposes an OF API. OF has been significantly extended, adding new fields and actions to enrich the expressiveness of the predicate of the OF rules allowing a flexible definition of data flow able to encompass all possible datapaths in 5G .
- **5G Multi-tenant Classifier:** It is the entry point of the software datapath. It receives the network traffic and performs a deep inspection of every packet. The design and development of this parser is a significant enhancement over the current state of the art.
- **Slice Definition Table:** This module keeps a database containing the definition of the network slices in form of OF rules. The left part of the rule is the flow definition matching the slice. The right part includes the ID of the slice assigned to each flow and the actions to be performed on the traffic before sending it to the network slicing core.
- **Match Flow Action:** This module compares the 5G flow key extracted by the 5G multi-tenant parser with the entries in the slice definition table, seeking a slice matching the packet.
- **Actions and Slice Enforcer:** This module performs the actions associated with each slice before sending it to the last module of the pipeline.
- **Network Slicing Core:** This module is in charge of effectively enforcing the network slices in each of the network interfaces connected to the software datapath, both physical and virtual.

5.2 5G Multi-tenant Software Data Plane Workflow

This section provides the reader with a thorough understanding of the workflow designed in the proposed software data plane. Fig. 5.2 illustrates an overall view of the workflow that

a network packet follows across the software dataplane and how the different architectural components cooperate together to enforce the network slices in the DP and, thereby, fulfill the QoS policies and performance requirements specified for the data flow associated with each slice.

The incoming network traffic to the software data plane can arrive from either a physical or a virtual network interface. Notice that this is so, because as mentioned above, the software datapath is the point in the DP where the different virtual networks of each tenant and the common shared physical network converge. Regardless of the source of the network traffic, before entering the software datapath, the packets are processed by the Linux kernel device driver attached to such network interface. Among other tasks, the driver is in charge of allocating the packet in memory buffers provided by the networking subsystem of the Linux kernel. The first stage in the software datapath pipeline is the *5G Multi-tenant Classifier*. The driver delivers the packet to the classifier which carries out a deep inspection of it by visiting all the protocol headers in the packet structure, including those after the encapsulation, tunneling and tagging headers. As a result, a *flow key* is generated that will allow to assign the packet to a specific slice. The role of this architectural component is paramount in the design of the proposed solution and therefore it is further described in detail on section 5.3. The network packet and its extracted *flow key* is then received by the *Match Flow Action* module where the *flow key* is compared against the *Slice Definition Table*. The *Slice Definition Table* is queried for a slice which associated flow (left side of the rule) matches the extracted *flow key*. If the lookup fails, i.e. there is no rule matching the *flow key*, a default policy is applied (e.g. drop, mirror, assign to a low priority slice or send to SDN controller). On the other hand, if the lookup is successful, the specific actions associated to that slice are executed (right part of the rule). The reader may observe in the workflow in Fig. 5.2, that a network packet may be dropped because of the application of a default policy or due to the specific actions of a slice. Finally, if the packet is not dropped, it is sent to the last module in the pipeline, the *Network Slicing Core*. This module manages the slices, providing isolation between them and ensuring the specific QoS requirements of each network slice in terms of bandwidth, delay and reliability.

Fig. 5.2 5G Multi-tenant Software Datapath workflow

To conclude this section, it is worth highlighting that the workflow diagram shown in Fig. 5.2 is the final version produced at the end of this research work. It is the culmination of an iterative refining process carried over the course of this thesis as described in the adopted methodology in chapter 4. A first version of the design, without the *Network Slicing Core* module and with a reduced version of the *5G Multi-tenant Classifier* was presented in [4] to provide firewall capabilities in 5G NB-IoT networks. The classifier has undergone successive enhancements in [3] and [5], adding support for overlay networks and SFC to allow a fine-grained identification of the network traffic. The *Network Slicing Core* module was introduced in [3]. Finally, the whole final design was tested and validated in contribution [6], where it was integrated as part of a 5G IoT framework with network slicing capabilities.

5.3 5G Multi-tenant Packet Classifier

When a MNO agrees to deliver a service with tailored and guaranteed parameters defined in a SLA, from the DP perspective, this results in a commitment of the MNO to meet specific QoS requirements in terms of bandwidth, delay or reliability to the data flow associated to that SLA. Thus, the first stage in providing guaranteed services is to be able to unambiguously identify the traffic associated with each SLA. This poses a challenge in 5G multi-tenant networks. First, the granularity of the network traffic associated with a SLA differs depending on the stakeholder involved in such SLA. For instance, a SLA could map the network traffic of a particular tenant, the aggregated traffic of a network service, the traffic of a end mobile subscriber or even, with a higher granularity, the traffic of a specific service from a specific end subscriber. Secondly, the deployment of overlay networks in 5G multi-tenant infrastructures implies that the needed information from tenants, services and users is carried in the encapsulated inner headers. Furthermore, access to data in the headers of tunneling protocols (e.g. VXLAN or GTP) in network packets with multiple levels of nested encapsulation is mandatory in 5G multi-tenant networks to support fundamental network features such as tenant isolation and user mobility.

Fig. 5.3 5G Multi-tenant classifier

Existing traffic classifiers in current software datapath solutions such as OVS, DPDK, XDP or Netmap are based on traditional 5-tuple and do not provide the levels of flexibility and granularity required in 5G multi-tenant networks. The first contribution of this research work is the design and implementation of a novel packet classifier that fills this gap in the current state of the art.

The design aim of this packet classifier is to achieve flexible fine-grained identification of the traffic. This fine-grained identification will be later used to provide enhanced control capabilities over such network traffic. The novel 5G multi-tenant traffic classifier has been continuously developed and improved along this research work, in a iterative refinement process in which each outcome is a new version with improved capabilities. In case the reader is more interested in particular aspects and a deeper insight of the classifier, more detailed information is available in [3], [4] and [5]. In [5], a first simplified version of the classifier supporting GTP-encapsulated traffic for 5G NB-IoT traffic is provided as part of a 5G software firewall. In [3], among other new features, support for VXLAN and GRE is added, enabling to differentiate network traffic from different tenants. In [4], by implementing the capability to inspect Next Service Header (NSH) headers, the classifier is enhanced enabling support for SFC, a technology commonly used in SDN. This extension will allow providing network slicing capabilities covering the scope of network slice as a set of resources and a chain of connected network services forming a logical network to deliver QoS requirements.

Fig. 5.3 describes the complete final version of the 5G multi-tenant traffic classifier which has not been published so far and where all supported protocols can be observed.

The differentiating points of this novel traffic classifier when compared to the current state of the art are manifold:

- Capability to parse overlay traffic with encapsulation and tunneling protocols to allow a inspection of the outer and inner headers.
- Efficient design with a modular architecture with re-entrance between modules to optimise the parsing time.

- Deliver support for multi-tenancy capabilities in 5G networks.

5.4 Integration of the 5G Multi-tenant Classifier in OVS Architecture

As it can be observed in Fig. 5.3, when traffic arrives to the 5G software datapath from the NIC driver, packets are classified twice: first by the OVS parser and secondly by the 5G multi-tenant classifier. This is because OVS does not actually have a built-in parser and instead delegates this task to the Linux kernel flow dissector which provides a traffic classification based on traditional 5-tuple. Extending the Linux kernel classifier features with 5G and multi-tenant support is a complicated task that would lead to portability issues for the proposed solution, so this option was discarded. For this reason, it was decided to implement the novel 5G classifier from scratch as a new functionality completely embedded in the 5G software datapath. The 5G multi-tenant classifier, as well as other 5G features such as OF extensions and network slicing support, can be enabled or disabled at compilation time by using flags designed for such a purpose.

```
1 $ ./boot.sh
2 $ ./configure --uws-5g-network-slice=yes \
3             --uws-debug=no \
4             --enable-Werror \
5             --with-linux=/lib/modules/$(uname -r)/build
6 $ sudo make
7 $ sudo make install
8 $ sudo make modules_install
```

Listing 5.1 UWS 5G Software Datapath compilation with flags to enable 5G network slicing capabilities

Listing 5.1 shows the compilation process where two flags are set: the flag *uws-5g-network-slice* is activated to enable the 5G classifier and the network slicing capabilities and

the flag *uws-debug* is for debugging purposes. The novel 5G classification capabilities result in an extra delay when processing traffic in the 5G software datapath pipeline due to the deep inspection performed on each packet. This extra performance overhead has been extensively evaluated in [3] with different types of traffic, yielding more than acceptable values in the order of μsecs , thus demonstrating the robustness and suitability of the 5G classifier as a valid solution.

5.5 Extended 5G Flow Key

Traditional 5-Tuple, which OF fields are listed in Table 5.1, allows to enforce traffic control mechanisms based on data extracted from the outer L2/L3/L4 headers of the packets. This is not sufficient on multi-tenant 5G networks where data from tenant and subscribers necessary for fine-grained programmability of the data plane is encapsulated in the inner headers. For this reason, as a major contribution of this research work, the OF protocol has been extended with new fields in order to provide a novel extended 5G flow key. The outcome of the 5G multi-tenant classifier is this new extended flow key which represents a significant improvement over the traditional 5-tuple-based flow key provided by the OVS base version. The 5G flow key contains 17 new fields as listed in Table 5.2 along with the length in bytes and the field description. The new metadata extracted provides the required information to provide a flexible and fine-grained definition of network slice in 5G multi-tenant overlay networks. The new fields include information about the innermost overlay network in form of 6-tuple, the innermost DSCP value and information about the overlay networks. How the new fields are populated is explained in more detail in section 9.5.2.

The 5G classifier provides support for 8 different encapsulation and tagging protocols typically used in 5G multi-tenant networks as listed in Table 5.3. For each nested encapsulation level, i.e. for each overlay network, the gathered metadata consists of the encapsulation protocol (*tunnel_type_x* in Table 5.2) and the tunnel ID (*tunnel_key_x* in Table 5.2). It is worth highlighting that the protocol header field matching the tunnel ID depends on each encapsulation protocol context as indicated in Table 5.3. For example, in the case of GTP,

Key flow field	Length (Bytes)	Description of the field
ip_src	4	Source IP address from the outer IPv4 header
ip_dst	4	Destination IP address from the outer IPv4 header
udp_src	2	UDP source port field from the outer UDP header
udp_dst	2	UDP destination port field from the outer UDP header
ip_proto	1	Match the outer IPv4 protocol type (transport protocol)

Table 5.1 Open Flow fields for traditional 5-tuple based flow key

Key flow field	Length (Bytes)	Description of the field
inner_ip_src	4	Source IP address in the inner IP4 header
inner_ip_dst	4	Destination IP address in the inner IPv4 header
inner_tos	1	Type of Service value (TOS) in inner IPv4 header
inner_port_src	2	Source port in the inner UDP header
inner_port_dst	2	Destination port in the inner UDP header
inner_l3_protocol	2	Ethernet type of the inner layer 3 header
inner_l4_protocol	1	IANA protocol number of the inner layer 4 header
tunnel_type_1	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 1 ⁽¹⁾
tunnel_type_2	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 2 ⁽¹⁾
tunnel_type_3	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 3 ⁽¹⁾
tunnel_type_4	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 4 ⁽¹⁾
tunnel_type_5	1	Tunnel type of encapsulation level 5 ⁽¹⁾
tunnel_key_1	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 1 ⁽²⁾
tunnel_key_2	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 2 ⁽²⁾
tunnel_key_3	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 3 ⁽²⁾
tunnel_key_4	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 4 ⁽²⁾
tunnel_key_5	4	Tunnel key of encapsulation level 5 ⁽²⁾

⁽¹⁾ Mapping between values and protocol listed in Table 5.3.

⁽²⁾ Meaning of key for each protocol as given in Table 5.3.

Table 5.2 New fields included in the extended 5G flow key

used to deliver user mobility across the antennas and the 5G network, the tunnel ID refers to the Tunnel Endpoint Identifier (TEID) field in the GTP header. In VXLAN, used to guarantee isolation between tenants, the tunnel ID corresponds to the VXLAN Network Identifier (VNI) field of the VXLAN header. Notice that the pair (VNI,TEID) identifies unequivocally a mobile user. The NSH protocol was added in [4] (Chapter 10) to deliver network slicing in SFC.

Encapsulation Protocol	Value	Tunnel key description
VXLAN	1	VXLAN Network ID (VNI)
GTP	2	Tunnel Endpoint Identifier (TEID)
GRE	3	GRE Key
MPLS	4	MPLS Label
VLAN	5	VLAN Identifier (VNI)
NSH	6	Service Path Identifier (SPI)
VXLAN-GPE	7	VXLAN Network ID (VNI)
GENEVE	8	Virtual Network Identifier (VNI)

Table 5.3 Parsing of encapsulation, tunneling and tagging protocols: tunnel type values and meaning of the key values.

Notice in Table 5.2 that the maximum number of nested encapsulated supported is 5. This design decision was made as a result of a trade-off between overhead in matching time and flexibility to cope with all possible datapaths expected in 5G. A further explanation concerning this decision can be found in section 9.5.2.

5.6 Sequence Diagrams of Network Slicing Creation and Enforcing

5G networks are dynamic and evolving environments that are required to offer support for a wide range of heterogeneous use cases and services demanding diverse QoS requirements. Hence, 5G needs to cope with the deployment and management of network slices in the DP in an efficient and dynamic fashion allowing adaptation to an evolving 5G traffic. In contribution [6] (chapter 12), the proposed 5G software data path is integrated into a 5G network slicing framework providing a complete management of the life cycle of a network slice: creation (provisioning of network resources), maintenance (dynamic change of QoS parameters) and termination (decommissioning and realising of the network resources).

The reader can also find in that publication a sequence diagram of the network slice creation process, focusing on the interaction between the different participants involved along the 5G framework architecture: verticals, management applications, SDN Controller and the DP flow agents. For the sake of completeness, this section includes two more sequence

diagrams with a further low-level explanation focusing on what happens inside the proposed 5G multi-tenant software datapath. The first diagram shows the interaction between its components to create a network slice. The second diagram describes how the incoming network traffic is handled throughout the software datapath pipeline and how the network slices are enforced.

5.6.1 Sequence diagram I: Creation of a slice in the software datapath

As illustrated in the sequence diagram in Figure 5.4, the creation of a slice in the 5G multi-tenant software datapath consists of two phases. First, the provisioning of the network resources needed to ensure the QoS requirements of the slice is carried out (steps 2 to 8 in Fig. 5.4). Second, the actions and flow associated to each slice are stored in the *Slice Definition Table* (steps 9 to 14 in Fig. 5.4). The steps involved in each phase are explained below:

Fig. 5.4 Sequence diagram for instantiation of a network slice in the proposed 5G multi-tenant software datapath

- **network resources provisioning:** The architectural component responsible for this task is the *Network Slicing Core*. The process is triggered when the NBI receives a message from the management layer through the SDN controller (steps 1 to 3). The OFPROTO module in the NBI parses the intend message and sends a request to the

Network Slicing Core module (steps 4 and 5). This request includes the network interface on which the slice is to be created and the QoS parameters of the slice (priority, minimum guaranteed bandwidth and maximum peak data allowed). In step 6, the slice is created as a HTB queuing discipline and attached to the appropriate network interface where the traffic associated with the slice will be steered and shaped. If the operation is successfully completed, a series of backwards ACK messages are sent to report the completion of the process to the management layer (steps 7 and 8).

- **Slice definition:** Once the network resources have been allocated, the SDN controller sends a new OF message to the 5G software datapath flow agent (step 9 and 10). The message contains an OF rule in which the left part identifies the data flow mapping the slice and the right part contains the actions to be performed on the traffic matching the left part, the network interface and slice ID where the traffic will be forwarded. The message is parsed and the slice definition is inserted in the *Slice Definition Table* (steps 11 and 12). Finally, similarly to the resource provisioning phase, if the action is successfully executed, a series of ACK messages are sent backwards to report the outcome of the operation (steps 13 to 15).

5.6.2 Sequence diagram II: Network traffic pipeline in the 5G software datapath

At this point, the slice has been instantiated in the Data Plane and the 5G software datapath is ready to receive traffic. Sequence Diagram 5.5 shows the logical steps involved in order to ensure that a network packet is steered to its matching slice.

First, in step 1, the incoming traffic is delivered to the 5G software datapath by the NIC driver. The ingress point is the *5G Multi-tenant Classifier* module which is in charge of performing a deep packet inspection (step 2), checking all the protocol headers with the purpose of obtaining the extended 5G flow key discussed in the previous sections. The packet and its associated 5G flow key are sent to the *Match Action Flow* module (step 3), which compares the flow key against the *Slice Definition Table* entries (steps 4 and 5). If there is an

entry matching the flow key, the packet to the *Action and Slice Enforcer* module alongside with the actions to be performed and the associated slice ID (step 6). Once the actions have been executed (step 7), the packet is finally processed by the *Network Slice Core* (step 8). The packet is queued into the buffer of the slice assigned to the packet and forwarded to the egress NIC. For each slice, the associated buffer is a queue with a "First In, First Out" (FIFO) policy where incoming packets are dropped if the queue is full (tail drop mechanism). The default size is 1000 packets which is the default value for the transmission queue length for Linux network interfaces. This parameter is customizable during the creation of a slice.

Fig. 5.5 Network traffic pipeline in the proposed 5G multi-tenant software datapath

A traffic control policy based on slice priorities is implemented by the *Network Slicing Core*. This means that traffic belonging to higher priority slices is always forwarded before traffic of lower priority slices whereas slices with the same priority are handled with a round robin policy. On the one hand, This priority mechanism is key to ensure low latency in critical mission URLLC use cases. On the other hand, if the slice priorities are not carefully configured by the network manager, it could lead to starvation of the lower priority slices in over provisioned scenarios. Finally, traffic within a particular slice is treated with a FIFO policy so that if the queue is full, the incoming traffic is dropped. An experimental validation of the priority mechanism was published in [3] (subsection 9.6.5).

5.7 Software requirements

The 5G software datapath with network slicing capabilities proposed in this research has been developed by undertaking significant extensions to the base networking functionalities provided by OVS version 2.9.2 that was the most up-to-date version of this well-known software switch at the time of beginning this research work. Therefore, following the recommendations given in the OVS documentation, the proposed solution should be built against Linux kernel versions 3.10 to 4.13.

As explained in detail in section 9.5, several OVS modules have been upgraded in both user space and kernel space to provide enhanced programmability of the DP and network slicing capabilities. OVS user space (daemon and command line applications) is not sensitive to Linux kernel version and it should compile against almost any kernel version. However, the extended OVS kernel module provided in this solution needs to be compiled and installed to replace the OVS module distributed in the upstream kernel versions, thus compatibility with the aforementioned kernel versions must be taken into consideration.

In the testbeds deployed for the empirical validation and evaluation of the solution, it has been successfully compiled and tested in two different settings. In the experiments performed in [6], the operating system was CentOS version 7.8.2003 with Linux kernel version 3.10.0. For the experiments carried out in [3], [4], and [5], the 5G software datapath was compiled on a computer where the Linux distribution was Ubuntu 18.04 with Linux kernel version 4.10.0.

Chapter 6

Results

This section provides the reader with a overall discussion and a comparative analysis of the empirical results achieved in the course of this research work, complementing with additional information and extending the explanation of these results.

Every publication composing the core of this portfolio-based thesis contains a results section where the proposed solution has been empirically validated and evaluated in a realistic testbed for one or more use cases, thereby demonstrating the robustness and suitability of the prototyped 5G software datapath to fulfill the challenging 5G KPIs in terms of latency, bandwidth and reliability. These results, reported in the second part of this document, endorse the accomplishment of the objectives established in section 1.2, in particular objectives 5, 6, 7, and 8 since these objectives are focused on the experimental assessment of the proposed 5G software datapath.

It is worth highlighting that the experiments have been carried out within the context of the European H2020 SliceNet project in a realistic 5G infrastructure with multi-tenant support in the data centre of the *UWS Beyond 5G HUB* research group based at the UWS Paisley campus [83] (see Fig. 6.1). In contributions [3], [4], and [5] the experiments have been conducted on a server of the 5G infrastructure with the following hardware specifications: Dell T5810 with an Intel Xeon E5-2630 v4 CPU, 10 cores with hyper-threading, 32768 MBytes of RAM and 512 GByte SSD hard disk. In Contribution [6], the empirical validation of the prototyped solution has been executed in a testbed consisting of a server with a

2-node NUMA architecture where each node was an Intel Xeon CPU E5-2660 v4 based on Broadwell architecture with 14 cores operating at 2 GHz and hyper-threading features. The system had a 128 GByte RAM and a 2 Terabyte SCSI HDD. The 5G infrastructure deployed in the UWS data centre follows the architecture proposed in Figure 2.1. In this sense, the aforementioned servers on which the experiments in this research work have been performed are part of the data centre shown in Fig. 6.1 and correspond to any of the servers accommodated in the edge or core segments of the architecture described in Figure 2.1.

Fig. 6.1 UWS Beyond 5G HUB infrastructure. 5G cloud computing and data centre at UWS Paisley campus facilities.

6.1 Global analysis of the results of the publications

This section contains a detailed and chronologically organized discussion of the results gathered and published in the second part of this thesis.

6.1.1 Performance overhead of the new 5G classification capabilities

Once the first functional prototype of the 5G software datapath has been designed and developed, the initial step is to measure the impact of the enhanced classification capabilities in the overall system performance. To this end, in subsection 9.6.3 of [3], a set of experiments has been executed with 4 types of traffic typically found in 5G multi-tenant networks (IP, 4G/LTE, Multi-tenant and 5G Multi-tenant traffic) using different packet sizes ranging from 64 to 1500 bytes (see table 9.4). In order to isolate the impact of the 5G classifier, there is only a single slice enforced in the software datapath in these experiments. The base version of OVS only parses the outermost headers corresponding to L2/L3/L4 IP traffic of the physical infrastructure, so this is the baseline time to compare the achieved results. Three conclusions are drawn from the analysis of the results shown in Fig. 9.8. First, regarding IP traffic, the behavior of the 5G classifier is almost identical to the OVS base implementation with gaps below 50 η secs, a difference that is statistically insignificant. These results demonstrate the efficiency and robustness in the design of the proposed solution. Second, as it could be reasonably anticipated, the main factor that penalizes the classification time is the packet structure and not the packet size. In other words, the complexity of the traffic in terms of the number of headers to be visited by the classifier is what determines the classification time. In Fig. 9.8, it can be noticed how multi-tenant 5G traffic with 2 levels of nested encapsulation (VXLAN) and GTP) and 10 headers is the type of traffic causing the highest delay, followed by multi-tenant traffic with 1 encapsulation (VXLAN) and 7 headers and 4G/LTE traffic with 1 GTP tunnel and 6 headers. Thirdly and finally, in the worst case, the absolute time cost of the 5G classifier is less than 2 μ secs, introducing an additional delay of around only 0.2 μ secs when compared with traditional IP traffic processed by the OVS base implementation.

6.1.2 Comparative of KPIs achieved in different scenarios

Table 6.1 offers a comparative of the results obtained in the different use cases and scenarios in which the proposed solution has been evaluated throughout this research. Promising results have been obtained in all scenarios tested, satisfying the stringent KPIs defined in 5G

for all traffic categories, thus proving the feasibility and suitability of the network slicing capabilities of the prototyped solution for 5G infrastructures with multi-tenant support.

Publication Chapter	[3] 9	[4] 10	[5] 11	[6] 12	[6] 12	[6] 12	[6] 12	[6] 12	[6] 12
Use case	Generic NS Validation	SFC	NB-IoT	Smart Farms	Robot Control	Smart Cities	Smart Buildings	AV-RV tactile	Het. IoT traffic
Traffic profile									
ITU Category	–	–	mMTC	mMTC	URLLC	mMTC/eMBB	eMBB	URLLC/eMBB	Heterogeneous
Overlay traffic	5G MT	5G MT	NB-IoT	IoT 5G MT	IoT 5G MT	IoT 5G MT	IoT 5G MT	IoT 5G MT	IoT 5G MT
Packet Size (Bytes)	1500	1500	1500	232	360	1500	1500	1500	232/360/1500
Scalability									
Number of Slices	8,192	8,192	1	1000	104	24	40	24	432
Number of Rules/Flows	8,192	8,192	1,048,576	1000	104	24	40	24	432
Number of Users/Devices	8,192	8,192	1,048,576	10 ⁶	208,000	72000	40000	480	280,920
KPIs achieved									
Maximum Bandwidth (Gbps)	10.00	20.00	4.00	1.86	2.40	13.82	19.20	19.00	13.83
Maximum Delay	4.98 μ s	11 μ s	4 ms	143 μ s	133 μ s	1054 μ s	955 μ s	945 μ s	956 μ s
Mpps	0.830	1.660	0.333	1.000	0.832	1.152	1.300	1.584	1.404
% Packet loss ratio	0.0 %	0.0 %	8.2 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %	0.0 %

Table 6.1 Comparative of achieved results in different use cases in terms of 5G KPIs

In [3], the scalability and performance of the system has been evaluated in a generic use case with 8192 slices enforced and 8192 users (1 per slice) transmitting traffic in 1500 byte packets reaching a combined total bandwidth of 10 Gbps. In this scenario, the 5G software datapath has been able to deliver a maximum delay of 4.98 μ s while providing high reliability (0% packet loss).

In [4], the programmability of the data plane has been extended by providing support for NSH and VXLAN-GPE protocols used in SFC/NFV infrastructures. In this scenario, the 5G software datapath acts like an ingress and egress SFC-aware classifier and a SFF with network slicing capabilities in the logical Service Data Plane Domain. The system successfully handles up to 16384 SF hops (8192 slices) achieving a total throughput of 20 Gbps with 0% packet loss and a maximum delay of 11 μ secs.

In [5], in a security use case for 5G NB-IoT networks where the software datapath played the role of firewall, the scalability limits in terms of number of rules have been explored, applying another type of action (drop). Only one slice was on board in the system, handling all incoming 5G NB-IoT traffic. The system has demonstrated to be able to cope with more than 1 million firewall rules simultaneously installed while the same number of devices were forwarding traffic from the same base station reaching a total bandwidth of 4 Gbps. In this challenging scenario, the maximum delay was around 4 ms while the packet loss ratio reached 8.2 %. The gathered results are more than satisfactory in NB-IoT infrastructures that

are not delay-sensitive scenarios and with no high reliability requirements but may not be acceptable in other use cases with more severe QoS requirements.

Publication [6] provides the highest amount of experimental results (last 6 columns of Table 6.1). The 5G software datapath has been tested on a 5G IoT infrastructure using 5 realistic use cases chosen to cover all ITU categories or a combination of them. First, the overall system performance has been evaluated individually for each use case (columns 4 to 8 in Table 6.1). Then, in the most stressful scenario, the proposal has been further evaluated when simultaneously processing 5G IoT traffic from all 5 use cases. The analysis of the results clearly have shown that the proposed 5G software datapath is able to fulfill the QoS requirements required by the verticals in all executed scenarios, providing support for up to 1 million devices for mMTC traffic, data rate peaks of 19.20 Gbps for eMBB use cases or maximum delays of 133 μ secs in critical mission communications (URLLC). In the scenario involving heterogeneous IoT traffic, with 432 slices enforced, the software datapath successfully handles the traffic coming from 281,000 IoT devices, reaching a total bandwidth of 13.83 Gbps. Notice in Table 6.12 that in all scenarios evaluated with both homogeneous and heterogeneous IoT traffic, the packet loss is 0% and the maximum delay always remains below 1 ms.

Figures 6.2 and 6.3 depict respectively a comparative of the maximum bandwidth and delay achieved for each use case. It is important to remark that these values are the maximum values measured in the most demanding configurations and that, for each use case, the 5G software datapath has been extensively evaluated by ranging different parameters in the experiments such as number of slices, number of end-users/devices or packet size. A comprehensive discussion of the experiments carried out for each individual use case can be found in the results section of every publication in the second part of this thesis.

It is worth to remark to the reader that, among the 4 published contributions, the proposed 5G software datapath with network slicing capabilities has been extensively evaluated in 10 different scenarios. For each scenario, the solution has been tested with heterogeneous traffic profiles where large batches of experiments have been conducted ranging in parameters such as bandwidth, packet size, traffic type, number of users and number of slices. The system

Fig. 6.2 Comparative of the maximum bandwidth reached for each use case evaluated.

Fig. 6.3 Comparative of the maximum delay reached for each use case evaluated.

has demonstrated in all of them being able to successfully tackle 5G traffic, meeting the 5G KPIs and QoS requirements of each use case and thus demonstrating the feasibility of the

proposal as a valid solution for this kind of infrastructures. In fact, the system limitations that have been found are those inherent to the Linux kernel networking stack in the packet processing capacity as explained in Chapter 7 (Critical Analysis).

6.2 Functional Validation of Network Slicing Capabilities

This section provides a functional validation of network slicing technology as an effective technology to ensure QoS requirements in 5G networks. Fig. 6.4 depicts the network behaviour in terms of Tx bandwidth, Rx bandwidth and packet loss ratio during the experiment conducted for validation. The experiments have been conducted in the same testbed as described in contribution [6] and the results discussed hereafter are currently in consideration for publication.

The baseline scenario consist of 500,000 mMTC IoT devices sending traffic at a constant bitrate of 1 PPS and reaching a total bandwidth of 0.92 Gbps (see green line in Fig. 6.4a). For simplicity, at this point there is only one network slice created in the software datapath. This slice has been enforced to process all the incoming traffic and it has been configured with a maximum allowed bandwidth of 1 Gbps which is also the maximum throughput of the virtual NIC on which the slice has been instantiated. Hence, all the emulated traffic transmitted from the IoT devices is forwarded throughout this slice to the virtualized services hosted in the edge or core segments of the network. At this stage, the network is not saturated and it is capable of dealing with all the incoming traffic with no packet loss (see left side of Figs. 6.4b and 6.4c).

In the instant 1.6 seconds, there is a significant increase in background traffic. The cause of this traffic spike could be many (e.g. IoT botnet attack or breach of SLAs by a vertical or end-user) although it is not relevant in this scenario. The network starts to receive simultaneously 400,000 PPS of background traffic (see red line in Fig. 6.4a). As a consequence, the network has no capacity to cope with the traffic and over 40% of the packets are dropped (see central part of Fig. 6.4c). The reader may notice in the central part of Fig. 6.4b how the bandwidth of the mMTC service traffic falls sharply as a result of

the network saturation. Furthermore, there is no security policy enforced in the data plane allowing to discriminate between authorized and harmful traffic. Thus, the 5G software datapath is unable to properly distinguish legitimate mMTC service traffic from background traffic with lower priority and it drops packets of both types of traffic indiscriminately as the queue of the network slice becomes full (see stacked bars in green and red in the central part of Fig. 6.4c).

(a) Accumulated Tx bandwidth.

(b) Accumulated Rx Bandwidth.

(c) Packet loss ratio in % for service and background traffic.

Fig. 6.4 Functional validation of network slicing capabilities.

As a measure to mitigate the illegitimate background traffic into the network, a new network slice is created (instant 2.6 seconds in Fig. 6.4). This slice redirects the background

traffic to the new network slice that has been configured with a limited bandwidth of 74 Mbps (approx. 10% of the total available bandwidth) and lower priority than the service slice. This implies that only 10% of the background traffic is sent through the 5G network and the remaining 90% is dropped. It can be noticed that, after enforcing this new network slice, the system regains stability in just 0.2 seconds, from 2.6 to 2.8 seconds in Fig. 6.4b. The authorized traffic recovers the expected bandwidth and all dropped packets match background network traffic (see right part of Figs. 6.4b and 6.4c).

Hence, through this experiment, the proposed solution has demonstrated its effectiveness by using network slicing technology to deliver fine-grained QoS policies to ensure the 5G requirements demanded by the variety of use cases supported in 5G networks.

Chapter 7

Critical Analysis

This research work has successfully accomplished the objectives set out in section 1.2 and aimed at finding a valid answer to the research questions raised when undertaking the main aim of this dissertation. The core of this port-folio based dissertation consist of 4 direct publications that have been released in top international journals and conferences and support the successful completion of the objectives as well as the novelty and feasibility of the proposed solution. Additionally, 3 software projects have been developed by the candidate. He has also contributed as co-author of 3 publications related to the research topic of this thesis. This research has been conducted under the umbrella of 2 European H2020 projects, SliceNet [1] and 6G-BRAINS [2], where the candidate has been actively involved in development and integration tasks as well as participating in plenary meetings and contributing to the publication of project deliverables. This has allowed to integrate, use and test the proposed solution in realistic scenarios and use cases deployed by these European projects.

How the objectives have been achieved is briefly explained below where the link between the objectives and the publications where they have been fulfilled is highlighted:

- Objective 1: All the peer-reviewed publication comprising the core of this dissertation include an exhaustive review and analysis of the state of the art and a clear identification of the research gap addressed. Therefore, this objective has been met throughout publications [3], [4], [5] and [6].

- Objective 2: In view of the different approaches to the concept of network slice found in the literature, a novel definition of network slice is proposed, flexible enough to encompass all of them and cover all types of traffic identified in 5G multi-tenant networks. This novel definition is the cornerstone from which the 5G multi-tenant software datapath was designed and developed. The novel definition of network slice was published in [3].
- Objective 3: A first version of the packet classifier is provided in [3]. Subsequently, the classifier was improved by adding support for the NSH protocol as published in [4]. Nevertheless, the versions of the classifier shown in [4] and [5] provide only the limited functionality required to deal with the use case addressed. The complete architecture of the classifier has not been yet released and the reader can find it in the Chapter 5 of this thesis.
- Objective 4: This objective was achieved in publication [3] although a more detailed explanation of the OF extensions carried out is provided in Chapter 5.
- Objective 5: The novel 5G software datapath with network slicing functionalities was prototyped and published in [3] where a detailed description of its architecture is provided. The evaluation and validation of the network slicing capabilities was successfully demonstrated through extensive experiments in which promising results were achieved.
- Objective 6: Enhancements to provide network slicing capabilities for SFC use cases were developed, empirically evaluated and reported in the publication [4].
- Objective 7: This objective was fulfilled in the publication [5] where the software datapath adopted the role of a firewall solution for 5G NB-IoT traffic and its scalability performance was empirically evaluated.
- Objective 8: This objective was achieved in publication [6]. The proposed solution was tested in a realistic testbed where the gathered experimental results confirmed the

effectiveness of the proposal to cope with the diverse QoS requirements demanded by 5G IoT scenarios with heterogeneous traffic such as eMBB, URLLC and mMTC.

Therefore, the main aim of this thesis has been fulfilled and this work provides a novel traffic control solution with fine-grained network slicing capabilities, which suitability for the software datapath segment of 5G multi-tenant networks has been thoroughly evaluated by extensive experiments achieving promising results in terms of 5G KPIs and QoS requirements met, thus demonstrating its effectiveness for this type of infrastructures.

Despite the novelty and high impact of this work within the research community, several challenges arose during its execution that revealed certain limitations that are worth highlighting in this document and that may provide a guide to the future line of research.

The first decision to take was whether to prototype the solution from scratch or taking as starting point the base implementation of any of the existing open source software datapaths. The first option was discarded as it implies the development of a huge software project that goes beyond the scope of a doctoral thesis. Therefore, the second option was finally adopted. It implied choosing as baseline an open source software datapath with at least some basic network functionalities on top of which to implement the novel 5G traffic classifier and network slicing capabilities. The open source approach did not pose any problem. On the contrary, It is rather aligned with the recommendations of 5G-PPP to provide open source solutions. After conducting a comparative review of the features of the existing software datapath solutions (see subsection 9.4.3), OVS was selected as starting point since it is a well-known software switch, widely used in virtualized and softwarized infrastructures and with SDN and OF support, which is an essential requisite in virtualized scenarios such as 5G multi-tenant networks covered in this research.

The first limitation arose from the fact that OVS does not perform an inspection of the network traffic by itself. Instead, OVS relies on the flow dissector of the Linux kernel networking stack, using the *sk_buff* [84] data structure attached to each packet to build the OVS flow key. Given the unfeasibility of extending the traffic classification features of the Linux kernel, it was chosen to design and develop a complete traffic classifier from scratch embedded as part of the OVS architecture. Unlike the kernel classifier, this novel

5G classifier does a deep packet inspection, accessing the encapsulated inner headers of the 5G multi-tenant traffic and providing an extended 5G key flow thus enabling a fine-grained traffic classification.

The second limitation that emerged was also related to the Linux kernel. OVS is implemented in both user space and kernel space with a sophisticated fast datapath and slow datapath mechanism that allow to achieve high performance and efficiency. However, the Linux kernel has performance limitations when processing network traffic because of the complexity of the Linux networking stack. On the one hand, the Linux kernel network stack provides a robust design and plenty of network functionalities such as routing, firewall, tunneling and encapsulation protocols support or multi-cast capabilities just to mention a few [85]. On the other hand, these features turn network traffic processing into a complex task imposing constraints on the volume of traffic the Linux kernel is able to handle. The experiments carried out in this research work yielded results similar to those reported in [86], showing that the Linux kernel limitation in processing network traffic is a matter of number of packets rather than bandwidth, being between 1 and 2 million the maximum number of PPS the kernel is able to cope with.

A possible approach to overcome this limitation is to avoid the the Linux networking stack by means of a kernel bypass tool such as Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) or eXpress Data Path (XDP). Alas, the networking functionalities, QoS capabilities and the integration with OVS of these tools was at an early stage at the time of this research work, lacking enough maturity to be considered as a valid option. At the time of completing this dissertation, the latest versions of DPDK provide a packet pipeline with QoS features [87] and some promising results such as [88] and [89] have been published in this regard. This encourages as a future research line the support of network slicing capabilities in OVS-DPDK virtual switches running in user space to deliver improved 5G KPI and higher data rates (up to 100 Gbps).

Another limitation came when implementing the new OF extensions in OVS. Due to the complexity of the OVS architecture, extending OF entails dealing with a significant number of modules, APIs, data structures and Inter-Process Communication (IPC) protocols such

as Netlink [90], in both user space and kernel space, turning it into a time-consuming task. Unlike other traffic control solutions based on Extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) [91] or P4 [92] [93] that enable real-time programmability of the datapath, this limitation restricts the flexibility and agility to increase the expressiveness of the flow definition and thus to deliver enhanced programmability of the software DP. On the other hand, existing P4 and eBPF solutions lack SDN support, which is a key capability in 5G multi-tenant infrastructures on which this research is focused.

Regarding the SFC use case addressed in Chapter 10, the logical architecture proposed and the deployed testbed only covers the Service Data Plane Domain and not the VNF provisioning which is an important aspect of these architectures. VNF provisioning, performed by the NFV MANO, orchestrates the deployment of VNFs on virtual resources such as VMs and virtual switches. NFV MANO also manages the lifecycle of the VNFs. An efficient, dynamic and smart on-demand placement of VNFs enables the network operator to honour the use case KPIs while optimally managing the limited resources available, allowing to meet the QoS requirements demanded by customers in highly changing environments such as those found in 5G multi-tenant networks. As future work, the integration and testing in NFV architectures will be carried out in realistic challenging scenarios within the context of the 5G-PPP European project *5G-INDUCE* [94] in which the candidate is currently involved as a member of the *UWS Beyond 5G HUB* research group [83].

Chapter 8

Conclusions and Future Work

The research work presented in this dissertation is supported by 4 publications in which the PhD candidate is the main author. These publications have been submitted, peer-reviewed, accepted and published in international journals and conferences with exhaustive anonymous peer-reviewed processes. The reader can find each one of these 4 publications as an individual chapter in the second part of this document. In addition, 3 software projects have also been designed and developed by the candidate as major contributions of this thesis, including the novel 5G datapath software with network slicing support as core contribution of this work. During the course of this thesis, the candidate has also co-authored 3 articles related to 5G and has participated in the release of 4 technical deliverables of the large H2020 European project SliceNet [1], in the context of which this research work has been carried out. Therefore, the total number of outcomes achieved in this thesis is 14 considering main authored publications, software projects and collaborations.

The contribution presented in this dissertation is a significant improvement with respect to the existing current state of the art, providing for the first time a novel traffic control solution with fine-grained network slicing capabilities suitable for the software datapath segment of 5G multi-tenant networks. The solution is able to deal with all types of traffic expected in 5G. Particularly, it is able to cope with the complexity of overlay traffic used in multi-tenant environments, providing network slicing features that guarantee performance isolation between tenants and user mobility as well as ensuring their QoS requirements.

The prototyped solution has empirically demonstrated its feasibility in challenging scenarios such as security for 5G NB-IoT networks, network slicing support for SFC in NFV architectures and network slicing support for heterogeneous 5G IoT traffic. As a firewall solution for NB-IoT traffic, the system demonstrated high scalability, being able to simultaneously process traffic from a million devices reaching an aggregate throughput of 4 Gbps while the maximum delay was 4 ms and the packet loss rate was 8%. As SFF in NFV environments, the system fulfilled the 5G KPIs (delay of only 11 μ secs and no packet loss) in a demanding scenario with 8192 slices enforced dealing with a total bandwidth of 20 Gbps. Finally, in the most demanding scenario, the system was tested with 5 heterogeneous IoT use cases with diverse QoS requirements deployed simultaneously and competing for network resources. The traffic profiles covered the different service categories defined by ITU or a combination and the 5G IoT framework successfully satisfied their QoS demands. The 5G IoT framework was exhaustively tested, being able to support 1 million devices for mMTC traffic, reaching peaks of 15 Gbps for eMBB traffic and ensuring delays in the order of μ secs for critical URLLC services whilst delivering high reliability in all tested use cases with 0% packet loss ratio. All the aforementioned contributions have been validated through peer-reviewed publications, thus proving that the objectives identified and targeted in section 1.2 have been satisfactorily accomplished.

The future line of work will be focused on improving the robustness and overall performance of the current version of the 5G multi-tenant software datapath. This will require mitigating the performance limitations caused by the complexity of the Linux kernel network stack. To tackle this, it is planned to explore the integration of the software datapath with kernel bypass tools such as DPDK [95], XDP [96], or PF_RING [97] that will allow to execute traffic control tasks and provide network slicing capabilities in user space. The goal is to be able of dealing with higher data rates, with the challenging target of achieving 100 Gbps while providing improved KPIs and boosted scalability. Another interesting approach to be studied will be to provide support for integration with new high-performance FPGAs recently released in the market such Netronome [98] or Mellanox [99]. The hardware offloading capabilities and the high bandwidth performance (up to 100 Gbps) of this kind of

programmable NICs have the potential to contribute considerably to improve performance and scalability in demanding 5G scenarios. The research work of this thesis will be further continued and extended in the framework of 3 European H2020 research projects related to 5G and beyond technologies in which the candidate is actively engaged at the time of finishing the writing of this dissertation: 6G-Brains [2], Arcadian-IoT [100] and 5G-Induce [101].

Part II

Accepted Publications

Chapter 9

SliceNetVSwitch: Definition, Design and Implementation of 5G Multi-Tenant Network Slicing in Software Data Paths

Journal	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management
Title	SliceNetVSwitch: Definition, Design and Implementation of 5G Multi-Tenant Network Slicing in Software Data Paths [3]
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9.1 Abstract

Network slicing is a primary Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networking technology to create virtualised and softwarised logical networks for various vertical businesses with diverging Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. Meanwhile, there is a clear gap in providing network slicing capabilities in 5G multi-tenant networks to enable guaranteed QoS in terms of well-defined network metrics for the multiple tenants sharing the same physical infrastructure. This paper designs and implements novel software data path architecture that enables such network slicing with assured QoS in 5G multi-tenant networks. Highly flexible and customisable definition of network slicing is also allowed to be aligned with different existing definitions on demand and at run time. The proposed architecture has been prototyped based on the popular Open Virtual Switch (OVS), and empirically validated to demonstrate the deployment and management of network slices with the above capabilities. Intensive scalability results are provided where more than 8,192 network slices are achieved simultaneously with warranted QoS through performance isolation in terms of bandwidth and delay in a real softwarised 5G multi-tenant infrastructure at speeds of up to 10 Gbps.

9.2 Introduction

In the upcoming years, the emerging Fifth-Generation (5G) technology will change the ecosystem of mobile networks, transforming completely the current business models. 5G technology is expected to provide a wide range of new tailored services to a wide range of vertical businesses such as Industry 4.0, Autonomous Driving, Smart Cities, Smart Grid, IoT Technology and Tele-surgery to mention a few. In this context, a vertical is a business that serves a specific set of final customers and demands a specific set of requirements to make it happens. These new use cases have extremely demanding Quality of Service (QoS) requirements in terms of latency, bandwidth, reliability, scalability and flexibility. To meet these ambitious requirements, ITU (International Telecommunication Union) has classified three main use case categories: eMBB (Enhanced Mobile Broadband), mMTC (Massive Machine Type Communications) and URLLC (Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications)[64].

In a URLLC 5G ambulance use case scenario, a paramedic is wearing a headset with camera to deliver video to the doctors at the hospital while it is in the ambulance with the patient to allow early remote tele-assessment while mobile on the road until arriving to the hospital. The network should be able to provide a reliable and timely service for patient monitoring, audio and video. This imposes strict requirements in terms of latency, reliability and warranted bandwidth and should also ensure mobility across gNBs and different mobile operators. We will use this use case along this paper to illustrate how our approach fits in the context of E2E network slicing.

It is widely recognised that traditional networks are based on the "one-size-fits-all" paradigm and thus not flexible enough to address the myriad of new use cases that are classified under the umbrella of these three ITU categories [102]. This problem is exacerbated by the fact that 5G architecture is based on softwarisation and virtualisation, using Software-Defined Networks (SDN) and Network Function Virtualisation (NFV) ([103],[104]), as a cornerstone paradigm to reduce capital expenditures (CAPEX). Softwarisation and virtualisation have enabled the capabilities to share physical infrastructures by multiple tenants (e.g., network operators) in a multi-tenant environment to further reduce both CAPEX and operating expenditure (OPEX) through virtualisation/containerization[105].

The shift to the novel 5G network slicing paradigm will enable providing customised and warranted QoS "as-a-service", in terms of well-defined QoS metrics such as bandwidth, latency and jitter, for 5G mobile operators and their customers, especially vertical businesses. To achieve this game-changing network slicing paradigm, several enabling technologies are required along the whole data path of the 5G network. This paper proposes an enabler for the software data path that interconnects virtual and physical machines to provide QoS warranties among operators sharing a physical machine and between vertical sectors using the services provided by such operators.

Currently, the most advanced software data paths allow warranting both bandwidth and latency in traditional IP networks by intelligently using packet classifiers and queuing disciplines [106] where the rules are applied to the same IP traffic along the different network segments.

However, 5G multi-tenant networks imply the use of overlay networks to deal with both 5G user mobility and tenant isolation. Overlay networks are networks that are built on top of other networks and thus, vertical in their nature. In multi-tenant infrastructures, each tenant has a dedicated overlay virtual network for their own purposes whereas all overlay networks share the same underlying physical network. Analogously, in 5G networks, each 5G user equipment (UE) has a dedicated logical connection to the User Plane Function (UPF) to allow mobility across antennas and thus, maintain connectivity whereas all the 5G traffic is shared over the same physical network. In these contexts, the definition of a network slice represents the association of overlay traffic with QoS warranties e.g., in terms of bandwidth, latency and jitter.

The main problem addressed in this paper is that there is no existing software data path that allows a flexible definition of network slices in a 5G multi-tenant infrastructure. The direct implications of this lack of support is multi-fold: no fine-grained control of 5G traffic or tenant traffic is possible, neither 5G users nor tenants have performance protection capabilities, and consequently, there is no support for the new use cases envisioned for 5G. These are the main motivations of this paper. Accordingly, the main contribution of this work is the design and implementation of a novel software data path that brings a significant number of innovations beyond the current state-of-the-art, summarised as follows:

- Providing a flexible and programmable definition of network slices in 5G multi-tenant networks by enhancing traditional packet classifiers to support 5G overlay networks.
- Extending the current programmability of the network control to support enforcing QoS (bandwidth, latency and jitter) warranties in 5G overlay networks.
- Realising a management interface where the life-cycle of network slices can be controlled in real time.
- Prototyping the above innovations in a well-known software data path, OpenVSwitch (OVS) as a proof of concept.

- Validating and demonstrating the proposed solution in a 5G multi-tenant testbed where both functional testing and scalability results have been analysed.

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows: Section 9.3 reviews the different approaches to the concept of network slicing in the current state of the art and introduces our novel proposed definition of network slice. Section 9.4 explains the 5G multi-tenant architecture proposed in this paper, the different segments it consists of and the scope of the software datapath within this architecture. This section also includes an overview of the current state-of-the-art regarding software data paths and a comparison to our proposed solution. Then, Section 9.5 describes the proposed 5G software data path architecture. Section 9.6 provides implementation details to achieve network slicing and explains the deployed scenarios to validate our contribution and the empirical results achieved in terms of functional and scalability validation. Finally, section 9.7 concludes the paper.

9.3 Network Slicing: Literature review and proposed definition of network slice

9.3.1 Existing Definitions of Network Slicing

An increasing number of studies such as Rost et al. [107], S. Zhang [108] and Afolabi et al. [104] have indicated the concept of network slice as one of the most important pillars in 5G networks. However, there is no unified vision or consensus, and in consequence, not yet a clear and precise definition of network slices, leading to various perspectives.

For instance, according to NGMN Alliance[109] (Next Generation Mobile Networks), a network slice is defined as a set of network functions running on top of physical resources where both, network functions and resources form a logical network to meet some network characteristics. GSMA [110] complements the definition of network slicing from a mobile operator's point of view, as an independent end-to-end logical network that runs on a shared physical infrastructure, capable of providing a negotiated service quality, which indicates that a network slice comprises dedicated and/or shared resources, e.g. in terms of

processing power, storage, and bandwidth and has isolation from the other network slices. Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) [111] defines a network slice as a managed group of subsets of resources, network functions at the data, control, management/orchestration and service planes at any given time. In the paper entitled "5G-TRANSFORMER: Slicing and Orchestrating Transport Networks for Industry Verticals" [112], the authors propose a complementary concept of network slice from the perspective of a vertical industry as "*a dedicated logical infrastructure provided to verticals to support their services and meeting their specific requirements*".

Therefore, the definition of a network slice can vary depending on the business roles. For vertical businesses, a network slice can be perceived as a customised service to fulfill their performance requirements in terms of QoS such as bandwidth and latency, coverage and network functions such as encryption, load-balancing, caching and so on. For Infrastructure Service Providers, a network slice could be defined as the services dedicated to and consumed by a particular tenant that needs to fulfill a set of specific requirements. Analogously, for Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), a network slice could be the services dedicated to/consumed by specific User Equipment (UE) that needs to fulfill the user's requirements.

It is clear that a 5G infrastructure is a heterogeneous ecosystem where many different business roles and technologies, both hardware and software, coexist. Network slicing should be defined either implicitly or explicitly as an end-to-end concept that must be implemented in all the different segments of the network infrastructure including Radio Access Network (RAN), Fronthaul, Edge, Transport, Core and Backbone networks.

9.3.2 Proposed Definition of the Scope of a Network Slice

Our contribution complements the definitions of network slicing in subsection 9.3.1 by providing a more accurate and precise, yet flexible definition of the scope, in terms of network traffic over the data path, that conforms a given network slice. Thus, our definition is as follows: "*a network slice in the data plane is any network flow or aggregation of flows that represents the traffic of a specific user or a specific user's service or groups of users' services, a specific tenant or a specific tenant's service, specific infrastructure or infrastructure's*

Fig. 9.1 Scenarios of different infrastructure data paths: a) traditional best-effort IP network; b) service differentiation IP network; c) traditional LTE/4G network with QoS; d) multi-tenant infrastructure with QoS support; e) 5G multi-tenant infrastructure with QoS support

service that can be uniquely identified, isolated and controlled to warranty a set of service level agreements in any of the network segments of the infrastructure, regardless of the technology, packet structure or encapsulation protocols employed". The proposed definition, firstly, includes and takes into account all previous definitions found in the current state of the art and, secondly, is more accurate and precise than previous definitions due to the flexibility enough to deal with all types of traffic that can be identified in a 5G architecture in order to cope with vertical use cases and requirements.

Figure 9.1 is composed by five different scenarios to show graphically how the different data paths evolve in complexity. Scenario a) is a *traditional best-effort IP network* where all the traffic is equally controlled in a "one-size-fits-all" paradigm. Scenario b) corresponds to the *service differentiation IP network*, usually implemented by the IP DiffServ header where services are differentiated and controlled according to QoS policies. Scenario c) represents the data path of a *traditional LTE/4G network with QoS support* provided by the Policy and Charging Rules Function (Policy and Charging Rules Function (PCRF)). The PCRF allows assigning QoS traffic rules to different users and their services in the 4G networks. This scenario fits the case where a mobile operator manages its own infrastructure without sharing resources with any tenant. Scenario d) represents the data path of a *multi-tenant infrastructure*

with QoS support where different digital service providers (Digital Service Providers (DSP)) share the same infrastructure offered by an infrastructure service provider (ISP). Both DSP and ISP services can be treated differently according to QoS policies. Finally, scenario e) represents the data path of a 5G multi-tenant infrastructure with QoS simultaneous support at multiple levels of granularity, e.g. at physical infrastructure level, at multi-tenant level, at 5G users level and at 5G users belonging to each of the virtual mobile network operators to meet the use case requirements demanded by different vertical businesses and service providers. Our definition of the scope of a network slice is flexible enough to cover all these scenarios and to the best of our knowledge, it is the first time to provide a framework with support for these capabilities.

In terms of innovation, scenario b) is widely referred to as Quality of Service/Differentiated Service Code Point (QoS/DSCP) control over traditional networks although some studies are starting to refer to it as network slicing. Our definition is a significant extension to this view by allowing different business roles to define the scope of network slices respectively in all the scenarios described. Scenario b) is considered as the state of the art, scenario c) as a very advanced deployment of 4G networks, and scenario d) as experimental features¹. Only scenario e) is flexible enough to be able to provide user mobility, multi-tenant isolation and fine-grained control over 5G traffic and thus, offer an E2E network slicing service and it is usually associated to virtualised mobile network operators. However, to the best of our knowledge, this paper is the first one to propose and achieve scenario e). Our proposed architecture provides support for all these scenarios. In fact, to fill this significant gap in the support for all of them has been our main motivation.

¹OpenStack Network and further release provide partial support for this capabilities <https://docs.openstack.org/mitaka/networking-guide/config-qos.html>

9.4 Software Data Paths: Overview of a 5G Multi-tenant Software Data Path and related work on Software Data Paths

9.4.1 Dissection of a 5G architecture: network segments and architectural components

Fig. 9.2 Overview of 5G multi-tenant data path along 5G network segments

Figure 9.2 shows an overview of the different network segments of a 5G multi-tenant network, focused on the data plane for the 5G users. From the left to the right, 5G UE devices are connected to Distributed Units (DUs) via the 5G New Radio interface. In our use case, these are headset devices held by the paramedics in the 5G ambulance to deliver video to the hospital doctor in real-time allowing early remote tele-assessment while on the road. DUs provide connectivity to the edge network segment. The edge is considered the last mile, close to the final users where Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) computers can allocate different components of the 5G architecture.

The 5G architecture is characterised by two distinct features. Firstly, architectural components have been softwarised and now can run on top of software using commodity containers/virtual machines. Secondly, COTS computers are now shared in a multi-tenancy environment where multiple telecommunication operators share the same physical infrastructure through virtualisation and tenancy isolation. The Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC)

architecture, directly associated to 5G multi-tenant networks, extends these two features to the edges of the network. Thus, the different physical machines in Figure 9.2 allocate different softwarised Centralized Units (CUs), associated to different tenants. CUs deal with the management of the radio interface, user handovers and security, among others, usually referred as gNB. To this end, CUs create an overlay network to handle the mobility of the user across DUs. The edge is connected to the core, usually by a transport network. The core network is a traditional cloud computing infrastructure. In Figure 9.2, each 5G core has a set of User Plane Function (UPF) in charge of forwarding user data in the data path and a set of control and management functions in charge of authentication, user mobility, handover management, user registry, and so on [113].

In the data path, UPF acts as a mobility anchor for the 5G users and as a gateway where they get access to the Internet. The figure shows the associated naming of the 5G functionality to the 4G equivalent in parenthesis. Thus, to warranty the quality of the video transmission across the whole network, in every single network segment, it is required a complete end-to-end network slicing solution involving: slicing of the radio interface from the paramedic device located at the ambulance, passing by the slicing in the edge network, in the transport network, in the core-network and in the multi-domain network until the doctor located at the hospital. See Figure 9.2 with all the network segments. The coordination of the control functions in charge of the enforcement of network slicing across different network segments to achieve a true E2E network slicing is carried out by the management and orchestration (MANO) architecture. In this context of E2E network slicing, our contribution is focused on the control functions in charge of the enforcement of network slicing in both edge and core network segments.

9.4.2 Virtualisation and softwarisation: key role and challenges in 5G networks

Softwarisation and virtualisation have imposed the usage of software data paths to interconnect the virtual interfaces of virtual machines (VMs) and containers to the interfaces

available in the physical machines. This is currently happening in both edge and core network segments. Figure 9.2 shows the area covered by a particular software data path in both edge and core network segments, plotted with dotted lines. Two software switches are available in each of the physical machines, and they are used to interconnect the physical network interface card (NIC) with the different virtual interfaces exposed by the hypervisor to allow VM traffic to go in/out by mean of a software switch that provides the same functionalities as an Ethernet switch. The figure also shows how different VMs, belonging to different tenants, are connected to the same software switches. This imposes significant challenges. Firstly, traffic isolation needs to be enforced for security purposes using overlay networks. Secondly, filtering and charging policies need to be applied for security and auditing purposes. Thirdly, performance isolation should be carried out to ensure that VMs make the best controlled and optimised usage of the available physical resources. The first two features can be considered the state of the art. However, the third one is not yet available in the current cloud computing stacks. The situation becomes more complex when 5G infrastructures are deployed therein, and then UPF and DU components (shown in Figure 9.2) create an overlay network to isolate the network traffic of all the mobile users among them. 5G networks need to provide network slicing by design and currently there is no such fine-grained 5G user level control of network slicing in softwarised data paths. This is the main contribution of this work.

9.4.3 Related Work on Software Data Paths

Table 9.1 Software datapath capabilities for 5G network slicing

Datapath	Classification capabilities										Control and actions capabilities								Other Features	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	API	Execution Environment
Netmap[114]	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	C Syscall	Kernel
PF Ring[115]	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	C	Kernel
DPDK[116]	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X	C API	User
OpenVSWitch	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	X	✓	X	X	X	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	✓	OpenFlow	Kernel & User
eXpress DataPath (XDP)[117]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X	✓	X	eBPF	Kernel
Linux Traffic control (TC)[118]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	eBPF & U32	Kernel
Linux Netfilter (IP Tables)[119]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	✓	X	✓	X	eBPF & U32	Kernel
Our Contribution	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	OpenFlow	Kernel & User

Table 9.1 provides a detailed comparative analysis of the main data path implementations available against the key capabilities required to provide support for network slicing. Such capabilities are differentiated in two groups: classification and control capabilities, identified

Table 9.2 5G Network slicing capabilities

	Classification Capabilities	Matching Headers	Type of Traffic Classified
1	Traditional IP Traffic	Ether/IP/[UDP]/[TCP]	Traditional user and/or services
2	Traditional DiffServ (DSCP)	IP DSCP	QoS in Traditional services
3	5G User DiffServ (DSCP)	5G User DSCP	QoS in 4G/5G User's services
4	5G User Mobility Network (UMN)	GTP	5G Users
5	IP traffic in UMN	5G User IP/[UDP]/[TCP]	5G User's services
6	5G User Mobility Overlay Network (UMN) over a Multi-Tenant Overlay Network (MON)	GTP over VXLAN/GRE	5G User connected to a Tenant network
7	IP traffic in UMN over MON	IP/[UDP]/[TCP] of a 5G User of a Tenant	5G User's services connected to a Tenant network
8	Multi-Tenant Overlay Network (MON)	VXLAN/GRE	Tenants
9	IP traffic in MON	Tenant Ether/IP/[UDP]/[TCP]	Tenant's users and/or services
10	Tenant DiffServ (DSCP)	Tenant DSCP	QoS in Tenant's services
11	5G User DiffServ (DSCP) over a Tenant	5G User DSCP over VXLAN/GRE	QoS in 5G User's services connected to a Tenant network
	Control & actions capabilities	Description	
12	Drop	Drop Packets	
13	SW Bandwidth	Set Minimum Bandwidth Warrantied and Maximum Bandwidth Available	
14	SW Latency	Set Traffic Priority (Directly associated to latency using PRIO queuing discipline)	
15	Set DSCP	Set Traditional IP DSCP field to signal/propagate QoS	
16	Inherit Overlay DSCP	Copy the DSCP value of the most inner overlay network to the outer IP DSCP field to signal/propagate QoS	
17	Forwarding	Set the interface where the packet will be forwarded	
18	Open Flow	Support for Open Flow protocol to allow SDN control capabilities	

by a number that matches the number available in table 9.2 where a complete description of such capabilities is provided. These capabilities allow defining the classification of network slices based on devices, users, tenants or their respective services according to the flexibility and precision of the definition of network slices proposed in subsection 9.3.2.

Capability 1 is required to support the *traditional best-effort IP network* scenario depicted in Fig. 9.1. Capabilities 1 and 2 are required to support the *service differentiation IP network* scenario. Capabilities 1 to 5 are required to support the *traditional LTE/4G network with QoS* scenario. Capabilities 1 and 2 and 8 to 10 are required to support the *multi-tenant infrastructure with QoS support*. Finally, capabilities 1 to 11 are required to support the *5G multi-tenant infrastructure with QoS support*. Netmap[114] and PF_RING [115] employ shared memory regions that can be mapped by both network devices and applications in user space and where network packets and their descriptors are stored. However, they do not provide any support for network functionalities such as QoS, traffic shaping or flow classification, and all these capabilities should be implemented from scratch in user space, as indicated in Table 9.1.

The Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK)[116] is a so-called *kernel bypass* framework that completely avoid the overhead introduced by the Linux kernel due to the complexity of handling a generic networking stack is avoided. Meanwhile, DPDK has maintenance and security drawbacks due precisely to this lack of Linux Kernel support and it has to re-

implement in user space all the functionality provided by the kernel. Regarding classification capabilities, DPDK provides mechanisms to guarantee QoS and traffic shaping for network traffic that has been previously classified. However, current DPDK flow classification only supports three 4-tuple flow patterns for User Datagram Protocol (UDP), Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and Stream Control Transmission Protocol (SCTP), respectively. In consequence, it lacks support for the different types of traffic available in a 5G multi-tenant infrastructure. The most widely tested software data path is the Linux Kernel Network Stack that provides two different frameworks to process packets: NetFilter[119] [120] and Linux Traffic Control (Linux Traffic Control (TC))[118]. Meanwhile, Netfilter lacks support to provide QoS and traffic shaping. On the contrary, the Linux Traffic Control does support QoS and traffic shaping but always in the context of the Tx Queues (transmission queues) of a given interface, and thus, it does not allow forwarding capabilities. Both Netfilter and TC can use either eBPF or u32 as a method for packet classification, and both provide similar capabilities to classify all the different types of traffic identified in Table 9.1. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is no proposal of a software data path that explores these technologies for a 5G multi-tenant infrastructure to provide QoS and traffic shaping capabilities, probably due to the scalability limitations of the Linux networking stack. Salva et al. [121] is the only proposal found in the reviewed literature that is able to work in a 5G multi-tenant network to process Ultra High Definition (UHD) video in 5G networks using Netfilter but focused on dropping packets in congested scenarios and not providing network slicing services with guaranteed QoS.

eXpress Data Path (XDP)[117] is a programmable packet processing platform that performs a high-speed packet processing up to 24 million PPS. Nonetheless, XDP does not provide any QoS support or any classifier that allows the identification of 5G multi-tenant flows. Although such a classifier could be implemented using eBPF, there is no previous work providing such innovations.

In terms of control, capabilities 12 to 14 in Table 9.1 associated to the isolation of bandwidth, latency and the dropping of packets are the minimal ones required to provide network slicing in a concrete network segment. Thus, only DPDK, OpenVSwitch and TC

are those that can provide such capabilities. When network slicing signaling is a requirement to consider scenarios where the slice needs to be extended across different network segments, capabilities 15 and 16 are required and this is where our contribution makes a differentiating point. It is noted that the DSCP field can be used for signaling QoS between different network devices. Our solution proposes a novel action related to the inheritance of the overlay DSCP signaling to pass the network slicing signaling information across the physical machines involved in the overlay networks and thus, ensures that such signaling is not discarded along the different network segments.

OVS [122] [123] is an open source, multi-platform software switch that has become the de-facto standard in virtualisation and SDN technologies. OVS offers support for the definition of QoS SLAs in terms of bandwidth and priority in traditional IP networks. However, it does not provide support for defining network slices, where SLAs are defined over the traffic available in overlay networks. In contrast, only our proposal, as indicated in Table 9.1, provides all the classification and control capabilities required to support network slices for all the scenarios described, which is our main innovation.

Lastly, it is worth mentioning a complementary work focused on a different data path of the 5G network, the programmable hardware data path available inside of the network interface cards (NIC). Ricart-Sanchez et al.[7] propose a hardware-accelerated data path based on FPGA using the P4 language[124] to support network slicing in 5G multi-tenant traffic. Good performance is achieved due to the hardware approach but are limited in the number of rules supported, mainly due to hardware size constraints. Only 512 multi-tenant 5G network slices can be enforced simultaneously. Our software classification is inline with this hardware approach but ours is focused on providing network slicing capabilities for the virtual machines and their services with a significantly higher level of scalability with respect to the number of network slices supported.

Fig. 9.3 Proposed software data path architecture with support for network slicing in 5G multi-tenant networks

9.5 Proposed Network Slicing Support for 5G Multi-tenant Software Data Path

Fig. 9.3 shows a detailed view of the architecture proposed to support network slicing in the software data path of 5G multi-tenant networks. This architecture implements a SDN

virtual switch that enables a dynamic and efficient network management in environments where virtualisation plays an important role such as 5G networks. The northbound interface that communicates with the SDN controller provides an OpenFlow API. OpenFlow [125] is considered the de-facto standard protocol SDN technologies. This architecture is based on a stack implemented in both the kernel and the user spaces to deal with scalability in terms of packet processing capabilities. Thus, the user space exposes OpenFlow capabilities (see upper part of fig. 9.3) where a SDN controller or simply network administrators can insert rules to program the behaviour of the data path. These rules are enforced in the kernel space only when there is active traffic that uses such rules, thereby maximising efficiency in hardware resources controlled by the kernel due to the fact that only a subset of rules is enforced at a given moment, depending on the current status of the communications. This approach is followed by OVS [123], employed as the base foundation to extend the network slicing capabilities presented in this work. Thus, in order to show clearly our contribution and innovations with respect to OVS, our proposed extensions are highlighted in Fig. 9.3.

When packets are received in the physical interface (see the bottom part of fig. 9.3), they are processed by the driver and sent to the traffic control module of the kernel. This traffic control module cannot perform any shaping of the traffic in the ingress interface since the traffic is physically there already and needs to be processed. The traffic is then inserted in our network slicing kernel module. The kernel module is a match-action pipeline where packets are classified to extract values that will be used later to be matched against the set of rules installed to determine what action needs to be enforced to such packets. This packet classification should now be extended from the traditional classification for IP networks to a more complex classifier able to support all the data paths described in subsection 9.3.2 (see 1 in Fig. 9.3). This extension is explained in subsection 9.5.1. Moreover, the definition of the rules should also be extended to utilise the metadata extracted from the classifier (see 2). This is explained in section 9.5.2. If there is no rule matching the values extracted from the classifier, the packet is sent to the user space to determine if there are any installed rules there that need to be migrated to the kernel space, related to the packets being analysed. Thus, the

protocol for communicating the kernel and the user space application needs to be extended to support the inter-exchange of such new information (see 4).

When the packets are received in the user space, they are parsed by another packet classifier to extract metadata. This extra classification process could be considered redundant but is introduced, with its overhead associated, to allow decoupling the user and the kernel spaces and allow them to work independently. Although the implementation details of this classifier are completely different to the classifier in the kernel, conceptually, they could be considered analogous and thus it also requires to be extended. Once the metadata is extracted, it is matched against the set of rules installed in the user space, usually referred to as OpenFlow tables. These tables need to be extended as well to allow the flexible definition of network slicing, including the most complex 5G multi-tenant network slices (see 5). If the metadata matches the rules stored, the packet is associated to the scope of a given network slice and thus, such rules are sent to the kernel space using the inter-exchange protocol, to be installed and executed therein (see 4). When the rule matches in the kernel, it means that the packet has been associated to a particular network slice. Thus, a set of actions can be applied over the packet to honour the QoS parameters specified in the definition of this network slice. This set of actions is described in section 9.5.3.

9.5.1 5G Multi-tenant Classification Extensions

Fig. 9.4 shows the architecture of the novel packet classifier designed to support all the data paths analysed. The parser can be followed from left to right where each of the steps is related to a layer of a protocol stack, including layer-2, tagging, layer-3, layer 4 and tunneling protocols. What makes this classifier different to traditional ones is the fact that it has arrows producing re-entrance in the classifier to continue the classification of the packets presented inside of the overlay networks. These capabilities significantly enhance the flexibility of the classifiers to support all the data paths. This is why it enables the flexible definition of network slices. It is worth noting how the key tunneling protocols for multi-tenant traffic isolation are present such as Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN), VXLAN and GRE and how the key tunneling protocols for 5G user connectivity and mobility are present such as

Fig. 9.4 Proposed flexible packet classification with support for 5G multi-tenant networks

GTP. For traditional IP networks, the classifier only conducts one iteration on the parser. For 4G/5G networks and for multi-tenant networks, the classifier performs two different iterations. For 5G multi-tenant networks, the classifier runs three different iterations. The arrows going out of VXLAN, GRE and GTP in Fig. 9.4 illustrate what is an iteration of the classifier in this context. This new packet classifier has been prototyped in both the kernel and the user spaces (see 1 in Fig. 9.3).

9.5.2 5G Multi-tenant Matching Extensions

Fig. 9.5 provides an overview of the structure used in the OpenFlow tables (see 5 in Fig. 9.3). It can be appreciated how there are different OpenFlow tables with an identifier used to assign priority in the processing of the set of rules available in the tables. Each table comprises a set of rules and each rule has an associated priority. Both rule priority and table priority determine the global processing order of such a rule. Each rule is a traditional OpenFlow match-action rule. Different metadata fields are extracted in each of the steps of the classifier to conform the set of metadata values that will be checked in the match part of the rule. These key metadata values have been significantly extended to support the flexible

Fig. 9.5 Flow table structure with metadata extracted to support for 5G multi-tenant networks

definition of network slices in the overlay networks. Hence, the traditional 6-tuple (*src ip, dst ip, l4 protocol, src port, dst port, dscp value*) has been extended to deal with the support for overlay networks associated to 5G and multi-tenant networks. To do so, the 6-tuple is utilised to match the traditional IP traffic and the metadata has been extended with another analogous 6-tuple created to match the fields of the overlay networks (*inner src ip, inner dst ip, inner L4 protocol, inner src port, inner dst port, inner dscp value*).

Meanwhile, this extension imposes challenges to be addressed. Let us focus on a simple scenario where the data path does not contain any nested overlay networks as those imposed by 5G multi-tenant networks (see E in Fig. 9.1) and the data path only has multiple non-nested overlay networks (see C and E in Fig. 9.1). To define a rule where the inner 6-tuple of the overlay network matches against a particular overlay network, such a network needs to be identified. This is why the metadata has been extended with a field (*encapsulation id*) to identify such a network. Then, a problem arises when the data path is used to support multiple encapsulation protocols simultaneously. For example, a scenario where both support for a multi-tenant infrastructure and for a 4G/5G network need to be provided at the same time. In the hypothetical scenario where the encapsulation id used to identify the overlay network of a particular tenant, it could collide with the encapsulation id used to identify

a user in a 4G/5G network. The rule will match, causing an incorrect application of the network slice. In such scenarios, there is a need to match the metadata associated to the encapsulation protocol utilised to implement the overlay network. To this end, another field entitled (*encapsulation type*) has been added. This field checks the protocol utilised to implement the overlay network. Thus, it differentiates "vxlan" and "gtp" for the above example described. Currently, this field takes 5 values: "mpls, vlan, vxlan, gre, gtp", for the proposed parser.

At this point, the definition of network slices is supported for multiple concurrent non-nested overlay networks. To extend such support to deal with nested overlay network, the maximum possible levels of nested overlays should be defined. In our prototype, it has been fixed to five levels, based on the rationale in the most complex scenario that would make sense in 5G infrastructures. These five levels comprise one overlay for the management of physical networks, one for the management of the virtual/tenant networks, one for the management of the vertical/5G user networks, one for the management of DPI packet dissection and one additional for future extensions. It is worth mentioning that there is a trade-off between overhead in the matching time and flexibility in the support provided for different data paths. Thus, the previous two new fields are repeated five times, leading to (*encapsulation type 1, encapsulation id 1,, encapsulation type 5, encapsulation id 5*).

However, a new challenge needs to be addressed. When there is a nested overlay network, the parser will populate the 6-tuple for traditional IP networks, the 6-tuple for overlay networks with the information of the first overlay network, and then when the parser processes the second overlay network, it will override the values of the 6-tuple for overlay networks with the new information, and so on. As a consequence of this overriding, the 6-tuple for overlay networks will have information only about the innermost overlay network and the information for the intermediate ones will be overridden. The alternative to overcome this limitation is to replicate five times the 6-tuple, one per each different nested overlay networks supported. That extension has been carefully considered but it imposes a significant impact on performance, overhead and scalability of the proposed approach. Thus, a trade-off has been decided based on the selection of the intermediate traffic using the encapsulation

type and encapsulation id fields whereas for the final overlay network it can also use the information of the 6-tuple associated. Thus, as a result, the metadata extracted is composed by 2 x 6-tuples plus 5 x 2-tuples, totalling 22 fields to check in the matching stage. The matching stage supports the use of wild cards to enable or disable totally or partially the matching of such a field. The extension over the traditional fields is indicated in the lower part of Fig. 9.5.

The structure of metadata of the proposed OpenFlow tables are conceptually similar to the structure of the flow tables available in the kernel space (see 5 in Fig. 9.3). However, there are some difference. Firstly, rules in the kernel space do not support wildcards. Thus, a conversion process of one to many is conducted in the rules installed in the kernel space in order to convert the wild card to the possible combinations to be matches in the kernel. Secondly, rules in the kernel space are only stored for a given time and then they expire from the table if there is no traffic matched.

9.5.3 Network Slicing Action Extension

When a network slice matches a rule, a set of actions needs to be applied to enforce performance isolation of traffic among network slices. These actions are listed as follows: i) a warranted minimum bandwidth available for this slice, ii) a maximum allowed bandwidth available for the traffic of this slice, and iii) a priority to the traffic of this slice. The priority has a direct impact on both latency and packet loss. Thus, the higher the priority, the lower the delay and packet loss. These three primitives allow network performance isolation among slices and apply to all the data paths described (Capabilities 12 to 14 shown in Table 9.1). These primitives allow enforcing performance isolation in network slices at a particular point of the network. These are the extensions depicted as 3 in Fig. 9.3. To this respect, there is no need to propagate the maximum bandwidth allowed along different network segments since it can be enforced in the perimeter of the network and will be always respected along the data path since the specific traffic does not grow (noticeably) in size during transmission.

The priority, instead, needs to be signalled along the data path to allow different data path components to be aware of the priority. In traditional IP networks, DSCP is used for this

purpose (Capability 15 in Table 9.1). However, for the novel 5G multi-tenant networks, the packet sent by a 5G user changes its shape along the data path every time the packet enters or leaves an overlay network due to the encapsulation/decapsulation process associated. Thus, a mechanism based on the copy of the DSCP value from inner to outer headers (COPY_INNER_TOS) and vice versa (COPY_OUTER_TOS) is implemented to keep these values even when the encapsulation is removed and thus allowing the signalling across the whole data path (see 3 in Fig. 9.3).

The queuing discipline implemented to enforce the warranty of both bandwidth and delay is based on a Hierarchical Token Bucket (HTB) with a bucket of a limited maximum bandwidth only and a minimum warranted bandwidth matching the maximum speed of the interface. Different children token buckets are attached to the parent to allow borrowing capacity across all the children. Then, one child is attached per network slice. The children are defined by three values: limited maximum bandwidth, minimum warranted bandwidth, and priority. When they are not explicitly defined, the system will assume the default value 0. The attachment of a new child HTB triggers a new check to see if the minimum warranted bandwidth can be fulfilled and inform the error to the management plane.

When packets arrive at an interface, they are assigned to their associated slice by mean of a rule defined in the software data path, appended to the associated child HTB to this slice. If there is no rule matched, by default the traffic is assigned to slice 0. The packets are then policed against the bandwidth limitations and after that are de-queued in strict prioritisation with respect to the priority number associated to this child HTB. This mechanism allows performance isolation of network slices in terms of bandwidth and delay.

9.5.4 5G Multi-tenant Protocol Extensions

The NetLink protocol in Linux kernel for kernel-user space inter-exchange communications has been extended to allow inter-exchanging the new metadata in the rules. When rules are moved from the user space to the kernel space, a Cartesian product needs to be applied over wildcard values in the rules, producing different rules to be implemented in the kernel space. This mechanism has been extended with the new fields proposed (see 4 in Fig. 9.3).

Consequently, the OpenFlow protocol for matching the new fields and actions has also been extended (see 5 in Fig. 9.3). Finally, the command line tools to allow administrators to insert such slice definitions in both OpenFlow tables in the user space and the kernel tables have been prototyped (see 6 in Fig. 9.3).

9.5.5 5G encapsulation/decapsulation and fine-grained network slicing capabilities

Fig. 9.6 Double encapsulation in 5G networks for tenant isolation and user mobility

Therefore, the first stage to provide fine-grained network slicing capabilities is to be able to identify these types of traffic within a 5G network and access the inner headers with the information about the user and its associated metadata (GTP TEID, VNI, etc.). This is the reason behind the design of the parser (see subsection 9.5.1) and the new fields added to the match-action rules (see subsection 9.5.2). Our approach does not propose any particular method to carry out encapsulation and decapsulation. The method used to encapsulate/decapsulate traffic does not affect our implementation and does not require any special customization. Our innovation comes from the possibility to provide support for network slicing in such complex 5G traffic.

The following command line provides an example where the video flow coming from the 5G ambulance to the hospital need to be prioritized to guarantee patient care while in the road. In summary, all the video traffic to the destination port 45536 from the paramedic

(user with GTP TEID 1500) belonging to the virtual mobile network operator with VXLAN ID 1000 is mapped to the slice with id 4 and sent out to the port *vp2* to the hospital with a very high priority (5). The reader can appreciate how this rule carry out the matching of the double encapsulated traffic according to the values indicated in the bottom part of Figure 9.6.

```

1 root@host:~$ slicenetvswitch add-flow br0
2   table=0,priority=5,in_port(vp1),eth()
3   tunnel_type_1=VXLAN, tunnel_id_1=1000,
4   tunnel_type_2=GTP, tunnel_id_2=1500,
5   inner_dst_port = 45536,
6   actions=set_slice_id(4),vp2
    
```

9.6 Implementation details and empirical results

In this section, we first provide details on the implementation of the proposed software datapath. Then, we demonstrate the suitability and scalability of the new 5G multi-tenant network slicing capabilities prototyped in *OpenSliceVSwitch*, ensuring isolation among network slices and providing mechanisms to deliver guaranteed QoS in terms of delay and bandwidth for each network slice. It also provides analysis of the overhead in performance introduced by the novel functionalities, and scalability in the number of network slices supported and how many flows can be attached to such slices.

9.6.1 Implementation Details of Network Slicing Support

The proposed software data path has been prototyped with significant extensions to OVS version 2.9.2. To achieve the new network slicing functionalities over 5G multi-tenant networks, we have extended the *openvswitch.ko* kernel module, the *vswitchd* user space daemon, and the *ovs-ofctl* and *ovs-dpctl* command line utilities in order to match the proposed architecture. The extensions are enabled and disabled in the configuration step of the compilation process of OVS by indicating new flags, as a plug-in. OpenFlow v1.4 of the

Northbound Interface of OVS has also been extended with the newly proposed fields to enable the new flexibility in the proposed various definitions of network slices. The extended version of OVS is named *OpenSliceVSwitch*. The data structures that contain the flow rules have been extended with the new fields that allow the definition of 5G network slices (see 9.5.1 and 9.5.2). These data structures are different in user space and kernel space and hence it has been needed to modify them in both modules. The source code of the *dpif* library has been extended. This library is in charge of enabling communication between the user space daemon and the kernel module using the *netlink* protocol. The format of the *netlink* messages has been extended as well as the code needed to process them. Analogously, the *ofproto* module within the user space daemon has also been enhanced. This module handles all related to the OpenFlow protocol. These new OpenFlow extensions to the fields and actions extend the expressiveness of the programmability primitives exposed to the user. This new expose has a twofold implication. First, it allows users to program the definition of the slices in the 5G network. Second, it allows the new API to be integrated in Software-Defined Network architectures, being the main pillar of the 5G networks. The new OpenFlow Extension provide a fine-grained mechanism for handling network slicing with 5G capabilities to the control and management layer.

9.6.2 Experimental Setup

Table 9.3 Range of values for each parameter in the experimental testbed

Parameter	Values	Minimum	Maximum
Packet size	64, 128, 256, 512, 768, 1024, 1280, 1500	64	1500
Bandwidth (Mbps)	1000, 5000, 10000, 15000, 20000	1000	20000
Number of Rules	1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4096, 8192, 16384, 32768, 65536	1	65536
Number of Slices	1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4196, 8192	1	8192
Type of Traffic	IP, 4G/LTE, Multi-Tenant, 5G Multi-Tenant	IP	5G Multi-Tenant

All the experiments were executed on a computer with the following hardware specifications: Dell T5810 with an Intel Xeon E5-2630 v4 Central Process Unit (CPU), 10 cores with hyper-threading, 32768 MBytes of Random Access Memory (RAM) and 512 GByte Solid State Drive (SSD) hard disk. This computer is either an edge or a core node in the proposed 5G architecture with the proposed *OpenSliceVSwitch* installed. Fig. 9.7 shows the

Fig. 9.7 Testbed deployed for 5G software data path and empirical results analysis

testbed deployed to conduct the empirical validation of the new capabilities of the prototype. The testbed is driven by the experiment script controller that sets up each experiment with different parameters. The different parameters analysed and their ranges are detailed in Table 9.3.

Firstly, for each scenario, the experiment script controller configures the software switch to inject the configurations about the slices on-boarded into the system and the associated flows to each of such slices, through a dedicated management interface (see 1 in Fig. 9.7). Secondly, the traffic generator agent (Traffic Generator Agent (TGA)) generates several Packet Capture (PCAP) files, which are then sent in parallel by the traffic sender agent (2 and 3 in Fig. 9.7). This traffic is generated by the TGA following the experiment parameters (number of tenants, number of users per tenant, number of services, number of slices, Tx bandwidth per slice, etc.). The *OpenSliceVSwitch* receives and processes the traffic in the novel match-action pipeline, i.e., parses of the packet, looks up in the match-action table and performs the slice mapping. The outgoing traffic is sent back for the purpose of being captured by the traffic receiver agent and saved in a Rx PCAP file (4 in Fig. 9.7). Finally, the results analyzer agent compares both generated PCAP files, received and sent, to obtain the results of the experiment (delay, jitter, bandwidth). Every sent packet is identified by a

unique 8-byte ID that is included in the payload. Every packet is captured twice during the transmission. First, when it is sent by the Traffic Sender. And second, when it is received by the Traffic Receiver. In both cases, the packet is saved in a PCAP file with a timestamp. The delay is calculated as the difference between both timestamps and the ID is used to unequivocally identify each packet. For performance evaluation purposes, traffic is sent and received in the same node to provide full time synchronization between sender and receiver and thus allowing to measure an accurate latency at nanosecond scale.

To empirically validate the proposed architecture, four different types of traffic were generated according to the different scenarios described in subsection 9.3.2: Traditional IP, LTE/4G, Multi-Tenant and 5G Multi-Tenant traffic. Each kind of network traffic has different number of headers. This introduces an overhead in the parsing (a deep packet dissection is performed) and matching (the key has been expanded with new fields) phases: the more complex the packet, the longer it takes to process it. Table 9.4 shows all the parameters that were ranged in the different experiments.

Table 9.4 Different types of traffic used in the testbed

Type of Traffic	Number of Headers	Number of Encapsulations	Total Headers Length (in Bytes)	Packet structure
IP	4	0	42	MAC/IP/UDP/PAYLOAD
LTE/4G	6	1	82	MAC/IP/UDP/GTP/IP/UDP/PAYLOAD
Multi-Tenant	7	1	92	MAC/IP/UDP/VXLAN/MAC/IP/UDP/PAYLOAD
5G Multi-Tenant	10	2	132	MAC/IP/UDP/VXLAN/MAC/IP/UDP/GTP/IP/UDP/PAYLOAD

9.6.3 Overhead in Network Performance

Firstly, we analysed the cost of adding the new functionalities. At 20 Gbps, Fig. 9.8 shows the average delay introduced by the proposed *OpenSliceVSwitch* when compared with the original OVS implementation by ranging the packet size. The data shown corresponds to the average of the packet processing time of the traffic transmitted along 10 seconds. Preliminary tests revealed that once traffic is steady (less than 0.3 seconds in the worst case), it remains constant in terms of delay, jitter and packet loss and thus 10 seconds is time enough to produce accurate results. For traditional IP traffic, the behaviour was fairly similar across both implementations, indicating that the extensions introduce almost no delay, which clearly

Fig. 9.8 Overhead of the proposed 5G multi-tenant software data path for different types of traffic and MTUs when compared to original OpenVSwitch

provides significant efficiency in the implementation of the new capabilities. For the most complex kinds of network traffic, the original OVS cannot be compared since it does not support such capabilities. However, it can be noticed how much extra delay is associated to the extra complexity associated to each kind of traffic. Thus, the 5G multi-tenant traffic, which is the most complex traffic to process, imposed an additional overhead of about 0.2 microseconds (us) when compared with traditional IP traffic. The absolute values were around 2 us, which is very acceptable. In all the experiments, there is not any packet loss in both OVS and our solution and we are gathering the same throughput for the sender and receiver, thus there is not any impact in the throughput.

9.6.4 Calculating Safe Boundaries

When implementing network slicing, the delay and bandwidth should be warranted within the same slice and isolated from other slices. Thus, it is important to understand how many network slices can be supported in the system before it starts to violate such warranty due to

Fig. 9.9 Analysis of delay over 5G multi-tenant traffic for the prototyped software data path (scalability with respect to the number of rules and Rx bandwidth).

lack of resources. To this end, Fig. 9.9 and Fig. 9.10 show an analysis where both delay and packet loss were respectively analysed when different transmission speeds and the number of rules were ranged linearly and exponentially, respectively. This scenario sent 1500-byte packets and there was only one slice on-boarded in the system, defined in terms of limited maximum bandwidth (20 Gbps), minimum warranted bandwidth (20 Gbps) and priority (1). 20 Gbps were sent for 10 seconds of the most complex traffic (5G multi-tenant traffic). Priority was irrelevant since there was only one slice. Then, there were as many flows as the number of rules being inserted in *OpenSliceVSwitch*. All these flows were attached, one by one, to the same slice, and thus should be treated equally. Both Fig. 9.9 and Fig. 9.10 show the difference in their treatment. As shown, up to 16384 network flows were assigned, one by one, to the same network slice; all of them were respected in terms of delay and packet loss at all the transmission speeds analysed, up to 20 Gbps. It clearly indicates the boundaries that can be used in terms of the management of network slices and on the attachment of flows to network slices before the system starts to violate the warranted performance due

to the scalability of the architecture. It is noted that 16364 network flows at 20 Gbps with 16364 rules installed in our architecture to warrant the QoS produced 0% of packet loss and a delay of 9.34 us. These results demonstrate the high scalability of the proposed architecture. Graphs for bandwidth received are not presented since it can be inferred from Tx bandwidth minus packet loss.

Similar executions were carried out with the other types of traffic in order to validate the flexibility of the proposed architecture. In all the cases, the boundaries of scalability showed similar results, in terms of around 16364 rules. Thus, these similar graphs were not presented for brevity. The following is an example of the command line command used to introduce the network slice utilised in this experiment where a slice with id *slice-id-1* was created in port *vport1* with a minimum warranted bandwidth of 10 Mbps, a maximum bandwidth of 12 Mbps and priority 0 (the highest priority). The bandwidth of the interface was limited to 1 Gbps:

```

1 root@host:~$ slicenetvswitch set port port1
2   set port port1 qos=@slice1
3   --id=slice1 create qos type=linux-htb
4   other-config: max-rate=1000000000
5   queues: 1=@slice-1
6   --id=@slice-1 create slice
7   other-config: min-rate=10000000
8   other-config: max-rate=12000000
9   other-config: priority=0
    
```

9.6.5 Empirical Validation of Network Slicing

In order to empirically validate the effectiveness of the network slices, we executed scenarios when ranging exponentially the number of slices between one and 16384. It is noted that 16384 had been empirically achieved in the results previously analysed. In this experiment, there was one network flow associated to each of the available slices. Each slice had a different priority ranging from 0 to 16384 by increment of one. They also had the same

Fig. 9.10 Analysis of packet loss ratio over 5G multi-tenant traffic for the prototyped software data path (scalability with respect to the number of rules and Rx bandwidth).

maximum limited bandwidth. It was the total bandwidth of the experiment divided by the total number of slices so that they were equally split among them. In terms of the minimum bandwidth warranted, it was setup as 100% of the maximum limited bandwidth.

This means 30 scenarios (15 scenarios ranging from 1 to 16384 slices at 20 Gbps and 15 at 10 Gbps) where both delay and packet loss should be plotted, totaling 60 graphs. For each of these graphs, it should be drawn as many series as the number of slices associated to the graph. An intensive analysis has been carried out to deal with this amount of information. For the most complex scenario where there are 16384 network slices and 16384 flows, totaling 20 Gbps, it has been empirically demonstrated that delay of all the slices were not respected under this level of stress. The reason now is completely different. The HTB queuing discipline in the Linux kernel does not support to efficiently deal with 16384 different queues, required to control all the priorities associated to each of slices, at 20 Gbps. The

Fig. 9.11 Average delay by slice in the scenario with 8192 slices where all slices were transmitting with the same bandwidth with a total throughput of 10Gbps during 6.5 seconds

most complex scenario that validated the expected behaviour in terms of the performance isolation across network slices was 8192 network slices and 8192 flows, totaling 10 Gbps. Smaller scenarios showed similar trends.

In these scenarios, there was 0% of packet loss in the whole experiment. Thus, it is irrelevant to include a graph about bandwidth and packet loss. Instead, we plotted a heat map for the analysis of delay. The network slice identification number in the Y-axis allows understanding that all the heat information available horizontally corresponds to each of the slices deployed in the data path. The X-axis allows observing how each of the network slices behaved along the duration of the experiment. This experiment sent 0.83 millions of packets per seconds of a size of 1500 bytes (i.e., at 10 Gbps). The network slice identification corresponds to the priority associated to that slice. Thus, in the analysis of delay, if the proposed network slicing control was working as expected, the heat map should gradually be increasing color from bottom to top due to the fact that slices with higher priority are faster

than those with lower priority. At the same time, the heat map kept a constant color when reading the heat map horizontally across the same slice. This behaviour perfectly matches the empirical results obtained in Fig. 9.11 where delay is shown for the 8192 slices. When reading the graph horizontally, one can notice some variations in delay along the same slices, mainly due to jitter. The important aspect is to see that such variations were reduced when the priority of the slice was increased, achieving an almost constant behaviour for the most prioritised slices. The heat map was divided in four different intervals, corresponding to four different quarterlies for all the delays analysed. The percentage of packet going to the user space with respect to the total number of packets processed in the kernel space for the worst-case scenario of our experiments, at 10 Gbps and at biggest packet size, i.e. 1500 bytes, generates “only” 0.8 Mbps, and from them, 8192 packets (1 per flow) are going to user space. Thus, 0.01% of packet are going to user space in the worst-case scenario. With respect to the uRLLC 5G ambulance use case, the traffic will be mapped to a high priority slice (one of the green slices at the bottom of the heat map). Therefore, it will allow to offer a reliable and guaranteed service with low latency to make sure the patient has the better possible care. Furthermore, in a congested network that traffic will have priority over other slices, with lower priority, and thus, the bandwidth will also be guaranteed.

Fig. 9.11 has more than 204800 data points after averaging the 5600000 data points (one per packet) on time intervals (0.25 seconds). There is only one tool, the statistical framework *R*, that is able to render this graph from more than 10 different tools analysed. When absolute values are compared between Fig. 9.9 and Fig. 9.11 for the case with one and 8192 slices at 10 Gbps, respectively, it can be appreciated how the overhead in delay to deal with only one slice was around 4.48 us whereas the delay associated to 8192 slices was around 4.98 us. These results have validated the high scalability in terms of the number of slices and the fact that the number of slices up to 8192 only affected 500 nanoseconds, which is insignificant for a software-based solution. Consequently, the system has demonstrated that it is able to handle 8192 slices with guaranteed delay, bandwidth and packet loss.

9.7 Conclusion and Future Work

An unambiguous and flexible definition of network slicing suitable for the novel 5G multi-tenant infrastructures has been provided in this paper. This definition has been used as a fundamental part for the design of new network slicing control capabilities that allow warranting QoS in terms of bandwidth and delay for network slices comprising network flows, that are flexibly defined, with enough expressiveness to allow the definition of complex 5G multi-tenant traffic and network slices, far beyond the DSCP services of the traditional TCP/IP network stack. The novel network slicing capabilities have been successfully prototyped and a complete view of the architecture of this prototype has been provided. Empirical results indicate that the implemented prototype is able to deal with up to 8192 network slices at up to 10 Gbps. The performance isolation under this level of stress is respected across all the traffic associated to each of the slices and also across different network slices. It is worth highlighting the superior results associated to this number of slices. The proposed prototype has demonstrated that the new capabilities implemented do not impose any delay with respect to a reference software (OVS) that does not support such capabilities. Even in the most stressful scenario (worst case), the maximum delay is around 5.8 us and the maximum packet loss is 0%, which are within the scope of the boundaries of the performance of 5G networks and have clearly validated the suitability of the proposed architecture.

As a future work, we will investigate different 5G use cases such as NB-IoT which requires the network to control a million devices per square meters in the software data path. Moreover, future work will seek to accelerate some of the processes on the software data path in hardware by offloading selected processing tasks. Finally, much higher transmission speeds (up to 100 Gbps) will be explored by employing kernel bypass technologies in order to study if the scalability of the number of slices can be improved by some orders of magnitude, allowing ultra-fine-grained control of the network.

Chapter 10

Scalable Software Switch Based Service Function Chaining for 5G Network Slicing

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10.1 Abstract

Service Function Chaining (SFC) is a key enabler for network slicing in the Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networks. Despite the ongoing standardisation activities and open source projects in addressing SFC, built-in 5G network support for SFC has not been sufficiently addressed on 5G Multi-tenant infrastructures. This paper proposes an Service Function Forwarder (SFF) and Classifier which is able to provide network slicing capabilities to the Service Data Plane in this type of infrastructures. The proposed prototype has been implemented as an extension of the popular Open Virtual Switch (OVS). The results of the empirical validation demonstrate that the proposed prototype is able to deal simultaneously with up to 8192 network slices with a maximum delay of 11 microseconds and 0% packet loss processing traffic at speeds up to 20 Gbps in a 5G architecture. The performance values achieved in this work are compliant with the 5G KPI expectation.

10.2 Introduction

Service Function Chaining (SFC)[126], also termed as Network Service Chaining, is a technique that uses the capabilities supplied by Software Defined Networks (SDN) to create composed network services, that is, an ordered and connected sequence of Service Functions (SFs) that must be applied to a specific packet and/or flow that has been classified previously. Some examples of SFs are L2-7 firewalls, Deep Packet Inspection (Deep Packet Inspection (DPI)), video optimizers, load balancing servers and Network Address Translation (Network Address Translation (NAT)), among others. From network operator's point of view, SFC offers tenants and network users with suites or catalogues of network services with different requirements and characteristics that can be dynamically deployed on demand in an automated manner into the multi-tenant infrastructure.

It is widely accepted that the concept of Network Slicing is one of the most significant cornerstones in 5G infrastructures. There is no unique, clear and precise definition of Network Slice, and it depends on the perspective of the different stakeholders (Vertical business, Internet Service Providers - ISP, Mobile Network Operators - MNO). For instance,

Next Generation Mobile Networks (NGMN)[109] defines a network slice as a set of network services running on top of physical resources where both network services and resources conform a logical network to deliver specific requirements. This proposal of network slice fits perfectly from the perspective of a network manager that provides network services through SF chains to the different tenants and users within a 5G multi-tenant infrastructure.

There are several proposals to standardize SFC and diverse open source projects that provide SFC reference implementations such as OpenStack [127] and OpenDayLight (Open DayLight (ODL)) [128], both using the forwarding capabilities of OpenVSwitch [123].

However, as far as the authors know, there is currently no proposed solution providing built-in 5G multi-tenant network support for the network services provided as part of the features of the network slices. 5G multi-tenant infrastructures needs to deal with tenant isolation and 5G user mobility. This work addresses such lack of support by providing a novel 5G-aware scalable OpenVSwitch (OVS) support for network slicing beyond the current state-of-the-art. The following list outlines the major contributions of this paper:

- Novel packet classification capabilities to allow the definition of network slices on the novel 5G multi-tenant networks.
- Support for handling a large number of SF chains, used to provide tailored network services as part of the previous definition of network slice.
- Empirical validation based on the extension of the OpenVSwitch reference implementation.
- Scalability and performance evaluation based on a prototypical implementation in a realistic testbed.

The reminder of the paper is structured as it follows. Section 10.3 overviews the current state of the art on SFC standards and projects that offer different approaches to providing support for SFC capabilities in 5G and multi-tenant overlay networks. Section 10.4 explains details about the proposed 5G architecture with SFC capabilities and support for network slicing. Section 10.5 explains how the OpenVSwitch base implementation has been extended

to be able to operate as an SFC-aware classifier and Service Function Forwarder (SFF) providing network slicing capabilities. Section 10.6 validates the proposed solution and provides a performance and scalability analysis. Finally, section 10.7 is focused on conclusions and future work.

10.3 Related Work

Different approaches have been proposed by Standards Development Organizations (SDO) to standardize SFC. Similarly, there are several open source projects that provide SFC implementations.

Concerning standardization, the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) describes a Network Service (NS) as a chain of VNFs and highlights the demand for a new set of orchestration and management functions to be added to the traditional model of operations, maintenance, management and provisioning used in legacy networks where Network Functions are tightly coupled to the physical infrastructure they run on [129]. In [130], ETSI identifies the most common patterns for using SDN in an NFV architectural framework and proposes a framework with 3 main components: Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) and two subsystems termed respectively Management and Orchestration (MANO) and Network Functions Virtualization Infrastructure (Network Functions Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI)) where VNFs are deployed. In the Request For Comments (RFC) 7665[126], IETF describes an SDN-based SFC architecture in which, in the data plane, an SFC classifier performs a classification of user traffic to determine which SFs must be chained to process the traffic based on application requirements. The Open Networking Foundation (ONF) and C. Zhang et al.[131] propose an architecture based on SDN technology following the IETF SFC specification and providing the requirements for the North Bound Interface (NBI) and OpenFlow (OF) extensions that would be needed to enable SFC capabilities.

Regarding implementations and projects, OpenDayLight (ODL) is an open-source project that it is hosted by the Linux Foundation. ODL provides SFC capabilities based on the IETF SFC specification. SFC is implemented in both Open vSwitch Database Management

Protocol (OVSDB) NetVirt and Group Based Policy (Group Based Policy (GBP)) SDN applications. Both SDN applications make use of OpenVSwitch as classifier controllers [132]. OpenStack [127] [133] is an open source platform for management, provisioning and orchestration of network resources that steers traffic through neutron ports chaining. OpenStack also provide support for SFC using the SFF capabilities provided by OpenVSwitch[123]. The Open Network Operating System (ONOS) project [134] is a SDN controller hosted by the Linux Foundation that also leverages OVS for SFC.

All of these standards and open source projects are able to work on traditional IP networks. Also, the most advanced SDN controllers are also able to provider SFC for the different tenant/overlay networks they are dealing with. But, to the best of our knowledge, there is not any existing solution that provides support for 5G networks that are created in the context of a network, mainly in mobile network operators (MNO) scenarios or scenario with virtualization, which is one of the main drivers of 5G networks. This is exactly what is being provided in this contribution.

Next Service Header (NSH)[135] is a data plane protocol that allows SFC encapsulation providing topological independence, service chaining, independent transport encapsulation and exchange context information between participating entities and SFs. Another benefit of using SFC, through the use of SDN, is the optimization of network resources and the improvement of applications performance. Our approach follows the usage of NSH as a way to implement SFC for network slicing.

In [136], Ahmed M. Medhat et al. provide a state-of-the-art comparative analysis regarding existing SFC solutions that considers performance and architecture dimensions. Segundo Moreno et Al. [137] address SFC in 5G architectures but the authors focus on the management and control layer. They propose an Ant Colony Algorithm (ACO)-based (Ant Colony Algorithm) solution to minimize the routing cost of a service chain and offer low-latency services in 5G networks. In [138], D.Borsatti et al. describe a work that combines segment routing with NFV-MANO in 5G networks to provide SFC spanning through several cloud domains using different technologies and support for 5G network slicing. Nonetheless,

to the best of the author's knowledge, none of the above solutions is able to deal with multi-tenant traffic and GTP traffic which is a paramount requirement in 5G networks.

10.4 Proposed Architecture

Figure 10.1 shows an overview of the logical architecture of an SFC-enabled service data plane (Service Data Plane (SDP)) domain deployed in a 5G multi-tenant network. The figure focuses on the service data plane. How the service control plane addresses the management, orchestration and provisioning of the service data plane components and the deployment of SF chains within the logical service data plane is beyond the scope of this work. One architectural principle of SFC is the topological independence from the underlying network infrastructure. In other words, the service data plane is unaware of the underlying network configuration and where the logical components and services are placed across the 5G infrastructure. In figure 10.1, it can be appreciated how the links between the entities that compose the SDP are labeled as logical connections. For instance, SFF-1 could be a virtual switch running on an edge computer, SF-2 could be placed in a virtual machine on a different edge computer and the connection between them could pass through several switches, routers, virtual interfaces and NICs as well as different transport protocols and overlay networks could be used. By decoupling the SDP from the underlying network, all this information is transparent to the logical components of the SDP. As a result, SFC allows a more flexible SF deployment solution when compared to traditional static and topological-bound SF deployment models. This leads to a better optimization of physical resources, enhancing of performance applications and an agile on-demand service delivery which is a paramount challenge in current data centers and 5G networks where virtualization plays a key role.

Four logical entities can be located in a SFC architecture: Classifiers, Service Function Forwarders (SFFs), SFC proxies and Service Functions (SFs). The entry node to an SFC domain is a classifier. The role of the classifier is to map the arriving traffic to service chains and encapsulate the packet in a NSH header. The NSH header contains information about the SF chaining the packet will traverse and metadata extracted as a result of the packet

Fig. 10.1 Logical architecture for SFC in 5G multi-tenant network

inspection. Since SFC supports reclassification to allow branching to another service chain, classifiers can be allocated at any point within the service data plane. SFF is responsible for steering the traffic to the SFs that are logically connected to it using the information provided in the NSH encapsulation. Each of these logical connections is referred as a hop within a SF chain. A SF is an entity that provides specific treatment to traffic traversing a service chain. A SFC-aware SF is able to deal with SFC encapsulation. Finally, the role of SFC Proxy is to provide support for integration of SFC-unaware SFs, receiving packets on behalf of the SF.

An SF chain defines a network service as a sequence of ordered network functions. A network slice includes in its definition network services and thus they can be provided by an SF chain. In 5G multi-tenant network is imperative to extend the programmability of the service data plane to enable network slicing capabilities that meet the peculiarities imposed by 5G multi-tenant networks where it is involved the use of overlay networks to cope with 5G user mobility across the antennas and tenant isolation. Hence, it is needed to supply a fine-grained control mechanism for 5G traffic and tenant traffic together.

In the proposed 5G multi-tenant architecture, the SFs are placed in virtual machines across the edge and core network segments where each VM belongs to the administrative domain of a tenant. Connectivity between VMs belonging the same tenant across the physical layer of the 5G architecture is delivered by OpenVSwitch instances that fulfill both SFF and classifier capabilities. To provide 5G network slicing capabilities in a SFC-enabled domain,

the OVS classifier has significantly been extended (see subsection 10.4.1). Several modules, APIs and data structures of the OVS architecture have been also extended to provide such capabilities as well as the communication between the data plane and the service control plane. These extensions are all explained in section 10.5).

10.4.1 SFC-aware 5G Multi-Tenant Classifier

Figure 10.2 depicts the proposed SFC-aware 5G multi-tenant parser that provides an extension over the traditional IP traffic classifiers. The parser consist of a set of Metadata Extractor Modules (Metadata Extractor Module (MEM)). Each MEM is responsible for extracting metadata for a specific protocol and sending the packet to the next MEM according with the next detected protocol. Subsequently, this metadata will be used by the SFF nodes to, according to the rules injected by the service control layer, determine to which SF the packet will be steered. The metadata can be also used for other purposes such as firewalls, connection tracking or QoS policies, for instance.

An innovation that implies an enhancement when compared to traditional parsers is the capability of reentrance between MEMs. Reentrance allows to send a packet to a previously visited MEM (For instance, see the arrow from VXLAN to MAC in figure 10.2) and enhance the flexibility to support different data paths as well as extract metadata from the inner headers of the encapsulated packets. This inner data is essential to identify fine grained flows in a 5G multi-tenant infrastructure in order to allocate them to the slice of a network service.

It is worth noting the fact that the parser provides support for different encapsulation and tunneling protocols (GTP, VXLAN and Generic Protocol Extension for VXLAN (VXLAN-GPE)). GTP is the protocol used to encapsulate user data and provide 5G-user mobility and connectivity. Once a GTP header is detected, the Tunnel Endpoint Identification (TEID) is extracted and used to uniquely identify a 5G user within a SF chain deployed in a 5G network. VXLAN is the tunneling protocol used to ensure isolation between tenants. As in GTP, the VXLAN network identifier (VNI), which is unique for every tenant, is extracted when parsing a VXLAN header. Finally, VXLAN-GPE is used to provide topological independence to

Fig. 10.2 Extended classifier with 5G multi-tenant and NSH support

SF chains since service forwarding occurs within the service plane and it must be transport encapsulation agnostic.

Finally, the parser is also able to deal with NSH headers that is the protocol used to convey information about the SF chain responsible for processing the packet, the next hop (SF) in that chain and metadata for exchanging information between SFs.

This proposed parsing extension enables to provide network services that are in the context of a Network Slice created for 5G multi-tenant users. This extended classifier is the main contribution of this work.

10.5 Prototype Details

The proposed classifier and SFF has been implemented extending the functionality provided by OVS version 2.9.2. To achieve the novel 5G network slicing capabilities in SFC domains several modules both in user space and kernel space have been extended across the OVS architecture. The parsers in both the kernel module (*openvswitch.ko*) and the user-land daemon (*vswtichd*) have been modified to identify the new fields required to map 5G multi-tenant traffic to SF chains. The netlink communication between kernel and user land has also been extended with the new fields. Regarding management and control features, both *ovs-dpctl* and *ovs-ofctl* command line applications have been extended to allow SFC rules to be injected in kernel and user space respectively dynamically on demand.

10.6 Empirical Results

This section provides an empirical validation of the suitability of the proposed solution. It also provides an analysis of the performance overhead introduced by the new 5G capabilities and scalability in the number of supported SF chains.

Parameter	Range of Values
Packet size (MTU)	64, 128, 256, 512, 768, 1024, 1280, 1500 Bytes
Bandwidth (Gbps)	1, 5, 10, 15, 20
Number of SFC Hops/Rules	1, 2, 4, 8, 16 ... 16384 (2^n , n in [0,1,...,14])
Type of Traffic	5G multi-tenant traffic (GTP over VXLAN)
Type of Rule	[MAC - IP - UDP - VXLAN - MAC - IP - UDP - GTP - IP - UDP - PAYLOAD] Mapping tenant VNI in VXLAN header and user TEID in GTP header to SFC

Table 10.1 Range of values for each parameter analyzed in the experiments

10.6.1 Testbed

The experiments to validate the proposed solution have been carried out on a computer with the following characteristics: Dell T5810 with Intel Xeon E5-2630 v4 CPU with 10 cores and hyper-threading support, 512 Gbyte SSD hard disk and 32 Gbytes of RAM memory. Concerning the followed methodology, each experiment was repeated 10 times. To avoid atypical values, best and worst results were discarded and the final results shown in this paper are the arithmetic mean of the remaining 8 executions.

Figure 10.3 shows the testbed deployed to perform the empirical validation of the proposed solution. The experiments are driven by the *Automated Experiment Management Agent* that deploys a customized configuration for each experiment. First, The match-action table of the SFF is populated with the SFC rules via a dedicated management interface (see 1 in Fig. 10.3). Then, the *Traffic Generator Agent* generates a PCAP file that is sent in by the *Traffic Sender Agent* (see 2 and 3 in Fig. 10.3). The traffic is then received by our extended version of OpenVSwitch where it is processed by the SFF and sent back. The received traffic is then captured by the *Traffic Receiver Agent* and saved in a PCAP file. Finally, the *Results Analyzer Agent* compares both sent and received PCAP files to obtain the results of the experiment. The parameters used in the experiments and their ranging values are listed in table 10.1.

10.6.2 Overhead Results

The implementation of a novel classifier with more complex logic that enables parsing of more protocols than traditional IP traffic-based classifiers penalizes overall performance in terms on delay. Figure 10.4 depicts the average delay in comparison to the original reference OVS implementation v2.9.2. The shown data corresponds to the average delay of traffic sent

Fig. 10.3 Testbed deployed for carrying out the experiments

at 20 Gbps during 10 seconds ranging different packet sizes (from 64 to 1500 bytes). As is it can be observed, the behavior of the delay is roughly the same for traditional IP traffic which is an indicator of the efficiency in the implementation of the new capabilities. For 5G multi-tenant traffic, the extra overhead is barely 0.2 microseconds which is a perfectly acceptable value. The total delay when processing 5G multi-tenant traffic is less than 2 microseconds which fulfills the 5G KPI expectations in terms of delay. The reader can compare these values with those shown in table 10.2 which contains the 5G KPIs about

delay for different categories of traffic proposed by the Next Generation Mobile Networks (NGMN) in its 5G white paper [139].

Fig. 10.4 Overhead of the proposed 5G multi-tenant SFC-aware classifier and Service Function Forwarder (SFF)

Type of Traffic	E2E delay (ms)
mMTC (massive Machine Type Communications)	10 ms
eMBB (enhanced Mobile Broadband)	10 ms
URLLC (Ultra Reliable Low Latency Comm.)	< 1ms

Table 10.2 5G User Experience Requirements KPIs (E2E Delay)

10.6.3 Scalability Results

In terms of scalability, it is important to know how many slices the proposed SFF classifier can handle before exposing unacceptable overheads. Figure 10.5 provides an analysis of the behaviour of the delay of packets across the SFC in scenarios with different transmission speed and number of total hops managed by the SFF. The number of SFC hops is exponentially ranged from 1 to 16384 and the transmission speed values vary linearly between 1 and 20 Gbps. The transmitted traffic consists of 1500 byte size packets lasting 10 seconds. In this experiment, each network slice is enabled by two different SFC hops used to redirect the

traffic of the network service offered in a network slice and to redirect it back to the egress node of the SFC towards its final destination. I.e. two different hops are configured per slice. Different numbers of hops per slice has also been evaluated but similar results have been achieved, thus not plotted.

Fig. 10.5 Analysis of delay over 5G multi-tenant traffic for the proposed 5G multi-tenant SFC-aware classifier and Service Function Forwarder (SFF)

Thus, each 5G flow is mapped to a different network slice inserted in the SFF and forwarded to a different SF. As it can be appreciated in figure 10.5, the delay remains fairly constant and below 3 microseconds up to 4096 SFC hops (support for 2048 network slices) regardless the received bandwidth. Between 4096 and 16834 (8192 network slices) SFC hops, the behavior is slightly irregular with peaks of 11 microseconds. At any case, these values are well within the 5G KPIs. In all cases there is a 0% packet loss and therefore no graph is shown for the packet loss.

10.7 Conclusions and future work

This work proposes a novel SFF and classifier software solution that provides network slicing support for SFC in 5G multi-tenant networks where the scope of the network slice definition fits with a set of network services. A fine-grained classification of the traffic allows to offer tailored services to tenants and 5G users. The proposal has been empirically validated and

the results show satisfactory and promising performance: 16834 SFC hops can be handled concurrently in a stressful scenario processing 20 Gbps, introducing a maximum delay of 11 microseconds and 0% of packet loss. The achieved results fulfill the parameters suggested in the 5G Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

As a future work, this ongoing research will focus on how to provide a mechanism to ensure performance isolation between SF chains in order to warranty QoS requirements along the whole data path in terms of bandwidth, delay and jitter. The idea is to combine these foreseen capabilities with the ability described in this contribution. Besides, the classifier will be extended to be able to identify other protocols used in virtualization environments ant multi-tenant architectures like GRE, Stateless Transport Protocol (STT) or Generic Networking Virtualization Encapsulation (GENEVE). The impact of this extension on the overall performance of the system will be evaluated.

Chapter 11

Highly-Scalable Software Firewall Supporting One Million Rules for 5G NB-IoT Networks

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Authors	Antonio Matencio Escolar, Jose M Alcaraz Calero and Qi Wang
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11.1 Abstract

There is a significant lack of software firewalls for 5G networks especially when the support for the Internet of Things (IoT) technologies such as NB-IoT are considered. The main contribution of this research work is an advanced software firewall based on the Open Virtual Switch (OVS), which is able to provide firewall capabilities over these 5G IoT devices. The proposed software firewall is able to significantly scale up the number of rules to fulfill the 5G Key Performance Indicator of controlling 1 million IoT devices per square kilometer. Intensive experimental results are achieved in this work, validating the suitability of the proposed architecture for this remarkable level of scalability. In the most demanding conditions, where more than 1 million of firewall rules are installed and 1 million NB-IoT devices are sending traffic, yielding a total of 4 Gbps, the system shows only 8% of packet loss and 4 ms delay.

11.2 Introduction

The maximum 5G speed in the New Radio (NR) interface reported by Huawei in October 2019 [140] is 3.67 Gbps, beating their previous world-wide mark of 2 Gbps. A more typical scenario using the same technology indicates 1 Gbps for the coverage of 1 square kilometer. In that coverage, a 5G NB-IoT (Narrow Band-Internet of Things) network is expected to provide access to 1,000,000 devices according to the 5G Key Performance Indicator (KPI) defined by 5G Public-Private Partnership (PPP). When combined with softwarization and virtualization, which are the cornerstone technologies in 5G architectures to reduce capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX), it imposes a significant scalability challenge and performance overhead that need to be addressed to fulfill the ambitious 5G KPI.

Currently, software firewalls are primarily designed to protect traditional IP networks. The support to protect overlay IP networks used by 5G NB-IoT architectures has not been sufficiently provided. Moreover, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there is no published software-based firewall solution that is able to deal with the level of scalability envisioned

for the massive number of IoT devices. These gaps pose significant security challenges that need to be addressed.

This paper attempts to address these problems by providing a novel software firewall capability with support for 5G NB-IoT overlay networks. The software firewall exposes a significant increase in the scalability with respect to the number of rules, up to 5G expectations. The following list enumerates the main contributions of this work:

- Novel 5G software firewall architecture with advanced capabilities for 5G-enabled IoT networks.
- Significant enhancement of the scalability in terms of handling a large number of firewall rules for security proposes, being able to handle up to 1 million firewall rules per software firewall.
- Empirical validation of the scalability and performance of the proposed solution based on a prototypical implementation in a realistic testbed.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 11.3 outlines a state of the art on software firewall capabilities and firewall filtering in overlay networks. Section 11.4 describes the design and prototyping of the proposed scalable 5G IoT firewall architecture. Section 11.5 presents the implementation of the proposed architecture. Section 11.6 validates the solution and provides a scalability analysis of the prototype. Finally, Section 11.7 provides conclusions and future work.

11.3 Related Work

The vast majority of open source and commercial software switches that could be extended to act as firewalls simply have not been designed to support overlay networks, and they merely work in traditional IP networks. For example, Linux iptables, ebtables, ipcop, pfSense, ipFire, ufw, smoothwall and VyOS firewalls do not support any overlay network, including the GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP) used to implement 5G NB-IoT networks. Windows

Firewall, Avast, AVS, TinyWall, GlassFire and many others also lack the same capability for the Windows operating system.

There is significant absence of solutions to address the lack of support of firewall policies over the GTP protocol, used in LTE, LTE-Advanced (LTE-A) and 5G and on their respective adaptations for cellular IoT networks, LTE-M and NB-IoT. In the hardware side, Ricart et al. [141] provided a hardware appliance with these novel capabilities able to work up to 3.67 Gbps and up to 1024 wildcard-enabled firewall rules against 512 flows (305 kilo packets per second - KPPS). In the software side, Salva et al. [121] indicated that the maximum rules support for Linux IP tables, with an extended version to support GTP traffic, in the most ideal conditions, are 512 rules when traffic is transferred at 1 Gbps against 512 flows (666 KPPS). Salva et al. [142], further investigated the support for NB-IoT traffic using IP tables-BPF integration, optimized for scalability on the number of rules, achieving a maximum of 4096 rules for 4096 simultaneous flows at 90 Mbps (60 KPPS). At higher speeds, packets drops and delay start to be unacceptable. Such level of scalability will work for normal cellular network end users although it is not able to deal with the significantly higher level of scalability envisioned for 5G IoT. In early 2019, FortiGate, a software appliance from Fortinet [143], claimed to provide a carrier-grade firewall support for LTE, LTE-A, 5G and IoT. However, these capabilities are not reflected yet in their data sheets, no performance has been published and for their highest-end product (VM08), they claimed to provide support for up to 4 Gbps with a maximum of 40k firewall rules. Even that level of scalability in software appliances will not be suitable for 5G requirements. Another way to address this scalability is to perform the deployment of several virtual appliances in the same physical machine in order to use a distributed load-balancing approach to deal with scalability.

The lack of support for such advanced firewall capabilities in software solutions and the need to push the scalability boundaries to truly support for 5G networks has been the main motivation of this work.

11.4 The Proposed Architecture

Fig. 11.1 provides an overview of the proposed highly-scalable 5G NB-IoT software firewall architecture. It has been logically divided in three different planes. The kernel space module works at the maximum speed with hardware administrative privileges (execution ring 1). When a packet is received by the network interface card (NIC) driver, it is inserted into the match-action pipeline implemented in this kernel module. The match-action pipeline applies the firewall rules to the packets being received in the data path. To do so, the packets are parsed using the extracted metadata. An extension to the traditional IP packet parsing has been designed and prototyped to be able to extract information about the GTP protocol and also about the inner IP headers that are inside the tunneling protocol to be able to provide firewall capabilities not only to traditional IP traffic but also to 5G NB-IoT traffic. This parsing extension is explained later in subsection 11.2. The metadata extracted is matched against a firewall rule table where all the firewall rules are inserted for a lookup in the table. It is noted that the traditional design of a table of rules only considers fields of the traditional IP network. The proposed system extended the rule table with the new fields related to the GTP protocol in order to include the new expressions of the firewall rules for 5G NB-IoT. If there is a match in the rule table, then the action is taken. Different default policies are supported with deny or accept by default which is seen as the last implicit action to be applied if there is not any match against the rules. The key for speed is the design in the kernel space. Meanwhile, there is a noticeable trend to bypass the kernel and implement everything in the user space. Our approach is to make use of the kernel which is a much more optimized way when compared with the traditional kernel modules, and thus a new kernel module is proposed. To help achieve scalability, we have taken a co-design approach between kernel and user spaces, and thus further introduced another new module implemented in the user space. This module keeps all the rules inserted into the firewall by the user in memory. The module employs OpenFlow and the architecture of tables defined in OpenFlow for this purpose. When the packets being processed in the kernel do not match any of the installed rules in the table of the kernel, a communication between kernel and user spaces takes place to perform a lookup in the user-space tables. If there is a match, the firewall

rule in the user space is installed in the kernel module for performance purposes. This communication between user space and kernel module has been also extended in order to inter-exchange all the new metadata required to be copied between user and kernel spaces. Then, another key decision for scalability has been the fact that when rules are installed in the kernel, if they have not been looked up for a period of time, they are removed from the table, freeing up resources and thus enhancing scalability. When new packets come, the rules will be reinstalled into the kernel by means of the user space to kernel migration of rules mechanisms. This architectural philosophy is not radically new, and the Open Virtual Switch (OVS) [123] software switch, used for multiple purposes in softwarized networks, adopts a similar architecture. However, OVS does not provide firewall capabilities for 5G NB-IoT, which is addressed in this work. Our prototypes are a significant extension of the original OVS software to deal with an enhanced level of scalability.

Fig. 11.1 Architectural of the proposed software firewall

11.4.1 NB-IoT Parsing Extension

Fig. 11.2 shows the proposed extension over the traditional parsing of IP packets. When a network packet arrived at the parser, it visits different metadata extractors. For example,

in the MAC processing, the source and destination MAC addresses and the Ethernet type field are extracted in order to allow later on creating firewall rules based on the metadata. Analogously, source and destination IP addresses and key attributes available in the IP header are extracted, including transport protocol, Differentiated Services Control Protocol (DSCP) field, time-to-live (TTL) field, among others. In UDP and TCP, the source and destination ports are extracted. For TCP, all the TCP flags are also extracted to allow key security firewall rules to be applied and to deal with the tracking of the connection to support both stateful and stateless operational modes on the firewall. Then, when the GTP protocol is detected, the Tunnel Endpoint Identification (TEID) is extracted. This field is used to uniquely identify a 5G NB-IoT device across all the antennas of the network. This tunneling protocol has the IP packets generated by the NB-IoT devices (inner traffic) whereas the outer traffic is the 5G infrastructure traffic required to deal with NB-IoT connectivity, control and mobility (if supported). Thus, the inner traffic need to be parsed again. To do so, it takes a re-entrance on the previously visited parsing steps. It will allow extracting now the information related to the NB-IoT devices including, specifically, the source and destination IP addresses, ports and other key firewall information. This extension in the parsing provides the number capabilities to deal with NB-IoT firewall rules, which is one of the main motivations of this paper.

Fig. 11.2 Extended parser with 5G NB-IoT support

The following excerpt of code is an example of a firewall rule supported now thanks to our extension (rule in JSON format). A flow from inner source port 16500 of a given NB-IoT device with source IP address 10.10.10.1 going to outer destination port 2152 is identified

in the 5G network with the TEID 2001 using GTP as the tunneling protocol, and it will be dropped once mapped:

```
1 {"rule": {
2   "firewall": "fw0",
3   "action": "add-rule",
4   "table": 0,
5   "cookie": "0x100",
6   "priority": "0xFF",
7   "match": [
8     {"outer_destination_port": 2152 },
9     {"tunnel_protocol": "GTP" },
10    {"tunnel_key": 2001 },
11    {"inner_source_ip": "10.10.10.1" },
12    {"inner_source_port": 16500 }
13  ],
14  "action": "drop"
15 }
16 }
```

Listing 11.1 Firewall rule in JSON format matching GTP traffic

As it can be observed, each firewall rule has a field termed "cookie" which purpose is to uniquely identify a rule. Besides, Each rule is inserted into a table and a priority is set for it.

11.5 Implementation

The proposed architecture has been implemented as extensions in OVS (version 2.9.2) using the C language in both user and kernel spaces. More details of the original OVS can be found in [122]. To be concrete, the first extension has been carried out over the kernel module of OVS (openvswitch.ko) to support parsing of 5G NB-IoT protocol and

new fields in the expressions of firewall rules. The second extension has been applied on the Netlink communication between the `openvswitch.ko` module and the OVS user-space software daemon (`vswitchd`). The command line tools have also been extended, including both `ovs-dpctl` and `ovs-ofctl` in order to allow the administrator to insert the rules in both OpenFlow tables and kernel tables directly on demand. These prototypical extensions were introduced following exactly the design presented in Section 11.4, and the results achieved in this prototype are described in Section 11.6.

11.6 Experiment Results

This section validates the suitability of the proposed NB-IoT firewall and analyses the scalability achieved in the number of rules and the performance achieved in terms of delay, jitter, packet loss and throughput.

11.6.1 Testbed Description

Experiments have been conducted on a host computer testbed for the proposed OVS-based 5G NB-IoT software firewall, with the following specification: Dell T5810 with 1xIntel Xeon E5-2630 v4 CPU (10 cores with hyper-threading), 32GB RAM, and 512GB SSD HDD. Fig. 11.3 depicts the setup of the testbed deployed to empirically validate the proposed firewall. Experiments are handled by the *experiment controller script* that customizes the configuration of each experiment with different parameters that allow analyzing the behaviour of the firewall in different scenarios. These parameters and their range of values are explained in Subsection 11.6.2.

For each experiment, the *experiment controller script* injected the rules into the NB-IoT 5G firewall through a dedicated management interface (See 1 in Fig. 11.3). After that, the *traffic generator agent* generated several pcap files that were sent in parallel by the *traffic sender agent* (See 2 and 3 in Fig. 11.3). The pcap files generated are compliant with the NB-IoT protocol. The number of flows generated by each NB-IoT device was fixed to 1 flow, and the number of NB-IoT devices sending traffic was always matched with the

number of rules. Thus, a rule always produced a match to a given flow leading to dropping or passing. This is a way to ensure that the experiments were fair and there was not any kind of artificial acceleration due to the synthetic generation of the PCAPs. In fact, each NB-IoT device available in the pcap had different source and destination IP address, different source and destination ports, and even different GTP tunnel ID. This traffic represented the pattern and behaviour of a 5G node allocated at the edge of the network, where all these NB-IoT devices were connected to the radio interface managed by the edge node. The traffic was then received by the 5G NB-IoT firewall, which processed it through the NB-IoT 5G Match-Action pipeline. The outgoing traffic was sent back to the virtual machine where it was captured by the *traffic receiver agent* and saved in a pcap file. In a final step, the *results analyzer agent* compared both sent and received pcap files to gather the experiment results (delay, jitter, packet loss and throughput). In the experiments, the receiver received the whole traffic originally sent since there is an "drop-by-default" firewall policy and each flow has a "pass/accept" action associated.

11.6.2 Experiments

Table 11.1 lists the range of values of the different parameters that configured each of the experiments conducted to validate and evaluate the proposed 5G NB-IoT software firewall. As shown in the table, NB-IoT traffic consisting of 1500 byte MTU was transmitted by every IoT device. Scalability was analyzed in two different dimensions: the number of IoT devices sending traffic and amount of traffic sent by each of these devices. As mentioned, the number of NB-IoT devices matched the number of rules inserted in the firewall. The traffic sent by each of the IoT devices was classified and processed in an isolated way with respect to the rest of the traffic and each of the rules was tailored for that purpose. Through this scheme, an ultra-fine grained firewall control mechanism was provided for the NB-IoT traffic in a 5G architecture. For simplicity, for each different configuration executed in the testbed, all IoT devices transmitted traffic with the same bandwidth. This bandwidth was the result of dividing the total available bandwidth by the number of connected IoT devices.

Fig. 11.3 Testbed deployed for the proposed OVS-based 5G NB-IoT software firewall

With Regard to the methodology applied, each experiment was executed 10 times. To avoid outlier values, the best and worst results were ignored and the final outcomes shown in this paper are the arithmetic mean of the remaining 8 experiments.

Parameter	Range of Values
Packet size (MTU)	1500 Bytes
Bandwidth (Mbps)	1000, 2000, 3000, 4000
Number of Devices/Rules	1, 2, 4, 8, 16 ... 1048576 (2^n , n in [0,1,...,20])
Type of Traffic	NB-IoT Traffic (GTP)
Type of Rule	Matching inner source ip address and inner destination port

Table 11.1 Range of values for each parameter analyzed in the experiments

11.6.3 Results

Fig. 11.4 shows the evolution of packets loss when ranging exponentially both the number of firewall rules and devices in 1:1 ratio and also when ranging linearly the total bandwidth for transmission per corresponding number of devices. It is worth mentioning that 1 Gbps there was no packet loss when 1 million of flows and rules were installed in the firewall. For the case of 4 Gbps, speeds currently aligned with the maximum performance achieved in the new radio interface up to date, there was no packet loss either up to 32k rules. Beyond these boundaries of system stability, packet loss started to appear and in the most stressful condition, at 4 Gbps, with 1 million rules and 1 million devices, a very reasonable 8.2% packet loss ratio was achieved. These numbers are remarkably advantageous especially considering highly demanding nature of the IoT communications. It is noted that in all the scenarios tested, the transmission throughput was exactly the same as the reception throughput with the variations associated to the percentage of packet loss. Thus it has been decided not to include this graph although these facts are critical to understand that all the graphs presented next are accurate.

Fig. 11.5 shows the evolution of the delay incurred by the software firewall when ranging the same parameters. The behaviour of the graph is similar to that of packet loss. The system was stable despite the delay added by the number of rules up to 32k rules. After this threshold, the system behaved very decently at 1 and 2 Gbps. When the throughput were scaled to 3 and 4 Gbps, the delay was increased exponentially. It is very relevant to indicate that at 1 Gbps, the delay inserted when there was 1 million rules was around 0.1 ms and at 4 Gbps, the delay added was around 4 ms. These numbers are far beyond better than the acceptance boundaries

Fig. 11.4 Scalability analysis of packet loss

defined for 5G NB-IoT traditionally associated to delay-tolerant applications. These results show that the firewall will be suitable even for delay-sensitive 5G NB-IoT use cases.

Fig. 11.5 Scalability analysis of delay

Regarding the analysis of jitter (i.e., variance in packet delays), Fig. 11.6 shows a very similar trend with respect to the delay graph presented in Fig. 11.5. The stable boundaries were similar and then an exponential increase appeared following a similar pattern. This time, in the most stressed scenario (at 4 Gbps, 1 millions flows and 1 million rules), the jitter

was about 3.5 ms. When combined with the delay, the worst case maximum delay would be lower than 8 ms.

Fig. 11.6 Scalability analysis of jitter

These results have validated the suitability of the proposed architecture for the scalability and performance envisioned in 5G networks.

11.7 Conclusion

This paper proposes a highly scalable software firewall architecture that provides support for NB-IoT devices in 5G networks and beyond. The architecture has been validated with the extreme use case of massive machine-type communications composed by traffic of 1 million devices, totalling 4 Gbps, with 1 million of firewall rules installed. Experiment results have shown that the solution has very promising performance of around 8% of packet losses and just 4 ms delay under these extreme conditions where all these devices are connected to the same radio interface and the software firewall is deployed in the edges of the network. The level of scalability is compliant with the 5G KPI expectation.

In future work, this level of high scalability will be explored in the context of network slicing and network slice management where different types of actions need to be applied

over the same type of traffic. In addition, the compatibility to other IoT protocols will also be investigated.

Chapter 12

Adaptive Network Slicing in Multi-tenant 5G IoT Networks

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12.1 Abstract

The Fifth Generation (5G) mobile networking coupled with Internet of Things (IoT) can provide innovative solutions for a wide range of uses cases. The flexibility of virtualized, softwarized and multi-tenant infrastructures and the high performance promised by 5G technology are key to cope with the deployment of the IoT use cases demanded by various vertical businesses. Such 5G IoT use cases incur challenging Quality of Service (QoS) requirements especially connectivity for millions of IoT devices to achieve massive Machine-Type Communication (mMTC). In addition, network slicing is a key enabling technology in 5G multi-tenant networks to create logical virtualized networks for delivering customised solutions to meet diverse QoS requirements. This work presents a 5G IoT framework with network slicing capabilities able to manage a vast number of heterogeneous IoT network slices dynamically on demand. The proposed solution has been empirically tested and validated in five realistic vertical-oriented IoT use cases. The achieved results demonstrate a excellent stability, isolation and scalability while being able to meet extreme QoS requirements even in the most congested and stressful scenarios.

12.2 Introduction

The Fifth Generation (5G) mobile networks allow instantiating multiple concurrent logical systems to meet diverse vertical industry service requirements, over a common underlying softwarized, virtualized and multi-tenant infrastructure. The Internet of Things (IoT) is being embraced by the 5G architecture, where various vertical IoT services such as Industrial IoT (IIoT), Smart Agriculture or Smart Cities among others, can be instantiated over the same shared physical network and cloudified 5G infrastructure.

Each vertical imposes different requirements in terms of network Quality of Service (QoS) parameters such as bandwidth, reliability and latency/delay. For instance, IIoT typically requires high reliability to cope with critical services based on Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications (URLLC). Smart agriculture scenarios may need Massive Machine-Type Communication (mMTC), and demand efficient communications with millions

of constrained IoT devices. Some use cases in Smart cities e.g., traffic monitoring through video cameras would need Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) communication to achieve high data rates and low latency.

To meet the diverging network performance demands by heterogeneous vertical use cases, network slicing has emerged as a key approach in 5G. A network slice can be defined as a set of network functions and the associated network resources that are logically isolated and allocated according to the Service-Level Agreement (SLA), and can be shared per kind of traffic, per service, protocol or application, or dedicated per user or per device, if allowed by a flexible 5G management system. Different types of communications can be supported by different kinds of network slices [104].

Therefore, different IoT services can be virtualized and instantiated in dedicated slices based on different service requirements, where IoT service providers can allocate those slices in a cost-effective way and attend to users preferences. Industrial IoT services, e.g. mission critical services, can be moved to the Edge of the network in a specific slice to minimize transition delay while massive IoT services e.g. for smart cities will require vast number of dedicated slices, each one with different QoS needs. As recently highlighted as major challenges in [144], 5G network slicing should enable new business models for delivering heterogeneous 5G services exploited by different industry verticals, combining different 5G services types including mMTC, URLLC and eMBB while ensuring necessary performance and scalability through proper slice isolation and dynamism.

To realize a truly scalable 5G IoT slice management, there could be multiple concurrent shared slices plus a potential vast number of dedicated slices allocated per IoT device, with different network parameters needs, and with different packet sizes and protocols. In the worst case, this could mean that the virtual switches in the datapath need to cope with millions of heterogeneous concurrent adaptive slices.

5G management frameworks and network elements, such as virtual network switches and routers deployed over the 5G infrastructure need to be evolved to control dynamically the network traffic of multiple, heterogeneous and concurrent tenants, from diverse verticals, ensuring QoS parameters over the shared network's available resources. The new imposed

requirements are manifold, as the new 5G slicing implementations need to deal with nested-encapsulation in the datapath to support both mobility and multi-tenancy typically through tunnelling protocols such as VXLAN and GTP, support scalability to handle a vast number of concurrent heterogeneous slices, enable flexibility and elasticity to manage and orchestrate dynamically on demand slicing rules over multiple virtual network appliances and thus ensure the slices end-to-end, and assure interoperability with enriched slicing models enforceable and understandable in the data plane.

To the best of the author's knowledge, the solutions identified in the current literature provide either partial solutions for specific use cases or present preliminary outcomes. They have not been validated in a realistic 5G IoT scenario where different services with varying QoS requirements and traffic profile are demanded, challenging the 5G infrastructure and imposing the imperative of addressing 5G network traffic with multiple levels of nested encapsulation.

To contribute to addressing the above challenges, this paper introduces a new 5G IoT slice control framework that allows the adaptive instantiation and management of heterogeneous and evolving slices over multiple technological IoT domains, which demand different slicing according to the vertical needs.

The contributions of this paper are manifold:

- A practical cognitive network management framework is presented for autonomic enforcement of scalable network slicing in 5G IoT networks.
- A new, highly scalable network slicing approach is proposed for multi-tenant 5G networks especially devised for virtualized, multi-tenant, and mMTC communications, managing thousands of heterogeneous slices.
- A new enforceable protocol is defined to apply network slices in the 5G IoT network and cope with in a homogeneous and technology-agnostic approach with the different technologies and hardware composing the data plane.

- The network slicing approach has been implemented in the data plane by significantly extending Open vSwitch (OVS), using a kernel space mechanism in order to have full control of the slicing in virtualized 5G IoT networks.
- Agile and flexible management of slices which allows dynamic adaptation on demand to the verticals' needs.
- The proposed solution has been empirically validated, with performance evaluation over a real 5G IoT network deployment using vertical-oriented use cases.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 12.3 we analyze the current state of the art regarding network slicing in 5G IoT networks. Section 12.4 lays out the specific requisites that 5G IoT networks must satisfy to provide adaptive network slicing capabilities and provides an overview of the proposed 5G IoT multi-tenant architecture. Section 12.5 presents the proposed Slice Control architecture. Then, Section 12.6 introduces the vertical-oriented IoT use cases used to empirically evaluate and validate the solution proposed in this work. Section 12.7 provides implementation details and a description of the testbed deployed to conduct the experiments. Section 12.8 presents the achieved experimental results in terms of scalability, QoS performance and adaptive management of the life cycle of network slices. Finally, conclusions are drawn with future research activities outlined in Section 12.9.

12.3 Background and Related Work

Network slicing for 5G IoT deployments plays a key role to provide the capability to enable the new business models expected in the IoT era. This fact is evidenced by a significant amount of research activity and contributions on this subject.

In a recent survey, Khan et al. [145] review the latest advances of network slicing for IoT verticals and use cases, including smart transport systems, smart industry, smart homes and smart care. They identify scalability, interoperability and efficient resource allocation among the major open research challenges relevant to network slicing. Furthermore, the authors highlight as one of their main conclusions that network slicing is an indispensable

technology to enable a wide range of 5G use cases and beyond. They also underline that it is necessary to propose novel adaptive network slicing management schemes to cope on demand with services of varying users' demands.

Several authors have proposed 5G-based solutions for specific IoT use cases. For instance, Cheng et al. [146] propose a 5G IoT architecture for smart manufacturing although no implementation is provided. In [147], the authors analyze how network slicing technology in 5G networks can meet the specific needs of different smart grid services to support multiple power business scenarios in Power Internet of Things (PIoT). In [148], the authors focus on IoT solutions for Smart Home applications and propose a 5G architecture where three slices are deployed (Smart Home security, eMBB traffic and Massive IoT traffic). Unlike our proposal that provides a 5G IoT framework able to cope with heterogeneous 5G IoT traffic, all these work address the deployment of IoT use cases in 5G infrastructures from the perspective of a given single use case and the authors do not provide an empirical validation and evaluation of the offered solution.

Kapassa et al. [149] describe an IoT-oriented architecture for 5G network slicing that enables the allocation of Quality of Service (QoS) of diverse concurrent IoT applications and services with different requirements. Nonetheless, they do not implement or validate their proposal.

In [150], the authors propose an authentication framework supporting network slicing and fog computing for 5G IoT, allowing users to establish secure connections with IoT devices through dedicated slices. Unlike their work, we focus on the mechanism for slice management in the 5G datapath, rather than security aspects of slicing.

Kurtz et al. [151] propose and implement a slicing mechanism for 5G networks based on SDN/NFV, evaluated in demanding critical infrastructure use cases. They use OVS and SDN controllers to enforce the slices. However, they do not use real 5G traffic that demands specific modifications (e.g. due to encapsulation to provide tenant isolation and user mobility in 5G networks) in the datapath management (e.g. adaptation in switches like OVS) to handle the slices.

In [74], the authors propose an end-to-end mIoT slicing mechanism with enhanced control and user planes (CP/UP) for the 5G network. Unlike in our work that focuses on ensuring the QoS in the datapath, they focus on reducing the signaling overhead and an efficient UP resource utilization. Moreover, their solution is still preliminary as it is simulated not implemented in a realistic 5G network.

Bektas et al. [152] propose a RAN network slicing scheduler for 5G, aimed to deal with mission critical services demanded by IoT verticals (e.g. Smart Grid).

In [153], the authors propose and validate dynamic network slicing for 5G IoT and eMBB services. Although they manage properly and dynamically the slices, their proposal assumes just two slices for the traffic profile, i.e. one for IoT traffic and the other for eMBB services. Similarly, the slicing architecture proposed by [154] evaluates one slice per 5G services types: mMTC, eMBB, or URLLC.

A software-based data plane programmability approach is followed by Salva et al. [155] to perform network traffic filtering for multi-tenant 5G IoT networks in kernel space. Like in our work, they follow an intent-based and SDN model for adaptive, flexible and network filtering in massive MTC scenarios demanded by IoT. Similarly, Matencio-Escolar et al. [5] implement a software-defined firewall for 5G NB-IoT networks to increase considerably the number of supported rules (up to one million), which makes it fully suitable for highly demanded mMTC services demanded by IoT scenarios. Despite these two work address the mMTC services requirements, they are not focused on QoS management needed for dealing with 5G network slicing.

A novel network slicing framework for 5G networks is presented and evaluated in [156]. The authors address specific challenges of media use cases, through an End-to-End QoS-aware slicing intended to support migration of mission critical services (eHealth tele-medicine services) to 5G networks. The proposed system implements Low Latency MEC Platform, with QoS control based on data plane programmability that allows establishing priorities of the 5G network traffic. Unlike our work which supports combination of either mMTC, eMBB, and URLLC services, they focus mainly on media use cases, with high demands in terms of low latency (URLLC services) and high bandwidth (eMBB).

Regarding network slicing solutions complying with the specifications and standards developed by the Standardization Development Organizations (SDOs) and the 5G Industry, Diaz-Rivera et al [157] propose a Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF) to enable the selection of slices in the data plane meeting the 3GPP functionality specifications [158]. The authors provide a functional validation although they do not report results on scalability or behaviour in IoT environments or 5G multi-tenant networks. This paper highlights the importance of providing an abstraction mechanism for network configuration due to the growing complexity of the data plane which is one of the strengths of our contribution (see *Data Plane Abstraction Service* description in section 12.5).

Network Slicing in industrial environments with extreme QoS requirements is a major challenge faced by the 5G industry and several contributions have been made in the recent past. In this regard, in [159] authors propose a method to perform network slicing for deterministic and packet-switched industrial communication protocols such as *OPC-UA*. Rost et al [160] describe a testbed in a real industrial environment, the Hamburg port area, where they deploy a 5G infrastructure with network slicing capabilities such as slice isolation, flexible slice customization and multi-tenancy. In [161], authors propose a framework aimed at providing network slicing capabilities to meet the specific requirements of Industry 4.0. The framework provides slicing through public and private federated infrastructures across Radio, Edge and Core segments. The framework is validated with 3 use cases: remote production monitoring, remote equipment maintenance and dynamic industrial manufacturing. Although promising, none of these works give results on scalability and performance and therefore do not demonstrate their suitability in the foreseen large-scale industrial IoT scenarios. They also do not cover multiple use case running simultaneously to demonstrate the suitability of slicing.

Efficient QoS-aware data plane network slicing in 5G networks has been recently implemented in hardware by Ricart et al. [7]. It provides hardware-based traffic classification, priority configuration, and traffic scheduling using NetFPGAs. Moreover, the framework deals with traffic with two levels of encapsulation (VXLAN, GTP) to support multi-tenant 5G networks and allows performing isolation for 5G MEC network traffic. Although the

general goal of that paper is similar to ours, they do not address the particularities of IoT scenarios, with thousands of devices and slices, as evaluated in our proposal.

Despite the considerable number of related work in the area of 5G IoT network slicing, practical, scalable and flexible software-defined networking solutions are still not sufficiently researched from the 5G data path perspective to satisfy various use cases of diverging requirements including not only massive IoT scenarios but also hybrid scenarios with heterogeneous IoT traffic profiles.

12.4 Network Slicing in Virtualized and Multi-tenant 5G IoT Deployments

12.4.1 Slicing Requirements in 5G-enabled IoT Networks

There are a number of specific requirements for adaptive network slicing in 5G IoT networks, listed as follows:

- **Multi-tenant support:** 5G IoT networks comprise virtualized network functions running over a shared physical infrastructure, which is exploited simultaneously by different verticals and operators. Therefore, the network slicing system should be able to handle encapsulated network traffic intended to differentiate the network slices and the associated SLAs per each tenant.
- **Mobility support:** as identified as a major challenge in 5G IoT slicing [144], the slicing system should be able to handle, differentiate, manage and control efficiently the GTP encapsulated network traffic needed to deal with User Equipment (UE) i.e., IoT device mobility. This includes handling the Uplink/Downlink traffic differentiating tunnels by the management framework and the slicing agent. Indeed, the slicing system should support nested encapsulation to deal with mobility and multi-tenancy simultaneously.

- **Scalable slicing for mMTC:** in order to support mMTC services, the slicing system should be able to handle and differentiate traffic coming from a vast number (millions) of different devices. It could imply managing and control efficiently thousands of concurrent network slices (in the most demanding case one slice per IoT device).
- **IoT service differentiation with high bandwidth requirements (eMBB services):** certain IoT verticals (e.g. video surveillance in Smart cities) might require broadband communications with high transmissions rates. The slicing management system should support subscription associated to high bandwidth requirements, and the slicing control system should be efficiently handle that kind of traffic.
- **IoT device differentiation with reliable and low latency requirements (URLLC services):** the slicing system should support the subscription, management and control of dedicated slices with ultra reliable low latency requirements.
- **Heterogeneous slicing support:** the slicing system should concurrently and efficiently support the control and management of heterogeneous network traffic and protocols demanded by different verticals, who may use any of the 5G services types including mMTC, URLLC and eMBB or a combination of these types in more demanding use cases.
- **Flexible and adaptive management:** the slicing system should be able to manage on demand and efficiently adapting the slicing of the evolving 5G IoT network traffic, and adding or decommissioning the slicing policies. This will allow upper cognitive layers in the 5G management framework to automatically update the network slicing behaviour according to the context.
- **Interoperability:** the system should be managed by a common, interoperable and high-level abstract interface, following a common data model intended to handling dynamically different kinds of slices for heterogeneous traffic.

12.4.2 5G IoT Multi-tenant Infrastructure for Vertical Businesses

This section overviews an infrastructure that perfectly matches the case of study in this paper and gives a realistic scenario to research and evaluate the proposed solution. From a bottom-up perspective, Fig. 12.1 shows four different network segments: (i) The Radio Access Network to connect individual devices to the 5G network. (ii) The Mobile/Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) segment to enhance the experience of end users when accessing common services through computing resource localization. (iii) The 5G Core Network segment with expanded service capabilities, scalability, agility and network functions. (iv) The Inter-domain Segment to reach the Internet and other domains managed by different organisations.

It is noted that the 5G architecture follows a Service Based Architecture (SBA) and builds upon virtualization and softwarisation paradigms. These technologies are expected to have a significant impact on 5G deployment as they aim to offer significant agility and flexibility to meet vertical industries' service requirements while providing multi-tenancy and user mobility capabilities in a common underlying infrastructure. That allows scenarios like the one presented in Fig. 12.1 where different verticals, each one imposing different network requirements (e.g., eMBB, mMTC, URLLC), are co-existing in the same infrastructure. To deal with such heterogeneity of the network, this paper proposes a Software-Defined Network (SDN) approach that is based on extending the industry-leading, production-quality OVS platform and allows controlling, managing and acting on complex network traffic (see Fig. 12.4) traversing these architectures. The objective is to guarantee the effective functioning of the vertical slices associated to each tenant/service through the whole 5G network. Specifically, we leverage the proposed 5G IoT Slice Management Framework to interact with this enhanced Open vSwitch to ensure that SLAs are respected.

12.4.3 5G IoT Slice Management Framework

To be able to provide dynamic adaptation of the network slicing capabilities presented in this research, a Slice Management Framework has been adopted as illustrated in Fig.

Fig. 12.1 Overview of the proposed 5G IoT Multi-Tenant Infrastructure.

12.2. The framework is composed mainly of five architectural domains. The arrows in Fig. 12.2 indicate the communication management among the different planes and their underlying modules. Roles and responsibilities of each component are described below, from a bottom-up perspective.

Infrastructure Domain

- **Physical Area:** It contains all the 5G hardware resources such as computes, storage and networking devices, among others, placed throughout the physical infrastructure able to be shared among the different tenants.
- **Virtual Area:** It contains all the virtualised equipment (created by the hypervisor) running on top of the physical computers that represent logical hardware resources assigned to specific tenants.

Control and Management Domain

- **Sensing:** It provides a common point to manage all the different sensors that report metrics about the current state of the infrastructure. Here, time-based metric reports are collected for monitoring purposes such as port speed, bandwidth consumed or bandwidth available at different points of the network.
- **SDN Controller:** It is the module that maintains a strategic control point in an SDN as the one presented here. From its northbound API (NBI) it receives the instructions to apply the business logic by controlling flows and programming networking devices placed on the data plane. In particular, this research proposes a new component in the data plane, the Slice Control Agent (SCA), which will finally be in charge of such programming of the network device. This is further explained with more detail in Section 12.5.1.
- **VNF Orchestrator:** It is in charge of the deployment of the different Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) by considering current physical and logical resources of the infrastructure.

- **VNF Manager:** It is a key component of the Management and Orchestration paradigm that works in concert with the VNF Orchestrator (VNFO) and/or the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) and it is in charge of controlling, managing and monitoring the VNFs' life cycle. In addition, it also controls Element Management System (EMS) and/or Network Management System (NMS).
- **Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM):** It controls virtual resources and the life cycle of all the virtual hardware resources in the virtual infrastructure. It also keeps the catalog and the inventory of the existing VMs.

Adaptive Slice and Orchestration Domain

- **Monitoring:** It monitors metrics provided by the Sensing module to perform highly scalable data storage.
- **Analyzer:** It allows the definition of rules that are used to monitor the current status of the infrastructure by using spatial and temporal correlation in the information gathered from both the monitoring component and the resource inventory. The rules produce alerts about specific events in the infrastructure that require attention.
- **Policy Planner:** It makes it possible to define templates that are used to transform the strategy indicated by the Slice Policy Editor into an ordered set of implementable steps required to implement the strategy received.
- **Orchestrator:** It receives an implementable plan and then orchestrates the execution of each of the steps involved in the plan in order to enforce it into the infrastructure with the purpose of resolving the alert.

Admin Plane

- **Slice Policy Editor:** Any authorized external agent that can reach the exposed functions by the framework to create, modify or remove network slices. Usually, vertical services administrators will define here their tailored configurations.

Fig. 12.2 Architecture of the cognitive 5G IoT Slice Management Framework.

12.5 Slice Control Architecture

Fig. 12.3 depicts a modular architecture divided in three different planes. First (on top), the **Infrastructure Management Plane** provides the slice policies to be enforced throughout the infrastructure. Next, the **Infrastructure Control Plane** is used as an entry point to apply traffic control rules to any of the programmable networking devices available on the network equipment by following the SDN principles. It is noted that usually this plane directly programs requested network control actions into a concrete networking device. However, as it is shown in this figure, we delegate this task to a proposed Slice Control Agent (SCA) (at the Resource Control Plane), to abstract particular slicing tasks and to homogenize technology-dependant syntax among different Flow Agents that co-exist in the network. To this end, at the lower end of the architecture, it is placed in the **Resource Control Plane**, where the SCA processes every received message and programs a given network equipment.

12.5.1 Slice Control Agent Architecture

The SCA consists of three main modules, SCA-API, SCA-Core, and the Data Plane Abstraction Service (DPAS).

- **SCA-API:** This module is the access point from/to the Infrastructure Control Plane. It consumes intent-based messages (further explained in Section 12.5.2) to apply actions at any location of the data path by exposing the NBI of the proposed service. When the SCA is instantiated, as a first step, it publishes its location and capabilities by using the discovery and catalogue sub-modules respectively. After that, it waits for new intent-based messages coming from its NBI. Additionally, the ACK sub-module publishes the result of any applied action over the data plane and the metrics sub-module provides behavioral information on the performance of a successfully applied slice.
- **SCA-Core:** The SCA-Core module processes incoming intent-based messages and manages the life cycle of the slices. It has the logic to dissect the packet representation structure into different sub-flows associated to each overlay network. The slice builder

Fig. 12.3 Network Slice Control framework architecture.

sub-module creates generic instructions to satisfy the slice requirements but delegates their implementation to other underlying modules that contain the logic for a specific technology. In addition, it also contains a metric sub-module in charge of calculating and sharing slice metrics by using its local database.

- **Data Plane Abstraction Service (DPAS):** The DPAS is a module that provides an abstraction layer to deal with the different network traffic control technologies (Flow Agents) registered as plug-ins. Through this approach, the SCA-Core does not need to know how each of these Flow Agents works, thereby achieving a modular approach where the DPAS communicates within a common language with upper layers of the architecture and thus in a technology-dependent manner with any plug-able underlying Flow Agent. The aim of this module is to select a proper Flow Agent able to apply slicing policy rules in a specific hooking point (data path point) of the host computer.

12.5.2 Intent Definition for 5G IoT Network Slices

The Intent-based Consumer sub-module, depicted in the upper left corner of the resources control plane of Fig. 12.3, conceptualizes the lower level details used to interface with higher level infrastructure control components and decomposes concepts in the technical details to enable following sub-modules to program a target networking device on the data plane. Messages reaching this northbound interface are composed of one or more **resources** describing the flows to take action to, one **intent** that defines which kind of action has to be applied over such flows (e.g. create a slice), and a list of **parameters** for fine-grained specifications (e.g, target network interface, mode, time, duration, etc.).

Listing 12.1 gives an example of a message that could be received at the NBI of the SCA to be processed. This particular example shows an intent-based message with three resources, the original network traffic flow plus two encapsulations. Each resource contains valuable information about its own/previous encapsulation details and some networking parameters with specific protocol fields/values that represent the network traffic belonging to what has been defined as a slice. To keep this example simple for brevity, Listing 12.1

just includes *srcIP* and *dstPort* but any other field of any other protocol (if present in the packet structure) would also be allowed here. Moreover, the *Intent* section indicates to create a new slice where all network traffic matching this specification will be forwarded by using a *OVS-based* Flow Agent. Three fields of the *Intent* define the QoS requirements of the slice: *Priority*, *Minimum Guaranteed Bandwidth* (MGB) and *Maximum Allowed Bandwidth* (MAB) and they are further explained in subsection 12.6.3. Finally, the section *Params* gives instruction to program this just over the interface *eth0*. It should be noted that Listing 12.1 just shows an example with the aim of simplifying the understanding of the structure of an Intent-based message, meaning that much more complex resources, type of actions, and fine-grain parameters are also allowed here.

```
1 {
2   "Resources": [{
3     "resourceId": "F8A4C949",
4     "encapsulationID1": "00000445",
5     "encapsulationType1": "vxlan",
6     "srcIP": "146.191.50.26",
7     "dstPort": "4789",
8   }, {
9     "resourceId": "B6E6B2B3",
10    "encapsulationID2": "8894D0D4",
11    "encapsulationType2": "gtp",
12    "srcIP": "10.100.0.19",
13    "dstPort": "2152",
14  }, {
15    "resourceId": "5A07C580",
16    "encapsulationID2": "8894D0D4",
17    "encapsulationType2": "gtp",
18    "srcIP": "192.188.0.140",
19    "dstPort": "5004",
```

```
20     }],
21     "Intent": {
22         "flowAgentName": "OVS-based",
23         "actionType": "INSERT",
24         "actionName": "CREATE_SLICE",
25         "slice_id": "03E8",
26         "priority": "1",
27         "MAB": "12000000",
28         "MGB": "10000000"
29     },
30     "Params": [{
31         "paramName": "interfaceName",
32         "paramValue": "eth0"
33     }]
34 }
```

Listing 12.1 Intent-based Message

12.5.3 Slice Control Agent Southbound: Flow Agent capabilities to enable Network Slicing in 5G IoT Networks and Open vSwitch extensions

5G architectures are based on softwarization and virtualization, using SDN and NFV paradigms as enabling technologies [104][103]. This allows different tenants to share the same physical infrastructure and, as a result, Telecommunication Service Providers (TSP) can reduce both Operational Expenditure (OPEX) and Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)[105]. Furthermore, each mobile IoT device has a dedicated logical connection to the 5G User Plane Function (UPF) to maintain connectivity across different networks. Therefore, controlling tenant isolation and device mobility are two crucial aspects of 5G IoT networks. In typical

implementation, device mobility is supported by encapsulating the original IoT traffic with GTP, and tenant isolation is provided by using other tunneling protocols such as VXLAN, GRE, STT or GENEVE.

Fig. 12.4 Double encapsulation in 5G networks for tenant isolation and 5G IoT traffic mobility.

Fig. 12.4 gives an example of double encapsulated 5G IoT traffic where VXLAN has been chosen to create a virtual overlay network for each tenant over IoT traffic previously encapsulated with GTP. The GTP encapsulation and decapsulation are performed by the gNB in the RAN segment and the UPF in the core segment. Regarding tenant isolation, the virtual switches that interconnect the virtual machines in both edge and core segments are responsible for the encapsulation and decapsulation of the overlay traffic.

This work adopts the definition of network slice proposed in [3]. The scope of this network slice definition is flexible enough to deal with all types of traffic that can be identified in a 5G network (such as those shown in Fig. 12.4) in order to meet the diverse QoS requirements that vertical use cases demand. In accordance with this definition, different slices can involve traffic with different levels of granularity depending on the use case addressed. For instance, a slice could be all the traffic of a particular tenant, the traffic of a vertical or, with a more fine-grained detail, the traffic of a single IoT device or even the traffic of a single service of a specific IoT device. In the experiments conducted to validate the proposed framework, a slice corresponds to the network traffic of a vertical, that is, the aggregate traffic transmitted

by all the IoT devices of such specific vertical. Nevertheless, It is worth highlighting that our proposal is able to cover the wide scope of the slice definition proposed in [3].

Therefore, to provide fine-grained network slicing capabilities, the first stage is that the Flow Agents that handle network traffic in the data plane must be able to access the inner headers of the packets and extract information about the IoT devices including Source and Destination IP addresses, Source and Destination Ports, etc. and their associated metadata including GTP Tunnel Endpoint Identifier (TEID) and VXLAN network identifier (VNI). This scenario is exacerbated since 5G networks are complex heterogeneous ecosystems where different technologies co-exist and network traffic is treated by many different Flow Agents along the data path, both hardware and software, such as virtual switches, NICs, FPGAs or physical routers and switches.

As mentioned in subsection 12.5.1, the DPAS module of the proposed SCA mitigates this problem by providing the upper management layers with a common technology-agnostic API in a transparent manner regardless of the network device playing the role of Flow Agent and the underlying networking technology used. In addition, Flow Agents are required to have capabilities to enforce in the 5G data plane the QoS policies imposed by the upper management and control layer through the DPAS API.

The results presented in this paper are focused on a specific segment of the 5G data plane, the software data path, which is the segment that provides connectivity between the different VMs of the tenants allocated in the physical hosts of the 5G infrastructure. The Flow Agent deployed in the software data path of the proposed architecture is named *Open Slice Virtual Switch* (OpenSliceVS) and it has been implemented by making significant extensions to the base version 2.9.2 of OVS [122], [123]. OVS is an open source multi-layer virtual switch widely used in virtualized environments where SDN/NFV technologies play a key role [104][103]. It provides OpenFlow capabilities to the SDN controller through the northbound interface. Since Linux kernel version 3.3, OVS kernel modules are available within the upstream Linux kernel distributions. OVS has become essential in SDN/NFV deployments and it is used in leading open source SDN/NFV oriented projects such as OpenDayLight [162] and OpenStack [163], among others. The following subsection provides an overview

of the OpenSliceVS architecture and the extensions implemented to provide support for flexible, fine-grained control of 5G IoT traffic and network slicing capabilities in the software data path of the 5G IoT network.

12.5.4 OpenSliceVS Flow Agent: Architecture and Implementation Details

The proposed prototype has been implemented by extending significantly several OVS features and functionalities in different modules throughout the OVS architecture, both in user and kernel spaces: traffic parser and classifier, flow and actions table, netlink communications between kernel module and user space daemon (DPIF), OpenFlow protocol, OpenFlow northbound API (OFPROTO) and command line applications interfaces. Fig. 12.5 shows an overview of the OpenSliceVS architecture, depicting the main modules in both user and kernel spaces. These are the main extensions implemented to the base version of OVS to provide network slicing support within the software datapath:

- **5G IoT aware Traffic classifier:** OVS delegates to the Linux kernel flow dissector module the extraction of the flow key that identifies a flow unequivocally. However, the Linux kernel does not support functionality to inspect protocol headers such as encapsulation headers or the inner headers of overlay traffic with several encapsulations that are expected in 5G IoT networks. To solve this, the prototyped Flow Agent has been enhanced with a new classifier that performs a deep inspection of the network packets, providing support for encapsulation/tunneling and other protocols not supported in the base version of OVS such as GTP, VXLAN, GENEVE, GTP and GRE. This new classifier allows re-entrance between headers that enable an efficient deep inspection of the inner headers of the overlay networks, gathering data about the tenants, the IoT devices and the verticals so that a fine-grained identification of all types of traffic present in 5G IoT networks is possible.
- **Open Flow tables:** The OpenFlow tables have been augmented with new fields that increase their expressiveness, providing a flexible, fine-grained slice definition that fits

the intend-based message received by the SCA from the management plane. These new fields enrich the semantics of the left part of an OpenFlow rule, including metadata about verticals, IoT devices and encapsulation/tunneling protocols.

- **Netlink protocol:** The inter-process communication between the OVS kernel module (*openvswitch.ko*) and the OVS user space daemon (*ovs-vsitchd*) is implemented using netlink sockets provided by the netlink Linux kernel interface. The netlink handler sub-modules (*DPIF*) and the user-defined netlink messages have been extended to provide support for 5G IoT slicing capabilities.
- **North Bound Interface:** OVS exposes an OpenFlow-based NBI, named *OFPROTO*, to establish communication with the upper management and control layers on the basis of SDN principles. The OpenFlow messages and the NBI functionality to send and receive such OpenFlow messages have been extended to address the new fields added to the OpenFlow tables.
- **Command line applications:** Finally, the command line application suite included in the OVS distribution has also been upgraded with new capabilities to allow the upper layers to manage slices in the 5G IoT software data path either by the command line or via a REST API.

To conclude this subsection, the integration between OpenSliceVS and the DPAS module (Southbound interface of the SCA) is achieved via a REST API that enforces the slice polices (slice definitions and QoS requirements) in the 5G data plane using the command line applications provided by OpenSliceVS.

12.5.5 Dynamic Management of the Life Cycle of a Slice in the Data Plane

A network slice is a dynamic entity, hence it is required a management of its life cycle as it has been outlined by Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) such as 3GPP [164], IETF[165] or 5G Americas[166]. The proposed framework offers to the upper control and

Fig. 12.5 Overview of the architecture of the OpenSliceVS software data path Flow Agent.

management layers, a novel mechanism to control the complete life cycle of a slice within the data plane aligned with the specifications developed by the SDOs. In this regard, a network slice instance can be in three different states as depicted in Fig. 12.6:

- **Creation:** Provision of the necessary network resources to ensure the performance isolation and QoS requirements of the slice.
- **In Service:** The slice has been successfully instantiated within the data plane and it is processing network traffic. In this state, the framework offers a dynamic change of the QoS parameters of the slice on request. This allows the network to adapt to the continuously evolving scenarios expected in 5G IoT use cases.
- **Termination:** Decommissioning of the network slice and releasing of the network resources attached to the network slice.

The sequence diagram provided in Fig. 12.7 details the logical steps involved in the process of creating a network slice, and how different components of the architecture

Fig. 12.6 Life cycle of a slice in the data plane. A slice can be in three different states: Creation, in Service and Termination.

Fig. 12.7 Sequence diagram describing the slice creation process and showing interaction between the actors involved: verticals, management plane, the SCA and the Flow Agent in the software data path (OpenSliceVS).

cooperate to finally ensure the overall QoS of the data plane for a vertical service. As seen in Fig. 12.7, the sequence diagram is divided (horizontal gray lines) in three different stages: *SCA Instantiation*, *Slice Creation*, and *Vertical Use Case*. Each of these stages commences with an event, produced either by the management layer or the involved vertical, which triggers a sequence of automated steps.

- **SCA Instantiation (Steps 1-5):** First, after the infrastructure management has triggered a new SCA deployment, the SCA-Core requests for a list of available Flow Agents (1). After that, the DPAS module provides such a list of Flow Agents, their capabilities, and their locations throughout the infrastructure (2, 3). Finally, the SCA-Core sends this information, through its North Bound API (4), to the external agent (5) so that the next stage can take place, which is the slice creation.
- **Slice Creation (Steps 6-15):** This stage starts when an external policy enforcer defines a new slice and sends an intent-based message for it to be enforced (6, 7). Next, the SCA-Core processes the message (8) and delegates to the Data Plane Abstraction Service (9) the task of building a technology-dependant message (10). At this point, the DPAS module selects a specific technology depending on the Flow Agent that is specified in the intent-based message, which in this example is OpenSliceVS (see Listing 12.1). In (11), a tailored and technology-specific instruction is sent to this Flow Agent to create and enforce the requirements of the new slice in the data plane. In the OpenSliceVS example, the creation of a slice comprises two phases. First, the slice definition is inserted as an OpenFlow rule into the *slice definition and action table*. Second, a hierarchical token bucket (HTB) queuing discipline configured with the QoS requisites of the new slice is created and attached to the network interface where the slice traffic will be redirected. Steps 12-15 are the way back up to the external SDN application so that it can be aware whether the network policy (the slice) has been applied.
- **Vertical Use Case (Steps 16-22):** This last stage begins when the service starts to be used (16) and its network traffic reaches a data-path point that has been programmed to satisfy the slice specific requirements. When a packet arrives at the Flow Agent, it is deeply inspected to extract data from the encapsulated inner headers (17 and 18). This data, named *flow key*, includes, among other details, information about the vertical ID, the source IoT device and the destination IoT service, which is essential to provide a fine-grained slice control. The *flow key* is then compared with the *slice definition*

and action table (19 and 20). If the search is successful, the packet is forwarded to the assigned slice, i.e., to the htb queuing discipline responsible for enforcing the QoS requirements of the slice (21 and 22). On the other hand, if the *flow key* does not match any defined slice, a default policy (drop, sent to management plane, etc.) is applied.

The interaction between the different architectural components to update or delete a slice instance is very similar to the one described in steps 6 to 15 of the sequence diagram in Fig. 12.7 and therefore, for simplicity, no sequence diagram is included. The major difference lies in the fact that, to update or delete a slice instance, the SCA does not have to process a large and complex intend-based message (steps 8 and 9 in Fig. 12.7). Instead, the SCA delegates the task to the Flow Agent by passing the slice ID that uniquely identifies the slice throughout the data plane. Subsection 12.8.3 provides an empirical analysis of the response time to handle a network slice instance in any of its states.

12.5.6 Alignment and Integration with 5G Industry Standards and Specifications

To conclude this section, it is worth to highlight that the solution proposed in this work is fully compliant and aligned with different standards and specifications developed by 5G industry and SDOs. Most of the efforts made by 3GPP are aimed at the design of a global standard for the 5G New Radio (5G NR), the air interface of 5G networks [167]. In this regard, our solution is deployed in the edge and core segments of the 5G network providing slicing capabilities across such network segments. Thus, it is complementary to 3GPP achieving an UEs end-to-end network slicing service. In relation to the 5G architecture proposed by ETSI which is oriented towards orchestration and virtualization aspects [168], our SCA module described above matches the functional description required for the component named *Network Slice Selection Function* (NSSF) in the ETSI specification. The main functionality of the NSSF is the selection of Data Plane network slices, which are created and configured with tailored QoS that fulfils the requirements of network users [169].

12.6 Vertical-oriented IoT Use Cases for Benchmarking

To validate and demonstrate the suitability of the proposed framework, this paper considers five realistic IoT use cases that allow to evaluate the system’s performance in scenarios where different verticals pose diverse requirements in terms of latency, data rate, reliability and scalability (number of IoT devices and number of slices). The characteristics and requirements of these use cases are listed in Table 12.1. As Fig. 12.8 illustrates, these use cases have been carefully chosen to cover the three general categories of services defined by ITU: eMBB, mMTC and URLLC [21] [170].

Fig. 12.8 ITU category for every vertical oriented IoT use cases for evaluation testbed.

Use Case	Use case 1	Use case 2	Use case 3	Use case 4	Use case 5
Use Case	Ambient monitoring in Smart Agriculture	Robot control in Industrial Automation	Sound analysis in Smart Cities	Video surveillance in Smart Buildings	AV-VR tactile application in Manufacturing Industry
Category	mMTC	URLLC	mMTC/eMBB	eMBB	URLLC/eMBB
Latency	High (>1s)	Low (<1 ms)	High (>100 ms)	High (>100 ms)	Low (<1 ms)
Reliability	Low	High	Medium	Medium	High
Priority	Low	High	Medium	Medium	High
Maximum Number of Verticals (Slices)	1000	100	24	40	24
Maximum IoT devices per Vertical	1000	2000	3000	100	20
Maximum total devices	10 ⁶	2x10 ⁵	72000	4000	480
Packet size transmitted by IoT device (Bytes)	128	256	1396	1396	1396
Double encapsulated packet size (Bytes)	232	360	1500	1500	1500
Packets per Second (PPS) per device	1	4	16	400	3300
Device Tx bandwidth	1.86 kbps	11.52 kbps	192 kbps	4.8 Mbps	39.6 Mbps
Maximum accumulated bandwidth	1.86 Gbps	2.40 Gbps	13.82 Gbps	19.20 Gbps	19.00 Gbps

Table 12.1 Vertical oriented use cases: characteristics, KPIs and traffic profile

A brief overview of these three categories of services for 5G IoT use cases can be given as follows:

- **eMBB**: It supports enhanced 4G broadband traffic characterized by large payloads, moderate reliability and high data transmission rates. A moderate number of IoT devices are connected to the same base station (BS) demanding stable communication over time.
- **mMTC**: It supports a large number of IoT devices connected to the same cell, intermittently active and sending traffic with small payload at a low uplink transmission rate.
- **URLLC**: It supports traffic that demands very high reliability and low latency as main requirements, with a relatively low transmission rate of small payloads.

12.6.1 Overview of the Vertical-oriented IoT Use Cases

Below we provide a description of every use case from a vertical point of view, underlining the QoS requirements demanded by verticals in real-world operations and the traffic profiles generated by the IoT devices, which are then emulated in our testbed:

- **Use case 1 (Ambient Monitoring in Smart Agriculture)**: Smart agriculture aims to provide crop development optimization by means of environmental monitoring services. It provides farmers with timely information for better management and exploitation of their agricultural facilities, leading to maximized productivity. Each vertical deploys a large number of IoT sensors in their farms to perform real-time monitoring and gather a range of climatic metrics such as relative humidity, air temperature, soil temperature, light, soil moisture, wind or rain detection, to mention a few [171]. The traffic profile is typically packets with small payload sent every few seconds where requirements in terms of reliability, latency and throughput are not a big concern. Since it is a mMTC use case, one of the major challenges is to provide connectivity for a huge number of low-power wide-area (LPWA) IoT devices sending traffic intermittently. The proposed

5G IoT framework has been tested in providing service to up to 1000 farms (verticals) where each farm deploys up to 1000 IoT sensors. Therefore, the 5G IoT network processes traffic from up to 1 million IoT sensors simultaneously connected.

- **Use case 2 (Robot Control in Industrial Automation):** In Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), often referred to as industry 4.0, robot automation processes are used to automate highly repetitive routine tasks traditionally performed by humans. Such tasks are now accomplished with high accuracy by robots in a faster and more efficient manner, eliminating errors introduced by human factors. This leads to a productivity boost and cost savings in time and money [172]. To test the proposed framework, we consider a smart manufacturing scenario where every vertical is defined as a smart factory using sensors and robots for material handling (picking and packing) and assembly tasks. NFV-based services located at the edge of the 5G network enable the automation of complex operations such as control and monitoring of the manufacturing process, resource and asset management or predictive maintenance. A system malfunction can have a negative impact on the overall network and therefore low latency and high reliability are crucial QoS requirements in this scenario. Such QoS requisites are characteristic of URLLC use cases. In this use case, 100 smart factories are simultaneously connected to the 5G IoT network. An infrastructure made up of 2000 IoT devices (sensors and robots) has been deployed in every manufacturing plant whereby each IoT device sends traffic at a moderate constant throughput of 11.5 Kbps.
- **Use case 3 (Sound Analysis in Smart city):** The adoption of IoT in urban environmental acoustics helps provide solutions for use cases such as noise control at public events (concerts, festivals,...), detection of sound patterns for crime prevention (shots, screams, breaking glasses), traffic status monitoring or audio surveillance by using keyword spotting. The information extracted from sound data gathered by the city-wide acoustic IoT network is further analyzed by speech recognition and sound analysis algorithms [173]. Local authorities can benefit from this information and improve the

quality of life of citizens in a efficient and cost-effective fashion. The scenario for testing the proposed framework consists of 24 cities, i.e. verticals. For every vertical, an IoT infrastructure comprising 3000 sound sensors has been deployed throughout the city, sending real-time ambient sound to the application servers located on the edge of the 5G network. The sound is encoded in MP3 quality at a bitrate of 192 kbps and sent in 1500 byte packets. The traffic profile of this use case fits in a hybrid mMTC/eMBB service.

- **Use case 4 (Video Surveillance in Smart Building):** Video surveillance in smart building combined with video analytics solutions is able to serve a wide range of applications such as crowd control, visitor management, lighting and HVAC control for efficient energy consumption or safety and fire prevention. Traditional video cameras are replaced by IP devices that send data-rich video to application servers that analyze the data and trigger the appropriate actions. In this use case, IP video cameras send full HD 1080p H.264 encoded video with a standard frame rate (30 fps), which means a constant video bitrate of 5 Mbps per IoT device (recommended configurations for video bitrate and resolution settings in [174]). The buildings play the role of verticals and the proposed 5G IoT architecture provides connectivity for up to 40 buildings with up to 100 cameras deployed in each building. The traffic pattern corresponds to a moderate amount of devices forwarding large payload packets at a moderate rate, which is eMBB traffic.
- **Use case 5 (AR-VR Tactile Application in Manufacturing Industry):** In a smart manufacturing context, augmented reality (AR) focuses on improving the interaction between humans and machines by allowing humans to access digital information through a virtual layer on top of the physical world displayed on visualization devices such a smart glasses or tablets [175]. The applications are diverse: live guidance for maintenance, training for assembly or warehouse operations among many others. The use of AR in industrial environments involves real-time video processing that demands high bandwidth as well as transmission of critical information about real-time

industrial processes that imposes extreme requirements in terms of reliability and latency. In our testbed, the 5G network provides coverage up to 24 verticals, i.e. 24 smart manufacturing factories. Each vertical is equipped with 20 AR units operating simultaneously in its premises requiring a bandwidth of 40 Mbps per AR unit. This is the most demanding of the five use cases, combining URLLC and eMBB features.

In a first set of experiments, in subsection 12.8.1, every use case has been empirically evaluated separately to provide an individualized analysis of the scalability and performance of the proposed solution when processing homogeneous traffic matching the traffic profile and QoS requirements demanded by the verticals for a specific use case.

Nevertheless, IoT ecosystems are fragmented by nature in multiple verticals with diverse requirements and, as a consequence, heterogeneous services are expected to coexist simultaneously in 5G IoT networks within the same physical infrastructure. Therefore, once the performance boundaries of each specific use case are known, in a second set of experiments, the proposed 5G IoT framework has been evaluated under heterogeneous traffic in a more complex and challenging scenario (see results in subsection 12.8.2).

12.6.2 Bandwidth Overhead due to Double Encapsulation in 5G IoT Multi-tenant Networks

As mentioned in subsection 12.5.3, the double encapsulation of 5G IoT network traffic is necessary to support tenant isolation and IoT devices mobility in multi-tenant 5G IoT virtualized infrastructures. On the other hand, the double encapsulation results in the network dealing with larger packets than the ones originally sent by the IoT devices. As a consequence, there is an overhead in the overall bandwidth that the 5G infrastructure has to process. The encapsulation process modifies the network packets by adding new headers at the beginning of the packets. The structure and size of these new headers are constant regardless of the size of the packets initially sent by the IoT devices. Hence, the smaller the packet size, the higher the proportional impact of the double encapsulation on the overall bandwidth and network resources needed to cope with the verticals' demands. In the experiments carried out in our

testbed, VXLAN and GTP are the protocols employed to perform the double encapsulation and 104 extra bytes are added to every packet (as a result of inserting the sequence of headers *MAC-IPv4-UDP-VXLAN-MAC-IPv4-UDP-GTP* at the beginning of the packet).

Use case	Packet size in Bytes Original / Encapsulated	Bandwidth overhead (Impact in %)
1	128 / 232	+ 81.25 %
2	256 / 360	+ 40.62 %
3,4,5	1396 / 1500	+ 7.44 %

Table 12.2 Bandwidth overhead due to double encapsulation process in relation to the original packet size sent by the IoT devices.

It is noted that in Table 12.2 for use cases 1 and 2, which send packets with small payloads, the impact of the double encapsulation in the bandwidth is significant: 81% and 40% respectively. Regarding the remaining use cases (3, 4 and 5), the increase in the required bandwidth is lower, 7.44%. It is worth highlighting that all results given in this paper refer to double encapsulated traffic within the 5G infrastructure.

12.6.3 Parameters for QoS Requirements of a Slice in the Testbed

In terms of performance, the needed parameters to set up a slice are three: *Maximum allowed bandwidth (MAB)*, *minimum guaranteed bandwidth (MGB)* and *priority*. The MAB and the MGB values determine respectively the upper and lower boundaries within a vertical is allowed to send traffic according to its SLA. A traffic rate above the upper limit would be a SLA violation by the vertical and it should not be permitted by the control and management layer under any circumstances. A traffic rate lower than the minimum limit may indicate an under-utilization of the provisioned resources and a revision of the network slices configuration would be useful to optimize the available network resources.

For the experiments conducted in our testbed (see results in sections 12.8), the slices have been configured using the expected bandwidth as a reference value to determine the MAB and the MGB parameters, assigning an interval of $\pm 25\%$ of the expected bandwidth to every slice. Fig. 12.9 illustrates this with an example for use case 5. For this use case, every single

Fig. 12.9 Maximum allowed bandwidth (MAB) and minimum guaranteed bandwidth (MGB) for use case 5 in a scenario with 24 smart manufacturing factories (slices) with 20 AR units per factory.

IoT device transmits at a constant data rate of 39.6 Mbps. In the more complex scenario with 24 verticals and 20 IoT devices per vertical, the expected bandwidth of every vertical is 792 Mbps. The accumulated expected bandwidth, i.e., the sum of the bandwidth of all slices that the 5G IoT infrastructure must handle, is 19 Gbps. Thus, the MAB and MGB for every single slice are 990 and 594 Mbps respectively ($792 \text{ Mbps} \pm 25\%$). Similarly, the accumulated values of MAB and MGB are 23.75 Gbps and 14.75 Gbps respectively ($19 \text{ Gbps} \pm 25\%$).

Regarding priority, this parameter is tightly linked to reliability and latency. On every interface, the traffic scheduler prioritizes higher priority traffic over lower priority traffic. Consequently, packets with higher priority are queued for a shorter time and are forwarded before packets with lower priority. The direct implications on high priority traffic when

compared with lower priority traffic are higher reliability (a packet is less likely to be dropped due to a full queue) and lower delay (due to lower queuing delay). It is noted that priorities are set differently depending on whether the traffic is homogeneous or heterogeneous. In the experiments conducted with homogeneous traffic in subsection 12.8.1, since all network traffic corresponds to the same ITU category, all slices have been set with the same priority and, hence, equally treated. Regarding the experiments with heterogeneous traffic, the priority of every slice has been set according to the latency and reliability requisites demanded by the use case (see subsection 12.8.2).

12.7 Implementation Details and Testbed for Experimentation

This section provides details about the testbed infrastructure deployed to empirically validate and evaluate the framework proposed, and the methodology adopted to execute the experiments and analyze the gathered results.

12.7.1 Hardware and Software Specifications for Testbed

The experiments have been carried out on a computer with the following specifications: 2-node NUMA architecture where each node was an Intel Xeon CPU E5-2660 v4 based on Broadwell architecture with 14 cores operating at 2 GHz and hyper-threading features. The system had a 128 GByte RAM and a 2 Terabyte SCSI HDD. The operating system was CentOS release 7.8.2003 running a Linux kernel version 3.10.0.

Regarding the virtualisation software, the hypervisor was qemu version 1.5.3 using libvirt version 4.5.0. The CPU provides a constant Time Stamp Counter (TSC) that allows, using the virtual Precision Time Protocol (PTP) hardware clock provided by the Linux kernel, a time synchronization between the host and the guests with a sub-microsecond accuracy¹.

¹KVM guest timing management: https://access.redhat.com/documentation/en-us/red_hat_enterprise_linux/7/html/virtualization_deployment_and_administration_guide/chap-kvm_guest_timing_management

This is needed to get accurate time stamping of network traffic in virtualized environments like our testbed infrastructure where events such as interruptions, process migrations or deep C states could lead to issues of time keeping in guest VMs. Therefore, the empirical results achieved in this paper are accurate and trustworthy with an error of the order of nanoseconds.

12.7.2 Methodology to Execute Experiments and Analyze Results

Concerning the procedure followed to gather results, all the experiments have been reproduced for ten times. The results in the best one and the worst one have been discarded to prevent outliers and, therefore, the results (delay, packet loss, bandwidth, etc.) shown in this work are the arithmetic mean of the eight remaining intermediate values. For every single experiment, network traffic has been sent for at least 30 seconds, mapping the use case traffic profile, the amount of IoT devices connected and the number of verticals. Based on previous test carried out, 30 seconds is a reasonable time interval to produce trustworthy and accurate results.

12.7.3 Testbed Infrastructure and Implementation Details

Fig. 12.10 illustrates the testbed deployed to carry out the empirical validation and evaluation of the 5G IoT network slicing capabilities of the novel proposed framework. This figure also shows the software artefacts in the testbed and the workflow to conduct each single experiment, starting when the vertical requests subscription to a network service until the data gathered during the experiment are analyzed to obtain empirical results. The testbed infrastructure consists of three virtual machines. The first VM (VM1) is responsible for a centralized management of the infrastructure, and thus accommodates the control and management modules described in subsection 12.4.3 and the SDN controller. VM2 and VM3 virtual machines host NF-based virtualized services that send and receive 5G IoT traffic respectively. Connectivity between VM2 and VM3 is provided by an instance of *OpenSliceVS*, the Flow Agent tasked with provisioning and enforcing slicing policies in the software data path segment of the data plane. Therefore, the results achieved in this work

can start to send network traffic to the virtualized IoT services allocated in the servers of the 5G network. Next, the ASDS agent sends to the IoT service in VM2 the traffic profile of the experiment (including the number of IoT devices, transmission bandwidth per device, payload size, etc.) (see 5 in Fig. 12.10). The NF service allocated in VM2 generates network traffic matching this pattern. This traffic is sent to the *OpenSliceVS* instance where the slicing is performed and the packets are forwarded to the IoT NF service allocated in VM3 (steps 6 and 7 in Fig. 12.10). Every single packet is uniquely tagged along the experiment by a unique 8-byte ID and its associated slice ID, both included in the payload. Once the transmission has been conducted, both IoT services, sender and receiver, generate a PCAP file that is reported to the ASDS (8 and 9 in Fig. 12.10). Finally, the ASDS agent compares the data of both PCAP files (timestamp, packet ID and associated slice ID) to obtain the empirical results of the experiment.

12.8 Empirical Validation, Evaluation and Achieved Results

In this section, we first provide an empirical evaluation and analysis of the scalability of the achieved performance in terms of delivered QoS (latency, packet loss and bandwidth) when dealing with homogeneous 5G IoT traffic. Next, the proposed framework is evaluated in a more demanding scenario with heterogeneous 5G IoT traffic where we focus on results about priority QoS requirements and performance isolation between slices. Finally, we provide results about the flexibility and agility of the system when managing the life cycle of a slice (provisioning, modification and decommissioning of a slice).

12.8.1 Homogeneous Scalability of 5G IoT Network Slicing

This subsection provides an empirical analysis of the proposed framework suitability when processing homogeneous 5G IoT traffic, i.e., network traffic from only one of the use cases introduced in Section 12.6. Since all network traffic is of the same type, all slices are

configured with the same priority and thus, equally treated with a round robin policy by the queuing scheduler.

Fig. 12.11 shows the system performance in terms of latency (average delay per packet) when ranging the number of verticals and the number of IoT devices per vertical for each use case. As it can be observed in Table 12.3, the latency requirements listed in Table 12.1 are fulfilled for all the use cases even in the most stressful scenarios (configurations with the highest number of verticals and 5G IoT devices). It is worth highlighting that, for the majority of the scenarios, the average delay is in the order of μs while for some of the most demanding scenarios it is slightly over 1 ms. Packet loss ratio is 0% for all the executed scenarios in all the use cases, and thus no graph is provided regarding packet loss.

Use case	Testbed configuration for the most congested scenario (Verticals and IoT devices per vertical)	Total IoT devices	Average delay (μs)
1	1,000 Smart Farms with 1,000 Climate Sensors	1,000,000	143
2	104 Smart Factories with 2000 Robots	208,000	133
3	24 Smart Cities with 3000 Sound Sensors	72,000	1054
4	40 Smart Buildings with 100 IP Cameras	4,000	955
5	24 Smart Factories with 20 AR Units	480	945

Table 12.3 Average delay per packet for the most stressful configuration for every use case

In use case 1 (mMTC traffic), the maximum measured delay is 143 μs when handling the emulated traffic from 1000 smart farms equipped with 1000 IoT climate sensors. Therefore, the proposed framework is able to cope with one million mMTC IoT devices with 0% packet loss and yield very low latency. These values are significantly lower than the requirements specified for this type of traffic in Table 12.1. Concerning use case 2, since it involves URLLC traffic, high reliability and low latency are strict requirements that must be fulfilled. The outcome of the experiments carried out on our testbed proves that the proposed solution is able to cope with both successfully: low latency (133 μs for the worst case) and high reliability (0 % packet loss). Unlike use cases 1 and 2, latency and reliability are not challenging requirements for use cases 3 and 4. Notwithstanding, the gathered results are beyond the requirements imposed by the verticals: maximum average delay of around 1 ms

(a) Use case 1: Ambient monitoring in Smart Agriculture. Up to 1000 slices and 1,000,000 IoT devices sending 1,000,000 PPS at 1.86 Gbps.

(b) Use case 2: Robot control in Industrial Automation. Up to 104 slices and 208,000 IoT devices sending 832,000 PPS at 2.40 Gbps.

(c) Use case 3: Sound analysis in Smart City. Up to 24 slices and 72,000 IoT devices sending 1,152,000 PPS at 13.82 Gbps.

(d) Use case 4: Video surveillance in Smart Building. Up to 40 slices and 4,000 IoT devices sending 1,600,000 PPS at 19.20 Gbps.

(e) Use case 5: AV-VR tactile app. in Manufacturing Industry. Up to 24 slices and 480 IoT devices sending 1,584,000 PPS at 19.00 Gbps.

Fig. 12.11 Scalability results when processing homogeneous 5G IoT traffic (average end-to-end delay per packet in μs). For each use case, the framework has been evaluated ranging the number of slices (verticals) and the number of IoT devices per slice. It is given the maximum number of IoT devices per slice, packets per second (PPS) transmitted and accumulated Tx bandwidth configured for each use case.

(significantly less than the 100 ms specified for both use cases) and 0% packet loss even though both use cases are tolerant to packet loss. Finally, use case 5 is the one that demands more severe requirements since its traffic profile corresponds to a hybrid URLLC/eMBB category. As with the previous use cases discussed, the proposed 5G IoT framework is able to guarantee the requirements imposed by the verticals of the use case 5: low latency (delay lower than 1 ms in the most stressful configuration with 24 verticals and 20 AR units per verticals) and high reliability (0% packet loss) whilst being able to process a high bandwidth inherent to eMBB traffic.

So far, the performance achieved in relation to latency and reliability has been analyzed. Regarding bandwidth requirements, Fig. 12.12 shows the accumulated bandwidth achieved for every use case. For clarity and simplicity, the results showed for every use case corresponds to the scenarios with the highest number of verticals (slices) when ranging the number of IoT devices connected to the 5G IoT network. The results gathered with fewer verticals are similar or even better due to the fact that these are configurations where the network is less congested. Three different areas can be observed in every graph. The central yellow area indicates the bandwidth interval for every slice. The upper green and lower blue dotted lines that delimit this area determine the values of the MAB and the MGB as described in subsection 12.6.3. The orange dotted line in the centre is the accumulated expected bandwidth used as a reference to calculate the bandwidth limits of the slices. Consequently, no traffic should be allowed in the upper green area as it is a violation of the SLAs by the verticals. Finally, the verticals can send traffic bellow the MGB (the lower blue are in every graph), although, as mentioned in subsection 12.6.3, it indicates an under-utilization of the provisioned resources for the slice.

The results shown in Fig. 12.12 demonstrate that the infrastructure is able to fulfill the bandwidth requirements for all the executed scenarios. In fact, for most configurations, the accumulated bandwidth measured matches pretty closely the expected one. Only for the scenarios with the higher number of IoT devices deployed in uses cases 4 an 5, the accumulated bandwidth achieved is bellow the expected one, but still within the guaranteed limits. Since the framework is dealing with homogeneous traffic where all the verticals (slices)

demand the same requisites in terms of bandwidth, it is expected that the 5G IoT network will treat all the verticals in the same manner. In a first approach to illustrate this system behaviour, we intended to plot the standard deviation of the achieved bandwidth per slice with a whisker plot on top of each bar in the bar graphs in Fig. 12.12. However, the standard deviation values calculated are so close to the arithmetic mean that, once plotted, they are imperceptible in the bar graphs. In a second approach to assess the system's behaviour in relation to this, we provide the ratio (in percentage) between the standard deviation (σ) of the achieved bandwidth per slice and its arithmetic mean (μ) for the worst execution of every use case (see annotations in green boxes for every use case in Fig. 12.12). This ratio is a good indicator of how equally slices are treated by the network in terms on bandwidth. From a statistical viewpoint, 95% of the values for the achieved bandwidth per slice are in the interval $[\mu - 2\sigma, \mu + 2\sigma]$. Therefore, the smaller this interval is, the more equally the slices are treated in terms of achieved bandwidth. The highest value of this indicator is 0.13% (use case 3), which indicates a good stability and robustness of the system. Even in the more congested scenarios where the accumulated bandwidth measured is below the expected one, the available bandwidth is distributed almost equally among all the slices with the same priority and throughout requisites (see executions with higher number of IoT devices in use case 4 and 5).

To conclude this subsection, the gathered results demonstrate that the proposed framework is able to meet the verticals requirements in terms of latency, reliability (packet loss) and throughput when dealing with homogeneous traffic where all slices match traffic with the same profile and requirements. The proposed solution provides good scalability while being flexible enough to adapt to the diverse requirements of the use cases analyzed in this work: it is able to provide connectivity for up to 1 million IoT devices in mMTC traffic, achieve over 15 Gbps bandwidth in congested eMBB scenarios or ensure delays in the order of μs for critical-missions communications (URLLC), providing high reliability in all of the tested scenarios (0% packet loss ratio).

(a) Use case 1: Ambient monitoring in Smart Agriculture. 1000 slices and up to 1,000,000 IoT devices sending 1,000,000 PPS at 1.86 Gbps.

(b) Use case 2: Robot control in Industrial Automation. 104 slices and up to and 208,000 IoT devices sending 832,000 PPS at 2.40 Gbps.

(c) Use case 3: Sound analysis in Smart City. 24 slices and up to 72,000 IoT devices sending 1,152,000 PPS at 13.82 Gbps.

(d) Use case 4: Video surveillance in Smart Building. 40 slices and up to 4,000 IoT devices sending 1,600,000 PPS at 19.20 Gbps.

(e) Use case 5: AV-VR tactile app. in Manufacturing Industry. 24 slices and up to 480 IoT devices sending 1,584,000 PPS at 19.00 Gbps.

Fig. 12.12 Accumulated Rx Bandwidth (in Gbps) when processing homogeneous 5G IoT traffic and safe slice boundaries for each use case. It is given the maximum number of IoT devices per slice, packets per second (PPS) transmitted and accumulated Tx bandwidth configured for each use case.

12.8.2 Heterogeneous Scalability of 5G IoT Network Slicing

The prototyped 5G IoT framework has also been evaluated in a more challenging scenario where traffic from the 5 use cases demanding diverse QoS requirements is competing simultaneously for the available network resources. Table 12.4 provides a breakdown of the heterogeneous traffic profile of the experiments conducted. The configuration of this scenario is a realistic example of 5G IoT traffic which is expected in a real-world 5G IoT infrastructure. As it can be noticed, the proposed framework has been tested with 432 slices sending traffic from a total of 280,920 IoT devices. In terms of bandwidth, the 5G network handles 1,404,000 packets per second (PPS), reaching a combined bandwidth of 13.83 Gbps whereas it has to ensure the verticals' QoS requirements committed in the SLAs.

Use case	Testbed configuration (Verticals and IoT devices per vertical)	IoT devices	PPS	Bandwidth	Priority
2 Industrial Automation	8 Smart Factories with 2000 Robots	16,000	64,000	0.18 Gbps	2 (Highest)
5 Manufacturing Industry	8 Smart Factories with 15 AR Units	120	396,000	4.75 Gbps	3
3 Smart Cities	8 Smart Cities with 3000 Sound Sensors	24,000	384,000	4.61 Gbps	4
4 Smart Buildings	8 Smart Buildings with 100 IP Cameras	800	320,000	3.84 Gbps	5
1 Smart Agriculture	400 Smart Farms with 600 Climate Sensors	240,000	240,000	0.45 Gbps	6 (Lowest)
	432 Slices (1 slice per vertical)	280,920	1,404,000	13.83 Gbps	

Table 12.4 Testbed setup for empirical evaluation with heterogeneous 5G IoT traffic. Use cases ordered by priority.

Unlike the previous experiments with homogeneous traffic, priority is a key QoS parameter when dealing with heterogeneous 5G IoT traffic in a more complex scenario where it is required to guarantee delay-sensitive and high-reliable services. In congested networks with high traffic load, packets are buffered before being forwarded, causing an additional delay. Moreover, if the buffer becomes full, packets are dropped. This fact might compromise the fulfillment of the QoS parameters specified in the SLA in terms of latency and reliability. Prioritization mechanisms address this issue by forwarding high priority traffic (demanding low latency and/or high reliability) before other traffic with less strict QoS needs. Table 12.5 provides a proposal on assigning priorities to different types of 5G network traffic. These values have been used to set the priority for the traffic of each vertical business in the experiments carried out in the testbed (see the fifth column in Table 12.4).

Type of 5G traffic	Slice priority
Network control and management	0 (Highest)
Critical communications	1
Delay-sensitive and high reliable URLLC traffic	2
Delay-sensitive and high reliable bulk URLLC/eMBB traffic	3
High latency mMTC/eMBB traffic	4
High latency eMBB traffic	5
High latency and packet loss tolerant mMTC traffic	6
Best effort	7 (Lowest)

Table 12.5 Example of proposed priorities mapping different 5G IoT traffic profiles

Fig. 12.13 Average delay per slice and use case (in μs) when processing heterogeneous 5G IoT from 280,920 IoT devices and 432 slices enforced in the software data plane by the OpenSliceVS Flow Agent.

Fig. 12.13 displays the average delay per slice for every use case when the 5G infrastructure processes traffic from all 5 use cases simultaneously. The data correspond to network traffic captured for 10 seconds in the testbed. There are several conclusions that can be drawn from this graph. Firstly, an average delay below 1 ms is achieved for all slices. Secondly, as expected, the traffic transmitted by the IoT devices of the use case with the highest priority (URLLC category) gets the shortest delay (around 200 μs). Furthermore, it can be observed that the slices of use cases with higher priority (2 and 5) obtain a rather stable delay

in comparison with the remaining use cases (the whisker box's height is lower). This fact suggests that the 5G network is honoring the priority parameter specified when these slices, with more severe QoS requirements, were enforced in the data plane. As a consequence, their traffic is treated with higher priority by the the Flow Agent, leading in a better delay performance and stability. To conclude the analysis of fig. 12.13, it can be noticed that the delay interval of the slices with less priority (use case 1 with mMTC traffic profile) is larger than the rest of the use cases. This interval measures the stability of the delay along the time (jitter). Results indicate that lowest priority traffic is buffered longer and forwarded with a more irregular pattern depending on the network congestion. It depends on how other slices with higher priority are consuming network resources. In the worst case scenario, the jitter varies roughly $250 \mu s$ (between 650 and $900 \mu s$) for use case 1 which is a more than acceptable value for this kind of use cases. Concerning reliability, as with the experiments conducted with homogeneous traffic, the packet loss ratio is also 0% for all use cases so no graph is provided in this regard.

Fig. 12.14 depicts the system behaviour in terms of bandwidth when dealing with 5G IoT network traffic transmitted simultaneously from IoT devices of the 5 different use cases. The results correspond to a 10-second interval where the average bandwidth per slice has been computed at 0.25 second intervals. It can be observed that, for all use cases, the proposed framework is able to deliver a guaranteed bandwidth service within the boundaries agreed in the SLAs between the verticals and the service provider. Regarding the number of packets, the 5G infrastructure has managed around 1,2500,000 packets for this experiment while the average overall bandwidth obtained is 12.36 Gbps.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the proposed 5G IoT framework has been empirically validated against a large-scale infrastructure. It is suitable to deliver networking slicing for IoT services with guaranteed QoS requirements in 5G networks dealing with simultaneous and heterogeneous traffic. The framework has shown very promising results in terms of the number of slices supported, and in terms of the bandwidth, delay, jitter and packet loss able to be warranted in the 5G infrastructure.

(a) Use case 1: Ambient monitoring in Smart Agriculture. 400 Smart Farms (slices) with 600 IoT sensors deployed in each farm, transmitting a total of 240,000 PPS. Total BW achieved: 0.360 Gbps.

(b) Use case 2: Robot Control in Industrial Automation. 8 Smart Factories (slices) with 2000 robots per factory, transmitting a total of 64,000 PPS. Total BW achieved: 0.184 Gbps.

(c) Use case 3: Sound analysis in Smart City. 8 Smart cities with 3000 IoT microphones distributed alongside each city, transmitting a total of 384,000 PPS. Total BW achieved: 3.986 Gbps.

(d) Use case 4: Video surveillance in Smart Buildings. 8 Smart buildings, each one equipped with 100 IP video cameras, transmitting a total of 320,000 PPS. Total BW achieved: 3.848 Gbps.

(e) Use case 5: AR in manufacturing industry. 8 Smart factories and 15 AR units operating in each one, transmitting a total of 396,000 PPS. Total BW achieved: 3.960 Gbps.

Fig. 12.14 Average bandwidth per slice for each use case in a scenario with heterogeneous 5G IoT traffic. The measured results correspond to a 10-second interval where 5G network traffic is simultaneously sent for 5 vertical-oriented use cases. The combined total bandwidth achieved is 12.36 Gbps

12.8.3 Performance Evaluation of Adaptive Slice Management

Since 5G IoT networks are dynamic ecosystems subject to continuous changes, one of the most challenging features that a 5G IoT slice control framework must address is the flexibility to adapt to such complex scenarios. This implies a quick response in managing network slices and provisioning the appropriate network resources needed to enforce the slices in the data plane and meet the diverse requirements demanded by verticals. Fig. 12.15 provides a breakdown of the time spent by the proposed framework in creating different number of slices when ranging exponentially the number of slices from 2 to 256. The given results refer to the time consumed in the Resource Control plane (see Fig. 12.3), i.e., since the NBI of the SCA receives an intend-based message from the SDN controller until the slice has been successfully enforced in the data plane and an ACK message is sent back to the management plane. This process corresponds to steps 6 to 13 of the sequence diagram in Fig. 12.7 as discussed in subsection 12.5.5.

Fig. 12.15 Empirical analysis of the scalability of the time required by the Resource Control plane to create a network slice (process the intend-based message and provision the necessary network resources).

Three architectural components are involved in this task: the SCA core, the DPAS module and the Flow Agent (OpenSliceVS). It can be observed that the major workload relies upon the Flow Agent. The Flow Agent is responsible for the insertion of the OpenFlow rule matching the slice traffic in the *slice definition and action table* (the orange stacked bar in

Fig. 12.15) and setting up the htb queuing discipline where the slice traffic will be forwarded and the QoS requirements will be enforced (the green stacked bar in Fig. 12.15). Meanwhile, the time required by the SCA module to process the intend-based message has less impact on the overall time spent to create a slice (the blue stacked bar in Fig. 12.15).

The gathered results indicate that the proposed framework needs 1463 ms to create 256 slices, resulting in an average time of only 5.7 ms per slice. Similar experiments have been carried out to evaluate the time to delete and modify network slices, obtaining better results than those when creating new network slices (an average overall time of 21% lower). For the sake of brevity, these results are not shown. To delete or modify a network slice, the SCA core does not have to process a full intend-based message, instead it just delegates to the Flow Agent the required action based on the slice ID reported by the external policy enforcer of the management plane, which is faster. Similarly, regarding the Flow Agent side, releasing network resources or modifying previously provisioned network resources is quicker than provisioning them from scratch.

Hence, these results prove that the proposed 5G IoT framework is able to adapt on demand to evolving IoT traffic, adding, modifying or decommissioning in an efficient way (just a few milliseconds) the slicing policies imposed by the upper cognitive management layers.

12.9 Conclusions

This paper has presented a highly scalable and effective network slicing framework for 5G IoT networks, following the software-defined networking approach. All the specific requirements to provide network slicing capabilities in 5G IoT infrastructures identified in subsection 12.4.1 are fully addressed by our solution. It is capable of supporting key 5G features including network function virtualization, multi-tenancy, and device mobility. It is particularly designed for massive machine-type communications and is able to manage thousands of heterogeneous slices concurrently. Furthermore, it supports other 5G use cases that require enhanced mobile broadband, or ultra reliable and low-latency communications, or a combination. Five 5G IoT

use cases covering these three ITU use case categories individually and collectively have been considered and their QoS requirements were abstracted to inform a realistic emulation in a testbed, where the proposed network slicing framework has been successfully tested and evaluated. Empirical results have highlighted the high scalability and performance achieved by this proposed system. In the tests, the implemented framework has been validated to be able to support mMTC traffic of up to 1 million IoT devices, achieve over 15 Gbps eMBB bandwidth, ensure delays in the order of μ s for URLLC, whilst providing high reliability in all of the tested scenarios with 0% packet loss ratio. Moreover, it takes only 5.7 ms on average to create a network slice in the data plane for challenging heterogeneous traffic situations.

Future work will investigate the application of the proposed solution in real-world 5G and beyond trials and evaluate the perceived quality of its performance for various vertical business applications. In addition, the integration of the OpenSliceVS Flow Agent with kernel bypass applications such as DPDK or eXpress Data Path (XDP) will be assessed in order to mitigate the performance limitations of the Linux kernel network stack and, thus provide improved key performance indicators (KPIs) and boost scalability.

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